

Deliverable 4.2 Socio-Economic, Demographic and Psychological Analysis

Project ref. no.	H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA N° 824326
Project title	Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women's inclusion in transport systems,
Project duration	1 st November 2018 – 31 st October 2021 (36 months)
Website	www.diamond-project.eu
Related WP/Task	WP4 / T4.2
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document due date	31 May 2021
Actual delivery date	31 May 2021
Deliverable leader	STIR
Document status	Submitted

Editors/Authors: Dr Yvonne Hail, Dr Anne-Marie Cullen and Professor Ronald McQuaid, University of Stirling, with input into the report and analysis from all partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1			Draft version circulated to partners
1.2	26/3/21	STIR	Draft version circulated to partners
1.3	21/5/21	STIR	Final draft version circulated to partners
1.4	25/5/2021	Aitec	Document Review
1.5	28/5/21	STIR	Final complete version
1.6	30/5/21	STIR	Validation
2.0	31/5/21	Project coordinator	Final check and submission

Executive Summary

Background

This paper is part of Task 4.2 in Work Package 4 and expands on the work already completed in Work Packages 2 and 3 regarding the analysis of data collected for the four Use Cases of the project and on other Deliverables in WP4. The following research questions guided this deliverable:

1. What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
2. How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?
3. How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
4. What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

Such document consists of 4 sections:

Section 1 sets out a brief definition of fairness as operationalised in the DIAMOND project and a working gender-based definition of women (based on D3.1).

Section 2 presents the mixed methods methodology used in this report. First, a scoping literature review adds to the existing literature already analysed in WPs 2 and 3 and Task 4.1, in order to develop concepts which will support the thematic qualitative analysis. Second, the report analyses the relevant socio-economic, demographic and psychological data developed in the project. This is based on both the quantitative (set out in D4.3 and so only briefly summarised here) and the qualitative analysis (which is reported in detail in this deliverable, D4.2). The conclusions of combining these different forms of analysis are then presented. Due to the Covid-19 epidemic, the qualitative research interviews were generally conducted over the internet.

Section 3 considers Questions 1 and 2 (above) on factors affecting women's travel choices and modal differences. It provides a synopsis of the literature found during the review and a summary of the results of the project's quantitative and qualitative research related to Use Cases I, II and III, i.e., women as users of public transport, women as users of autonomous vehicles and women as users of bike sharing schemes.

Section 4 considers Questions 3 and 4 (above) and investigates women's needs as employees in the transport sector. It specifically considers the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across the transport sector, especially women working on-site and off-site in the railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors. The main evidence presented in this deliverable is based on qualitative thematic analysis (based primarily on the fairness characteristics used in DIAMOND) of interviews with those working in transport sectors (at various levels) in the partner countries of Ireland, UK, Spain and Poland.

The qualitative findings set out in this report also help explore issues raised in applying the fairness characteristics and so also inform the wider DIAMOND project. Hence the qualitative data presented here (including the extensive quotations set out in the Appendices) will help to inform the remainder of the project by providing a resource to add to analysis and tool development in

the project. They also crucially, to give voice to the lived experience of the predominantly female people affected by fairness in transport.

Summary Findings:

The Fairness characteristics (as identified in WP3) are the core of the DIAMOND analysis, and the themes identified in this Deliverable support their appropriateness in the project. Generally, the key findings related to the Research Questions closely followed the Fairness Characteristics.

The results across the multiple research methods used suggest the following conclusions:

Research Question (RQ) 1:

The key factors affecting women's choices in relation to them as users of transport

- Safety and security
- Costs
- Facilities for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of public service
- For AV's specifically simultaneity, trust in technology

Research Question 2:

In discriminating between different transport modalities results suggest that in the main the high-level factors are similar across all transport modes, and that women are particularly interested and focused on safety and security, costs, frequency, accessibility, availability, which should be understood in the context of the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines.

For each individual mode (Use Cases), the RQ1 and RQ2 analysis suggested:

Public transport (UC 1) - The qualitative data analysis suggests that in relation to UCI, women as users of public transport, the most important factors affecting women highlighted across the analysis are as follows

- Safety and Security
- Lack of facilities for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of service
- Cost of travel

Additional factors which impact on women as users of public transport highlighted, but NOT corroborated by further analysis were listed as

- Travel Information Provided
- Facilities and comfort
- Service Provision
- Travelling with dependents

- Having a chronic illness/disability
- Capacity to travel to work.
- Overcrowding
- Air conditioning and ventilation

Autonomous Vehicles (UC II) - In relation to women's use of autonomous vehicles the qualitative and experimental data analysed suggest that the following factors are seen as important to potential women users

- Safety and security
- Simultaneity

The experimental analysis also suggested that the following factors were important, (although this was not supported by the data collected via the DAD survey)

- Accessibility
- Energy Efficiency

Further findings from the DAD survey, not corroborated in the experiments included

- Trust in technology
- Mobility
- Vehicle behaviour
- Environmental
- Cost
- Public health
- Emissions

Bike sharing (UC III) - Analysis of the quantitative data from the User satisfaction surveys the DAD and observations corroborated the following factors that are important for women using bike hire facilities

- Safety and security – including the provision of safety equipment and personal safety
- Availability of child seats
- The presence of cycle infrastructure
- Public awareness of the facilities

When examined together the interview and focus group data collected from both the UK and France corroborate the following key themes as barriers to women's use of bike sharing facilities

- Unavailability of bikes at the station
- Unavailability of docking points to return bike after trip.
- Distant docking stations from user
- Traffic safety and aggressive driving
- Inadequate and unsafe infrastructure

When the recommendations made by participants were analysed together, they corroborated the following suggestions as methods which could increase women's use of bike sharing facilities in France and the UK

- The availability of accessories for transporting goods and travelling with children.
- Increase the percentage of E-bikes in the fleet.
- Improve the design of bikes (height, low frame etc.)

RQ3: The job characteristics and contextual factors identified by the data as being important in terms of affecting gender balance and female employability in different areas in the transport sector (UC IV) were

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors
- Policy and Legal
- Female Facilities
- HR Policies
- Terms and Conditions
- Flexible Working
- Training Provision
- Safety and Security
- Negative Attitude of Colleagues
- Caring/Parenting Responsibilities
- Skills
- Educational Attainment

RQ4: To sum up the key factors identified by the data as being important in relation to women's career choices in the transport sector were

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors – recruitment and retainment
- Policy and Legal – employment policies
- Female facilities
- HR Policies – training and promotion
- Terms and Conditions – equal pay, shift patterns,
- Flexible Working
- Safety and Security – Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) etc.
- Negative attitude of colleagues
- Caring and parenting responsibilities
- Educational Attainment

Recommendations from participants are included in the relevant sections and annexes.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
LIST OF TABLES.....	9
TERMINOLOGY AND ACRONYMS	10
I. INTRODUCTION	11
1.1 DEFINITION OF FAIRNESS.....	11
1.2 DEFINITION OF WOMEN	14
2. METHODOLOGY	16
2.1 MIXED METHODS.....	16
2.2 SCOPING REVIEW	16
2.3 DATA ANALYSIS	18
2.4 QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS OF DATA.....	19
3. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS: KEY FACTORS AFFECTING WOMEN'S TRAVEL CHOICES AND THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TRANSPORT MODALITIES.....	21
3.1 USE CASE I WOMEN AS USERS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT	21
<i>Scoping Review Findings</i>	21
3.1.1 Comparative Data analysis Findings Use Case I	23
3.1.2 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices Public Transport	26
3.2 USE CASE II WOMEN AS USERS OF AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.....	27
<i>Scoping Review Findings</i>	27
3.2.1 Comparative Data analysis Findings Use Case II.....	28
3.2.2 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices AV's	30
3.3 USE CASE III WOMEN AS USERS: BIKE SHARING	31
<i>Scoping Review Findings</i>	31
3.3.1 Comparative Data Analysis Findings	33
3.3.2 Use Case III UK Interview Data.....	34
3.3.2.1 Key Findings Use Case III UK.....	37
3.3.3 Use Case III French Interview Data.....	38
3.3.3.1 Key Findings Use Case III France.....	41
3.3.4 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices bike hire facilities.	42
3.4 CONCLUSIONS	44
4. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS: KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CAREER CHOICES OF WOMEN IN RELATION TO WORKING IN TRANSPORT SECTOR.....	45
4.1 USE CASE I WOMEN EMPLOYED ACROSS THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	45
SCOPING REVIEW FINDINGS.....	45
4.2.1 COMPARATIVE DATA ANALYSIS USE CASE IV.....	47
4.2.2 FACTORS AFFECTING GENDER BALANCE/FEMALE EMPLOYABILITY (RESEARCH QUESTION 3).....	50
4.2.3 KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING CAREER CHOICES FOR WOMEN IN TRANSPORT (RESEARCH QUESTION 4)	59
4. CONCLUSIONS.....	68
5. REFERENCES	70
ANNEX I WOMEN AS USERS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT SCOPING REVIEW.....	74
ANNEX 2 WOMEN AS USERS OF AUTONOMOUS CARS SCOPING REVIEW.....	75
ANNEX 3 WOMEN AS USERS OF BIKE SHARING SCOPING REVIEW	76
ANNEX 4 WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT SCOPING REVIEW.....	77

ANNEX 5 NVIVO CODES USED FOR USE CASE IV	78
ANNEX 6 USE CASE III UK INTERVIEW DATA.....	82
ANNEX 7 USE CASE III FRANCE INTERVIEWS.....	92
ANNEX 8 USE CASE IV QUESTION 3 INTERVIEWS	101
ANNEX 9 USE CASE IV QUESTION 4 INTERVIEWS	125
ANNEX 10 MODES OF TRANSPORT REPRESENTED.....	143
ANNEX 11 JOB LEVEL AND TITLE OF PARTICIPANTS.....	144

List of Tables

Figure 1 Use Case I Themes Identified in D3.1	21
Figure 2 UC II Themes Identified in D3.1	27
Figure 3 UC III Themes Identified in D3.1	31
Figure 4 Use Case IV Themes Identified in D3.1	45
Figure 5 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics	87
Figure 6 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics	91
Figure 7 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics	97
Figure 8 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics France	100

Terminology and Acronyms

AVs	Automated Vehicles
DX.X	Deliverable
DAD	Dynamic Argumentative Delphi
EU	European Union
FGC	Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya
FCs	Fairness Characteristics
GIS	Geographic Information System
H2020	Horizon 2020
HR	Human resources
ITS	Intelligent transformation system
p. X	Page
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
RQ	Research Question
STEM	Science, Technology Engineering, and Mathematics
STIR	STIRLING University
UC	Use Case
VELIB	SYNDICAT MIXTE AUTOLIB ET VELIB MÉTROPOLE
WP	Work Package
UK	United Kingdom

I. Introduction

This deliverable builds on the literature reviewed in Work Packages 2 and the data collected in Work Package 3 and elsewhere in Work Package 4. It seeks to **develop further concepts which support the thematic analysis in Task 4.1 and answer the following research questions:**

- What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
- How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?
- How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

In this section we briefly consider aspects of the definition of fairness as operationalised in the DIAMOND project (see D2.2 and D3.1 for a full discussion), before providing a working definition of women which is based on gender as opposed to sex and is used throughout the DIAMOND project. In Section 2 the methodology section includes a discussion of mixed methods research processes, an explanation of the methods used to conduct the scoping review for each Use Case and finally provides a breakdown of the process of thematic analysis conducted on the interview data collected. The deliverable is then divided into two distinct parts, with Section 3 exploring the key factors effecting women's travel choices extracted from the data and section 4 considering the key factors identified which influence women's career choices in relation to working in transport. New qualitative data is also provided in the Appendices.

I.1 Definition of Fairness

Women generally, and different groups of women specifically, can have complex mobility patterns in comparison to men e.g., mothers and older women report taking shorter commuting times but more journeys than men (McQuaid and Chen 2012; Madariaga 2013; Houston and Tilley 2016; Hanson 2010). It is also claimed that current transport systems do not always take these gendered differences into account when either planning or delivering services. Additionally, for many women driving private vehicles modelled on the general physicality of men has also created issues with regards to seating, posture and the seatbelt safety; while self-driving cars may use algorithms based on databases which reflect past biases in car use rather than fairness across the potential population of users (*for a full view of discussion see Deliverable 2.2 of DIAMOND*).

Fairness can be a vague and somewhat ambiguous concept which can evolve and change over time and space and can be based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences. This makes any attempt at producing a universal definition a difficult process. The terms "fairness" and "justice" tend to be used to describe both how decisions are made and how individuals are treated within a community. Throughout the wider literature the notion of fairness is closely related to the concepts of **justice, equity and human rights**. Hence fairness needs to reflect access or opportunity to use the transport system, but also the distribution of benefits across the transport system.

A key issue relevant to the broader definition of “**fairness**” relates to equality and there are two ways in which equality impacts on fairness in relation to transport: equality of opportunities and equality of outcomes (Hail and McQuaid 2021). Both are sometimes intertwined, but for this deliverable we will separate them. In the context of the fairness for women as transport users, equality of opportunity can be seen to relate to such issues as accessibility to suitable transport services. Equality of opportunity can therefore be defined as a state of fairness in which all groups of people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices, unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except when they can be explicitly justified for example cheaper fares for young or low-income people (see for instance, Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy). In other words, equality of opportunity should provide fair and equal opportunities for people with a variety of different characteristics to access a safe, secure, effective, and efficient transport systems that meets their daily needs.

Even if such formal equality of opportunity (and lack of formal discrimination) between groups exists, there may be a need for substantive equality of outcomes where indirect discrimination may exist. For instance, those who have primary responsibilities for young children when travelling should have full access to services (e.g., when using pushchairs). This ‘fair access’ should be the case irrespective of the sex of the person responsible for the child, but in most cases, this would be a woman. Hence this particular barrier mainly, (but not solely) affects women and under the umbrella of equality of opportunity, a ‘fair’ transport system would seek to remove the barrier. In contrast to equality of opportunity, the equality of outcome approach “focuses attention on the outcomes or end results of policies and programmes, imposing an expectation that an absence of inequity of any sort would be a hall-mark of a fair system” (Bowling 2007:23).

For both Litman (2018) and Gullo et al. (2008) fairness in relation to transport mainly relates to equality of opportunity as without adequate transport, access to education or employment is difficult, which further impacts income equality. Litman (2018) separates the concept of equity into two separate types, horizontal which relates to the egalitarian concept of equal treatment of equals and vertical equity which is related to social justice and social inclusion and focuses on the difference (in ability or need) between and within groups, i.e., transport policies which favour disadvantaged groups such as people with disabilities.

Lee, Sener and Jones (2017) introduce five separate types of equity, which they argue are related specifically to fairness with regards to public use of and access to public transport.

- **Social equity** – analysis of social groups and is measured using variables based on income, race, sex and age etc.
- **Spatial equity** – is a geographical level of analysis which looks to examine where the inequality is taking place, this is important in relation to transport policy planning “because the effects of public policies tend to cluster around specific physical locations” (p. 213)
- **Procedural equity** – is associated with equity in the policy making process as opposed to the outcome of policy, in the case of transport policy planning procedural equity is related to having fair and equal evaluations included in the policy making decision.
- **Modal equity** – is related to ensuring that there is safe access for all groups to the range of local transport modes, the example provided is that “because walking and bicycling have higher

mortality rates from vehicle accidents than driving, modal equity strategies would seek to restrict driving in order to slow or reduce vehicle traffic” (p. 215)¹

- **Distribution equity** – is linked to how transportation costs and benefits are distributed across society, currently this is evaluated for fairness by examining the accessibility to transport infrastructures which excludes any evaluation of how safely and easily people can travel to the station.

Pereira, Schwanen and Banister (2017) use the theoretical frameworks of Rawls’ egalitarianism and Sen’s Capability Approaches to argue that distributive justice concerns over transport disadvantage and social exclusion should focus primarily on accessibility as a human capability. This suggests that transport policies (and perhaps Toolboxes such as developed through DIAMOND) should explicitly consider their *distributional effects* and also set minimum standards of *accessibility* to key destinations. Policies should also prioritise disadvantaged groups, reduce inequalities of opportunities and mitigate transport externalities, while respecting individuals’ rights. They argue that a fair distribution of accessibility should include “firstly, that individuals’ basic rights and liberties should never be violated or sacrificed on the grounds of improving the accessibility levels of others. Secondly, a transport policy is fair if it distributes transport investments and services in ways that reduce inequality of opportunity. While aiming to enhance overall levels of accessibility, policies should prioritise vulnerable groups and thereby mitigate morally arbitrary disadvantages that systematically reduce their accessibility levels, such as being elderly, disabled, or born in an ethnic minority or poor family” (p. 184). This approach supports the setting of minimum standards of accessibility to key destinations, guaranteed by governmental social or transport policies. Lucas, van Wee and Maat (2015) further argue that fairness in transport involves access to opportunities to participate in activities, that an individual values, at a minimum level (such as health, employment, and education).

For a fair exchange the benefits must come back, in some way, to the users and potential users of transport (distributional issues). For example, an equitable exchange between the government (giving subsidies) and rail companies must also take into account train passengers *and* those suffering externalities (like noise or air pollution) *and* non-users (who may be put off travelling due to timetables or costs etc.). Fairness also must be accompanied by good governance, high levels of accountability and of transparency to all interested groups. This means taking account of the social costs and benefits, as well as financial ones, of poor transport (Social Exclusion Unit 2003).

A working **definition of fairness** for the DIAMOND project is a state in which people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices or unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except they can be explicitly justified.

The themes identified in this deliverable are to support the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the project surveys (including focus groups/ interviews). The themes highlight measures of unfairness that reflect revealed unfairness through actual behaviour (e.g., time travel to work, as a longer time may reflect fewer job opportunities in general); or perceptions (e.g., security fears, although these may or may not reflect actual risks); or direct perceptions (e.g., feelings of

¹ This can be extended to considering the effects of using modes (e.g. the consequences of accidents at different speeds on pedestrians) and which may disproportionately affect certain groups (e.g. children). It is partly the basis for introducing lower speed limits (e.g. around 30km/h) in many cities, such as Edinburgh in Scotland.

discrimination). Based on the Grant Agreement, previous WPs, and the literature review below, three main fairness themes related to transport systems which are inclusive of all demographic factors such as age, disability and ethnicity are identified as listed below:

- **Capable of meeting required needs of people.** In relation to people’s job roles, flexible working, training etc. ability to travel in an appropriately designed transport system, meeting basic expectations and being environmentally sound
- **Accessible.** Ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value; accessible to all groups also in terms of design and comfort provided, e.g., those with children, and in terms of fares and costs for those with lower income, including distribution of costs and benefits; all people can fairly access jobs for which they are suitable
- **Safe and Secure.** Ability to travel or work safely and securely for all type of users

Under each Use Case factors are identified that are particularly important, or where there are significant gaps in research.

From this perspective inequitable or unfair transport policies and planning can have diverse and significant impacts on various groups at various times in relation to individuals’ economic and social opportunities (see D2.2 for a DIAMOND definition of fairness). Although the focus of this project is fair access for women, ‘fairness’ applies to all people, but certain types of unfairness disproportionately affect people with certain characteristics, in particular, women or groups such as women with young children.

1.2 Definition of women

The DIAMOND project has adopted a broad working definition of women for this project which is underpinned by the acknowledgement that gender (as opposed to only the biological sex class definition of women) is a social construction which changes over time and space (Guenther, Humbert and Kelan 2018). From this perspective gender is understood as the specific cultural meaning attached to the roles of men and women across and within societies. In the main gender looks to explain, in a rigid societal framework, the social norms, attitudes, and activities that each culture deems appropriate for one sex over the other at a specific moment in time (Koester 2015). Gender ideology therefore contains an innate power structure with reference to the public and private lives and experiences of women and girls’ which impact on their role in the workplace, the academy, sports, and the arts (Scott 2018). The power imbalance associated with societal gendered roles has led Koester (2015) to described gender as the “most persistent cause, consequence and manifestation of power relations” (ibid 2015:1) globally. By providing a gendered distinction between men and women, Koester argues we are also identifying and labelling power and powerlessness. Therefore, when we explore the barriers and facilitators faced by women employed in and using public transport, we must also acknowledge the wider societal inequalities associated with their gender identity. Employing a gender focus in the project opposed to biological sex class also allows us to collect data from biological women and those who self-identify as women and live their life as a woman. Recognising that there are different legal and other definitions and recognitions across the EU and elsewhere, the general definition of women adopted by the DIAMOND project is based on the broad concept of gender as a social construction which changes over time and space and allows us to examine the varying experiences of women.

Women are also not a homogeneous group, with each women's lived experience being shaped by, amongst other things, their social class, their ethnicity, and their geographical location as well as by age, childcaring responsibilities etc (Oliveira and Nisbet 2018). In order to capture the experiences of a wide selection of women for this project we have developed an intersectional approach to our analysis and designed our research instruments to record demographic data such as ethnic background, ability/disability, and social class. Therefore, whenever we talk about women in this study, it is done so with an understanding of the complexity of women's multiple social identities.

2. Methodology

In order to ensure we captured the most robust literature which would sit alongside our common framework as set out in D3.1 and help to support our research on fairness in relation to women accessing and using transport, we conducted a scoping review of scientific literature in a systematic manner to identify relevant research exploring the current **facilitators** and **barriers** faced by women to help define a clear set of evaluation criteria and possible recommendations for organization to mature in the fairness of the service provided and or in the employment conditions offered.

2.1 Mixed methods

Overall, the research has taken a mixed methods approach where both quantitative and qualitative methods, and various types of qualitative and quantitative approaches, have been integrated where possible (for a fuller description of methods used see D4.1 section 2). This recognises that there are strengths and weaknesses with every method, but we have sought to build on complementary strengths and avoid overlapping weaknesses of the different methods used (Danzin, 2012; Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

While both quantitative and qualitative methods “differ in their philosophical assumptions and, consequently, the ways in which they go about collecting data and making sense of data, their ultimate task and aims are the same: to describe their data, construct explanatory arguments from their data, and speculate about why the outcomes they observed happened as they did”. Sechrest and Sidani (1995, p.78).

Mixed methods approach has helped triangulate our results, i.e., combining different insights from different approaches (and expanding our understanding of findings by combining different approaches) and so increasing the rigour and confidence in our findings when they are supported or convergent validated by other methods.

The mixed methods used was both sequential: qualitative focus groups helped identify issues that were considered in the quantitative analysis (e.g., on the fairness characteristics) and then qualitative webinars were used to explore some of the quantitative results. Also, the quantitative and qualitative methods were used in parallel as the key Research Questions were explored in parallel, using different approaches.

The descriptive results are brought together in D4.2, with in-depth quantitative analysis presented in D4.3 and the main results integrated in D4.4. However, to avoid excessive duplication and to ensure the coherence of the results in D4.3, we do not repeat the full descriptive quantitative results in the current deliverable.

2.2 Scoping Review

Due to resource constraints, it was not possible to conduct a full systematic review as per either the Cochrane or Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) frameworks and we therefore conducted a scoping review of current literature. Scoping reviews are in the main utilised to provide a descriptive overview of a corpus of literature when there is limited time and or resources available to conduct a full systematic review and the topic under review is a new concept (Pham et al. 2014). In the

main, scoping reviews are utilised in order to examine and map the range of research in a specific area and to identify research gaps in the existing literature (Mays et al. 2001). It is also claimed that utilising a scoping review to explore the wider academic literature provides additional value particularly when authors are looking to produce “evidence to inform practice” (Munn et al. 2018:3) as we are in this deliverable, rather than collating empirical evidence. A scoping review is also suitable as we are not looking to “produce a critically appraised and synthesised result/answer to a particular question” (Munn et al. 2018:3) but to map and identify current research which examines the barriers and facilitators to women using public transport.

Scoping reviews as a method of literature review employ many of the same processes as systematic reviews, they both use rigorous and transparent methods to identify and the relevant literature pertaining to a research question (Pham et al., 2014). The framework for conducting a transparent and rigorous scoping review listed by Arksey and O’Malley (2005) as the following steps: identifying the research question; utilising wider search terms than typically used in a systematic review to gather a wider range of literature; identifying relevant studies; study selection; charting the data; collating; summarizing; and reporting the results.

Following this framework and before the search for documents began, the authors established the search terms to be used for the literature search and the inclusion and exclusion criteria that would be used to distinguish documents of relevance.

The inclusion framework for documents for this deliverable was based on:

- English language documents
- Both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies
- Publication date 2000 or later
- A focus on the sex and/or gender in relation to transport users
- Field work being conducted in either, Europe, North America, Australia and New Zealand, as the main interest is in the EU.

The exclusion framework included:

- Papers where the field work was conducted in developing countries.
- Papers which referred to transport users but did not disaggregate by sex and/or gender.
- Papers published before 2000.

In addition, some other papers were identified using expert knowledge and contacts. To identify relevant documents, the University of Stirling data base management systems were searched and included WOS, BCI, CCC, DRCI, DIIDW, KJD, data bases in February 2020. Using the following search terms:

- **Women + public transport + users + NOT drug users (see Annex 1 for a ‘search tree’ diagram).** This resulted in the return of 188 documents, which was reduced to 176 when duplicates documents were removed. A further 74 documents were excluded as not suitable after reviewing the abstracts and conclusions of each document. 102 documents were then fully assessed for eligibility before a further 90 were deleted resulting in the inclusion of 12 documents suited to the paper.

- **Autonomous + Cars + women (see Annex 2 for a ‘search tree’ diagram).** This resulted in the 15 papers being identified. An additional two papers were found via snowballing from the original papers. There were 17 documents after duplicated documents were removed. These were then screened, and 6 further documents were removed as not being suitable. 11 documents were fully assessed for eligibility and a further 5 documents were removed as not being suitable. This resulted in 6 documents being identified as suitable for the paper.
- **Bike (Bicycle) sharing + Women + Users (see Annex 3 for a ‘search tree’ diagram).** This resulted in 15 documents were identified, 5 additional documents were found by snowballing the references of the original documents identified. After removing duplicate documents there were 20 documents. These 20 documents were then screened, and a further 7 documents were removed as not being suitable. The remaining 13 documents were assessed fully, and no further documents were removed which resulted in 13 documents being identified as suitable.
- **Employment Women – fairness – employment; (see Annex 4 for a ‘search tree’ diagram).** This resulted in 454 documents being identified, 253 documents were removed as duplicates or not meeting parameters, 201 records were screened, 82 further papers were excluded, 119 full text articles were assessed, 61 further articles were removed leaving 58 documents.

The documents retrieved were grouped under three separate headings, documents relating to existing barriers and facilitators for women on general public transport, train travel and bike sharing schemes. The original search and exclusion of documents was conducted by one of the authors, once the documents had been reduced the final selection was then reviewed by both authors before a consensus was made on the final document choice.

A list of documents, locations and publication details are set out in Annexes at the end of this deliverable.

The scoping review of the wider academic literature relating to women as employees in and users of public transport was conducted to supplement the initial literature review which took place in Work Package 3. Based on the importance of the issues raised together with an acknowledgement of the current gaps in the research, three high level **themes** were identified for each Use Case:

- **Capable of meeting required needs.** i.e., ability to access employment and services that people have reason to value.
- **Accessible.** i.e., access to employment and/or transport systems that is fair to all groups (e.g., income, ethnicity, age, those with childcare etc.) including the distribution of costs and benefits.
- **Safe and Secure.** i.e., ability to work and/or travel safely and securely.

2.3 Data Analysis

Within WP4 and Task 4.2 specifically we have utilised the outcomes of previous data collections from across the four Use Cases.

- Use Case I women as users of public transport,
- Use Case II understanding women’s emotional needs in autonomous vehicles.

- Use Case III women as users of bike sharing facilities and
- Use Case IV women employed across the transport sector.

This has included reviews, questionnaires, semi structured interviews, and focus groups to develop a self-evaluation tool to support transport organisations in providing fair access to transport services and employment for women in the field. The aim for the maturity tables is to list and address the essential steps that are required to be put in place by transport organisations to assist them in the diagnosis and identification of their current fairness maturity level and highlight possible areas for further improvement. The literature review and the data collected from qualitative interviews also lead to compiling a suggestion box with possible fairness improvement measures to enable organisations to establish their current level of maturity and the actions required to reach the next level.

The details of the socio-economic, demographic and psychological span the quantitative analysis set out in D4.3 (only a brief summary is included here) and the qualitative, mainly interview data, set out in more detail in this deliverable (D4.2). Specifically, the quantitative analysis of the User Satisfaction surveys, and the Dynamic Argumentative Delphi Analysis are described fully in D4.3 and are not repeated here.

This task also considered data collected from the interviews/focus groups of the case studies carried out in WP2 and WP3 that sought to collect best practices and suggestion on how to improve each area of fairness to achieve better level of maturity in the inclusiveness of the service and or employment provision.

In addition, focus groups and others forms of data gathering were used to collect views from a wide range of professionals and users of transport (building on D3.1 and D3.3, and especially D4.1). These were multi-level in terms of including Warsaw city, Catalonia region, and the UK and Ireland at the country level.

2.4 Qualitative Data Analysis of Data

Thematic analysis, as implied by the name, is a framework or matrix method of identifying, extracting and synthesising key themes contained within qualitative data (Bryman 2012). Key themes are identified in terms of their repetition across multiple sources of data and can include, but are not limited to, metaphors and analogies or linguistic connections (Bernard 2003).

A top-down approach is being taken to the data analysis with the data firstly being divided by case nodes which will identify each country, gender, age and all other demographic information of participants to allow us to provide a descriptive analysis based on disaggregated data for women and the association between different socio-economic and psycho-ethno-anthropological characteristics including different objective and subjective measures as set out in Part A of the grant agreement (page 19).

The process

All interviews and focus group data have been transcribed verbatim and edited where appropriate, to allow them to be uploaded to the NVivo software package used for qualitative data analysis. The NVivo software is based on creating nodes to code themes from interview transcripts. A node

is a collection of references about a specific theme (e.g., safety for women travelling at night), cases are units of analysis, in this context individual research participants. The coding of qualitative data is a fundamental part of the analysis process as it allows researchers to be able to organize and make sense of data that have been collected and allows us to begin conceptualising the data (Bryman and Burges 1994).

The general rules of thematic analysis for qualitative data, is that there are two methods of coding; one to support retrieval of text segments which relate back to the research questions and open coding for the generation of themes emerging from the text, (Richards and Richards 1991; Bryman and Burges 1994; Bryman 2008). With this in mind, we have developed 2 sets of codes for each Use Case to ensure we captured both the relevant data to answer the research questions and importantly, the themes that were emerging from the data as per the central principle of grounded theory, where we as researchers can construct a new theory that is “grounded” in that data that has been systematically obtained and analysed using comparative analysis (Tie et.al. 2019).

The nodes created for each Use Case were developed using the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) as set out in Work Package 3 D3.1. The FC’s themselves were developed using the findings from a thematic analysis of wide-ranging literature review (see D3.1 for full details) and further supplemented by the data collected from focus group discussions which explored the definition of fairness in relation to women in transport (see D3.1 section 1.1.2). The nodes developed were therefore based on the project definitions of fairness in relation to women as users and employers of transport, the barriers faced by women, the facilitators that helped to support women and any recommendations they made regarding increasing fair opportunities for women in transport. Due to the Covid-19 epidemic, interviews were generally conducted over the internet.

A thematic framework was employed using the same categories of nodes across all the data to provide a robust analysis (**see Annex 5**). This framework was discussed and agreed between the researchers conducting the analysis with ideas generated and documented through each stage of interaction with data. Frameworks for Use Case I and Use Case IV were also sense checked between partners at STIR and TUD to ensure they were valid to the project.

Partners from Spain and Poland provided STIR with summary reports of their interviews/focus groups which have been analysed using the same coding framework as the UK and Irish data where possible.

The extensive quotations are meant to be used as a resource for informing other parts of the project and readers and, crucially, to give voice to the lived experience of the predominantly female people affected by fairness in transport (**see Annex 6 for Use Case III UK; Annex 7 for Use Case III France and Annex 8 & 9 for Use Case IV**).

3. Summary of Findings: Key Factors Affecting Women's Travel Choices and the Difference Between Transport Modalities

This section starts by providing a synopsis of the literature found during the review and a summary of the results of the project's quantitative and qualitative research related to Use Cases I, II and III, i.e., women as users of public transport, women as users of autonomous vehicles and women as users of bike sharing scheme. It then considers the quantitative evidence from D4.3 and any new qualitative evidence from interviews and focus groups with users for each Use Case I to III. The aim is to consider the following research questions:

- 1 What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
- 2 How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?

3.1 Use Case I Women as users of Public Transport

Themes identified in D3.1 related to the analysis of data collected have been identified as:

- **Accessibility** – service and availability; travel info; fares and ticket options; purpose of travel.
- **Infrastructure design** – universal design; clean and maintenance; facilities and furniture.
- **Safety and security** – harassment; overcrowding etc.
- **Disaggregation of groups** - childcare responsibilities, income etc

Figure 1 Use Case I Themes Identified in D3.1

The objective of the Use Case I 'Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)' is to investigate women's needs as users of metro and urban railway infrastructures. This is aimed at supporting the development of gender-equitable transport planning and design policies. The final goal of the Use Case I is to increase the percentage of women using metro and commuter railway public transports.

Scoping Review Findings

The scoping review conducted for Use Case I using the search terms outlined above in the methodology identified three main high-level fairness characteristics (FC's) or variables related to achieving fairness for women in their use of public transport, **Accessibility, Infrastructure and Safety & Security**. A second level of characteristic or variables were then identified as a cluster of fairness characteristics (FC's) which are low level variables which can be operationalised as a method of assessing fairness in access to public transport. This section will now provide a synopsis of the findings gathered from the scoping review.

Accessibility linked to transport includes (as discussed in WP2): the availability of and physical access to the transport system (e.g. stations and other facilities and vehicles etc); service levels of the system (e.g. cost of travel, comfort, travel time); the spatial distribution of activities, including the location of services and facilities people are seeking access to (e.g. availability of bike sharing

points in low income but low use areas); and cultural diversity (especially in a low income country context) (Geurs et al., 2009, pp.76-7).

Many researchers across the gender and transport fields have noted that men and women differ in their transport behaviour with regards to modes of transport chosen and the times available to travel (Hanson 2010; Levy 2013; Blair et al. 2013; Basaric et al. 2016; Louis & Hernandez 2016; Arabikhan et al. 2016), highlighting the need to explore women and transport using a gendered perspective to address the individual barriers faced by women.

The existing literature also shows us that in the main, the wider travel behaviour of men and women varies significantly with women, especially those with childcare responsibilities, tending to travel less for work than men do and make multiple shorter and more complex journeys opposed to men who take longer and single journeys at different times of the day (Hanson 2010; Martens 2012; Levy 2013; Arabikhan et al. 2016; Basaric et al. 2016). Louis and Hernandez (2016) claim, at an extremely aggregate level, that ordinarily "...men display standard and linear travel patterns [and] women frequently have shorter travel patterns and more complex travel chains" (p. 4326). Further differences in travel patterns are attributed between different groups of men and women, with women who have children and women who do not have children with McQuaid and Chen (2012), analysing UK household surveys, adding that there are also variations between mothers and fathers with data showing that "fathers travel furthest to work while mothers travel least" (p. 66).

Arabikhan et al. (2016) argue that providing access to a fair public transport system suited to the needs of women is of particular importance for women who they claim have "...less access to cars" (p. 80) and are therefore limited in their opportunities for travel. The concept of women owning less cars than men, appears to be replicated across many northern European countries (Blumenberg 2004; Martens 2012; Basaric et al. 2016; Chowdhury 2019) and suggests including a gendered perspective on future public transport infrastructure and planning is required to provide fair public transport for women. However, there may be great differences between different socio-economic groups with middle- or high-income people of both genders having more access to cars than those on lower incomes.

The literature on women and access to public transport provides important data which highlights the specific issues faced by women including accessing public transport whilst traveling with children or with childcare responsibilities which constrain their travel options. McQuaid and Chen (2012) discuss the complex travel patterns of women and mothers specifically, who tend to make more and shorter journeys. Lucas et al. (2019) argue that access to suitable mobility options should be accepted as part of all of our human rights, but claims that there are at times that these rights can be compromised particularly "for women who face physical, economic, cultural and psychological" (p. 41) inequalities in relation to their participation in social life and access to public transport and suggest that fair access for disabled and elderly (women) in public transport is impacted specifically by "infrequent and irregular services" (p. 14) which compounds their experiences of unequal access to social life and in particular health care.

The cost and affordability of public transport is a further theme which emerges from the literature in relation to fair access to public transport (McQuaid 2009; Blair et al. 2013; Arabikhan et al. 2016; Chowdhury 2019) with Blair et al. (2013) claiming that in particular "a significant proportion

of low-income households (71%) experienced disadvantage due to travel cost” (p. 198) linking with Martens (2012) discussion relating access to transport and social exclusion. For Martens (2012) the barriers faced by people from low-income households have larger repercussions on their ability to participate in wider social life including access to education and employment therefore creating a form of transport disadvantage. With Chowdhury (2019) adding that one of the main aims of all public transport systems is to provide equal access to transport for all in our communities, particularly those on low incomes and argues that a gendered analysis of costs when planning public transport would ensure that women and those with a lower income will have fair access to a transport system that is both reliable and affordable. With a worldwide acknowledgement that there is still an existing gender pay gap between of at least 20% between men and women (Chowdhury 2019) women, particularly mothers more likely to be working on a part-time basis, (McQuaid and Chen 2012) we can therefore hypothesise that women are in the main, more reliant on public transport as affordable transport.

Personal safety has been identified as one of the most importance factors in women’s travel decisions and one of the largest themes to emerge from the current literature review regarding women and their use of public transport. From this perspective safety is related to women’s perceptions of safety and security whilst accessing, waiting for and travelling using public transport (Blair 2013; Arabikhan et al. 2016; Louis et al. 2016; Chowdhury 2019). The safety and security of women as travellers of public transport was discussed relating to a variety of wider environmental, physical, and psychological concepts. For Louis et al. (2016), Chowdhury (2019) and Arabikhan et al. (2016) this relates to the quality of each station, including information provision and waiting times., with Arabikhan et al. 2016 adding that women, particularly young women feel less safe than men when waiting at train stations. In Chowdhury’s (2019) report she claims that “perceived safety at stations was the only significant variable for female riders” (p. 855). For Chowdhury, the findings highlighted that fear of crime was a prominent factor in women deciding whether to use public transport and at what times they used it by citing data which claimed that with the presence of security guards, “women were three times more likely to ride a route compared with male’s who were two times more likely” (p. 862). We can therefore state that fear in general and fear of crime specifically can lead to many women deciding not to use public transport at any time.

Arabikhan et al. (2016a) and Louis et al. (2016b), also discuss the importance of the quality of the service provided by transport organisations and its impact on safety and security for women who travel. Louis et.al (2016b) also suggest that their findings indicate there is a difference in the expectations of quality between men and women regarding the levels of service they expect with “...woman’s expectations and the minimum level of service they found acceptable higher than men’s” (p. 80a). The findings were collected by utilising the concepts of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, tangibles, comfort, convenience, connection, and intelligent transportation systems (ITS) in public transport service enhancement. For Chowdhury (2019), the focus on quality of service entailed a closer examination of waiting times, walking times, the availability of information on transfer, the visible presence of security guards, and the availability of covered walkways within each station.

3.1.1 Comparative Data analysis Findings Use Case I

Analysis of Structured open data for the selection of urban railway infrastructures

To examine the level of accessibility of urban railway infrastructures by women users, a data-driven approach was used. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were used for the analysis of several geolocated open datasets related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) See section 3, Deliverable 4.3 for full details.

User Satisfaction Analysis

Responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception by transport users for fairness characteristics of the service in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features (see Chapter 6 of D4.3 for full details).

In general, across all use cases from the Northern European case study (Ireland), the southern European case study (Spain) and the Eastern European case study (Poland) highlighted the following key findings key factors affecting women's travel choices:

- Safety and security practices
- The lack of facilities for parents for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of service,
- Cost of travel
- Travel information provided.
- Facilities and comfort
- Service provision
- Travelling with dependents
- Having a chronic illness/disability

Although the Irish partner does not appear in Section 3, 4 or 5, they helped to gather additional UESI data. In this way, this information was an opportunity to compare and validate the results coming from our Spanish and Polish collaborators.

- Service provision
- Capacity to travel to work.
- Service frequency, efficiency and accessibility
- Cost of travel
- Safety and security
- The lack of facilities for parents for infant feeding and changing.

Dynamic Argumentative Delphi Analysis

The DAD survey, already described in the D3.2, is a tool that collects qualitative data about users' and employees' perception to give priorities about different fairness and inclusiveness characteristics structured in a hierarchical model (García-Jiménez, E. et al. 2020) and associated with the service and or employment experience they may express (a full description is provided in D4.3, section 7 and in Poveda-Reyes, S. et al, 2021). Data was collected from Spain, Italy, Serbia, Poland, France and the UK (Scotland & England). The Use case I analysis was carried out with the

384 DAD surveys completed and highlighted the following key findings key factors affecting women's travel choices:

- Safety and security
- Overcrowding and emergency situations
- Accessibility of the service
- Overcrowding
- Air-conditioning and ventilation

Qualitative Data Analysis Findings

A thematic analysis was carried out to report findings of UC-I where questions include.

- What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
- How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?

The analysis considered the objective of increasing the percentage of women using public transport by addressing issues of gender equitable and inclusive planning policies with respect to their needs as users of the public transport service. Coding took into consideration DIAMOND's fairness characteristics (Level 1) i.e., Accessibility of the service, Infrastructure Design plus Safety and Security. Additionally, level 2 FCs were used as sub-themes of Level 1 FCs as assigned in DIAMOND's hierarchy of fairness characteristics for UC-I with room for emerging themes.

Interviews and focus group consisted of a total of 59 participants with 22 interviews from Ireland, 29 focus group from Poland and 8 focus group from Spain. The samples of all countries comprised of both male and females aged between 25 and above 75 years, but for Spanish sample which consists of only women. Male sample breakdown includes Ireland's with 32% aged between 25 to 44 years and Poland with 55% aged between 18 and 55 years. There are similarities of concerns and needs in relation to the use of public transport highlighted across data from Ireland, Spain and Poland.

Exploratory analysis highlighted the most recurred themes in the Northern sample for 'accessibility of the service' includes Travel & Wayfinding information provision, Service availability and efficiency, Travel Purpose, Level of service at the public transport access point, Ticketing options & fares. Highly emergent themes for this FC's included Operational hours & intervals and Convenience of travel system & process. Similar to the Northern sample, Eastern European data indicated travel purpose as a protruding prior theme, while having Convenience of travel system & process and Fares, affordability and exclusions as new findings. In comparison to the preceding location, Southern European data views overall rating of the service as positive with highly frequent, punctual, reliable and well-connected trains service but suggest improvement on sufficient direct lines for reduced journey times as well as improved frequency on weekend trains. Like the north and east, southern participants noted high cost of travel for family and particular zones.

Following the theme infrastructure design viewed universal design as prominent across Northern and Eastern region. Yet furniture and facility were the most referenced level 2 FCs in Northern Europe. Southern collection noted proximity of seats that deters spaces needed by those with

personal needs, children or caring responsibilities. In view of safety and security, the most recurred emergent theme common across Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe is Gardi, security or staff personnel noted mostly by women with views of respond time or visible staff in the case of an incident been a concern. Southern Europe holds views of general rating level of security as positive. Following Harassment and pickpocketing are viewed to reoccur in all locations and affecting experiences of women while using public transport with concerns of feeling less safe noted. Visibility of the surrounding area of the station is referenced mostly in Northern Europe, yet Southern Europe notes the need for light in remote areas/locations.

Analysis of Northern Europe further shows the most recurred themes highlighted by female and those travelling without dependants. Convenience of the travel of the travel system and process noted by demographics which include women and men, participants travelling with and without dependants, participants not living with a dependant and those living with dependant under 5 years of age. Operational hours are viewed referenced by those living with dependant's while Garda (police), security or staff personnel noted by participant travelling with dependants.

Social Media Data Analysis

With social media data analysis, the aim was to complement the analysis of survey data with larger samples of users, to provide a broader perspective of issues for transport users. Data was retrieved from Twitter API related to a relevant topic using Kalium. Data was collected from our Spanish and Poland case study areas only.

In Spain, the data highlighted

- Women were more concerned about the environment and the cost of fares.
- Women also referenced the travel schedule, lines, and journeys.
- Men were more likely to mention physical factors such as platforms.
- Both men and women showed concern regarding delays and changes to schedules.
- During COVID-19 men demonstrated more anger and suspicion while women were more thankful but also concerned by practical issues such as disinfection use.

In Poland the data highlighted Women were more likely to mention their work, and to make references to schedule issues. In both cases (bus and tramway), women speak more about people, express more frustration and use more swear words.

3.1.2 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices Public Transport.

The qualitative data analysis suggests that in relation to UCI, women as users of public transport, the most important factors affecting women highlighted across the analysis are as follows:

- Safety and Security
- Lack of facilities for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of service
- Cost of travel

Additional factors which impact on women as users of public transport highlighted, but NOT corroborated by further analysis were listed as

- Travel Information Provided
- Facilities and comfort
- Service Provision
- Travelling with dependents
- Having a chronic illness/disability
- Capacity to travel to work.
- Overcrowding
- Air conditioning and ventilation

3.2 Use Case II Women as Users of Autonomous vehicles

Themes identified in D3.1 related to the analysis of data collected have been identified as:

- **Safety and security** – accidents; human error, training. Traffic management;
- **Comfort** – trust in technology; simultaneity;
- **Mobility** – travel time; congestion; accessibility;
- **Economy** – vehicle economy; momentary and non-monetary costs;
- **Environment** – noise; emissions; public health;
- **Design** – infrastructure; vehicle shape; vehicle behaviour; HMI (human machine interface)

Figure 2 UC II Themes Identified in D3.1

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women's emotional needs as passengers of autonomous vehicles. The goal of the Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology and identify what the key factors are that affect women's travel choices.

Scoping Review Findings

The scoping review conducted for Use Case II using the search terms outlined above in the methodology section, identified three main high-level fairness characteristics (FC's) or variables related to women's acceptance of autonomous vehicles (AV's); **safety & security; comfort, mobility, economy, environment, and design**. A second level of characteristic or variables were then identified and defined as a cluster of fairness characteristics (FC's) which are low level variables which can be operationalised as a method of assessing women's acceptance of AV's (see figure 2).

Lucas et al. (2019) suggests that in the UK use of AVs for everyday use will remain relatively low until sometime after 2030. This section will set out some of the key variables which emerged from the scoping review which identified the barriers and needs of women in accepting the use of AV's.

AV manufacturers have claimed AV's have the potential to reduce road accidents and produce a safer and more efficient and effective transport system (Clark et al. 2016; Böhm, et al. 2017). However, Pflugfelder (2018) claims that a lack of confidence in the technology used in AV's means that currently "more than half of the US population would rather retain total control of their vehicles, even at the cost of increased safety" (p. 105). This lack of trust in the technology can also be seen to correlate with comfort levels of individuals using AV's (Clarke et al. 2016) and in general has been identified as a barrier to both men and women accepting AVs as vehicles with Bohm et al. (2017) claiming that their study showed that AVs were accepted more as everyday vehicles by men than women. One reason why women may feel less accepting of autonomous vehicles could be based on the way that vehicles have traditionally been designed for male bodies with Pflugfelder (2018) highlighting that it was not until 2011 that American car manufacturers realised that they were using a crash test dummy based on male biology to conduct safety tests. In contrast however, there are fears of potential hacking and others taking unauthorised control of the vehicle and this may be a greater worry for parts of the population, including some women.

There are also policy and transport management issues around the introduction of AVs into mainstream use that will require "enormous changes in the way infrastructure is designed, operated, regulated and used" (Clarke et al. 2016, p. 10). However, Lucas et al. (2019) claim that the current uncertainty around any potential impacts of AVs is preventing transport planners from acting proactively to integrate AV technology in future decisions too many gaps regarding policy, insurance and law which would provide for drivers who would be unable to take over their controls manually when needed.

Training will be required for drivers in full control mode need to be aware of how to take back control in situations when required. Transport policy will need to accommodate AV's and allow drivers to do other things whilst the car is driving.

Lucas et al. 2019 – One of the arguments for AV's is economic based with claims that fuel consumption will be increased due to more effective driving (Clark et al. 2016, Pflugfelder 2018), so there are environmental issues. However, that does not take account of the initial cost of the ownership and maintenance which it is argued, prevent those on lower incomes from ever achieving ownership. Policy also needs to consider potential negative effects on other transport modes if many people shift to AVs (e.g., low-income people may have to rely on a reduced public transport system if they cannot afford public use AVs).

3.2.1 Comparative Data analysis Findings Use Case II

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women's emotions as passengers of autonomous vehicles. This is aimed at supporting the development of fully automated cars, able to dynamically adapt driving performance to women's preferences. The goal of Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology. All User Satisfaction Surveys and experimental data were collected in Spain with the DAD survey data coming from the same member states than other use cases.

Experimental Analysis

Data was collected by conducting an experimental analysis with a simulator to assess the emotional reaction of different demographic groups of people to autonomous vehicles' driving experience followed up by a survey on user's preferences and characteristics related to their expectations regarding the usage of AV, and how they may influence their likelihood of acceptance and to identify the key factors affecting women's travel choices in relation to AV's.

The experimental design was divided equally in terms of these two main factors, defining four groups of participants: Women with children under 12 years, women without children under 12 years, men with children under 12 years, and men without children under 12 years old

- Comfort
- Vehicle behaviour
- Driving Mode
- Simultaneity
- Trust in the technology

Full details of the methodology for data collection and analysis for Use Case II can be found in chapter 4 of D4.3 Experimental tests analysis for Use Case II. The data collected for Use Case II was collected in Spain.

User Satisfaction Questionnaires

In UC II UESI questionnaires were collected by two different sources. In the experimental sessions in IBV, participant answered the UESI questionnaires after the experiments in the autonomous driving simulator to gather their opinion. The other source was through an online survey with a Spanish and English version. A total of 96 questionnaires were collected (40 in the experimental session, 47 in the Spanish version of the online survey and 9 in the English version).

The following key themes were identified a summation of the key findings (for more detailed results, please see Chapter 4 of D4.3):

- Safety and security
- Accessibility
- Energy efficiency
- Simultaneity

Dynamic Argumentative Delphi and Anova Analysis Findings

116 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. Fairness characteristics identified by the responders were, in order: trust in technology, public health, non-monetary costs, emissions and vehicle behaviour. Analysing the ranking of high-level fairness characteristics, indicated that the key factors affecting women's travel choices related to AVs were.

- Trust in the technology
- Safety and Security
- Mobility
- Vehicle behaviour
- Environment

- Cost
- Simultaneity
- Public health
- Emissions

Taken together, we can clearly see that the overall perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample is positive. Even though, no systematic qualitative data has been collected for Use Case II.

Social Media Data

From the social media analysis and the content base data collected, and the estimation of gender based on the user's name, short bio and picture, the tool returns the estimated probability of a user to be man or woman (assigned only when probability above a threshold of 0.9 for one of the two genders).

- Men tend to focus more on aspects related to technology and business, women are more concerned with social impact, social context and feelings.
- Women tend to have overall a more negative language when speaking about AVs.
- Women seem less interested than men in business and technological aspects, and more interested in the impact of AVs on the social context and on daily life.

Observational Data

Was collected during the experimental analysis which was a simulator to assess the emotional reaction of different demographic groups of people to autonomous vehicles' driving experience followed up by a survey on user's preferences and characteristics related to their expectations regarding the usage of AV, and how they may influence their likelihood of acceptance.

3.2.2 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices AV's

In relation to women's use of autonomous vehicles the qualitative and experimental data analysed suggests that the following factors are seen as important to potential women users.

- Safety and security
- Simultaneity

The experimental analysis also suggested that the following factors were important. Although this was not supported by the data collected via the DAD survey.

- Accessibility
- Energy Efficiency

Further findings from the DAD survey, not corroborated in the experiments included.

- Trust in technology
- Mobility
- Vehicle behaviour

- Environmental
- Cost
- Public health
- Emissions

3.3 Use Case III Women as users: Bike Sharing

Themes identified in D3.1 related to the analysis of data collected have been identified as:

- **Accessibility and Spontaneity** - Membership costs; spontaneity of access bikes; Proximity and convenience of docking stations; Inadequate infrastructure; Sign up and booking process; Accessibility, including locations of docking stations, to diverse groups.
- **Safety and Security** - Traffic safety; separate infrastructure; personal safety; safe environment; harassment and drivers' behaviour.
- **Socio cultural constraints;** Peer influence; Family responsibility
- **Weather and Topography**

Figure 3 UC III Themes Identified in D3.1

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate women's needs and barriers faced as users of bike sharing services. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services. The data mainly refer to France and the UK.

Scoping Review Findings

The scoping review conducted for Use Case III using the search terms outlined above in the methodology section, identified three main high-level fairness characteristics (FC's) or variables related to women's use of bike sharing schemes, **Capable of meeting required needs, Accessible, and Safe & Secure**. A second level of fairness characteristic or variables were then identified and defined as a cluster of fairness characteristics (FC's) which are low level variables which can be operationalised as a method of assessing women's acceptance of shared transport (see figure 3).

The first free bike sharing system was recorded in the Netherlands in 1965 with a second wave of coin operated sharing schemes established in the 1990's and the current third wave based on a docking station IT based system (Chen, von Lierop and Ettema 2020). By the beginning of 2012 it was claimed that there were over 400 bike sharing schemes globally (European Cyclists Federation 2012 <https://ecf.com/resources/cycling-facts-and-figures>). Bullock, Brereton and Bailey (2017) claim that this number has grown and there are now an estimated 1000 bike sharing schemes across globally.

Docking stations, which are the collection and drop off points for these bikes, have sprung up across a variety of locations throughout the urban landscape with the purpose of allowing flexible and fair access to a fleet of shared bikes. However, 'free-floating', smartphone-operated, non-dock/station-based bicycle hiring is becoming more popular and offer new opportunities for more flexible use, but also suffer from many of the problems of dock-based systems and are, so-far, mostly commercial, and so raise equity issues, such as the low usage by older people and lack of

parking facilities leading to nuisances for those in areas where bikes are parked (Chen et al., 2020; Hirsch et al., 2019). There are many reasons cited for the recent increase in cycling including a renewed focus on, and commitment to, more sustainable travel modes (Serna et al. 2019), a greater general awareness of the health benefits of cycling to people's health and the benefits for the environment (Ogilvie and Goodman 2012; Couch and Bullock et al. 2017; Couch and Smalley 2019) ; Wang and Akar 2019) and being seen as a method of bringing transport equality to disadvantaged communities (McNeil, Broach and Dill 2018). However, existing research also indicates that in the main, current users of bike share facilities tend to be disproportionately white, middle class and male (Fishman, Washington and Haworth 2013; Wang and Akar 2019; McNeil, Broach and Dill 2018; Serna et al. 2019). So, fairness issues related to the under-representation of different groups is important (Golub et al., 2016).

McNeil, Broach, and Dill (2018) related barriers to use based on sex, income status, ethnicity, and educational status mirroring the general findings of the bike share literature which claims many users are white, middle class, men. However, they also extended the basis of the cost barrier by highlighting that not everyone has access to a credit or debit card to pay electronically as currently required. Many of the existing bike share schemes across Europe are also membership based which means that full membership must be applied for and received before individuals can access local bikes. However, this membership process has itself been identified as a barrier for many potential users (Lee et al. 2017; McNeil et al. 2018; Hosford 2019) and is linked to a lack of knowledge regarding how to become a member, the processes involved i.e., providing identification and the monthly or even yearly subscription single payments which prevent people from low-income areas being able to access the schemes.

Serna et al. (2019) also highlight the importance of cost in relation to bike share schemes, before discussing how the individual locations of docking stations, the condition of bikes and the availability of safety equipment provided also have impact on the number of users of bike sharing schemes (see also: Bullock et al. 2017; Teschke et al. 2017; McNeil, Broach, and Dill 2018; Wang and Akar 2019). However, the findings of Serena et al. (2019) are not presented by gender, and it is difficult to separate which variable had impact on men or women. These findings around accessibility mirror those reported by Fishman, Washington and Haworth (2013) who also identified barriers to use based on the location of docking stations and the availability of safety equipment such as cycling helmets particularly around the notion that many bike sharing facilities do not provide helmets and therefore users must supply their own and then carry them around with them in between trips.

A further limitation of the majority of the research cited is that it is based on data collected by bike share organisations from their members, for example the Serena et al. (2019) paper data was originally collected six years before the start of the project. If we are to identify the barriers faced by women in accessing fair bike share facilities, we should look to involve women who do not currently use the service to examine their reasons why.

With claims of environmental and socio-economic benefits prevalent in the research findings (Ogilvie and Goodman 2012; Teschke et al. 2017; Serena et al. 2019) how then do we ensure that all members of the community have fair access to and use of these services? A first step would be to define what fair access looks like in relation to bike share facilities. Lee, Sener and Jones (2017) provided a synthesis of existing research to support transport planners in addressing **equity** in

transport outcomes. The paper argues that transport projects do not always include a consideration of equity in their design or outcomes and are in the main focused on the experience of “middle class suburban neighbourhoods” (p. 212). With regards to ongoing evaluations of fairness, the paper claims that current evaluations are in the main based on measuring the distribution of the actual geographical locations of transport facilities in terms of the distribution of docking station sites (**spatial equity**) but fail to include an examination of the financial costs to users (**social equity**). This process, they claim, “fails to capture equity effects” (p. 220) robustly in terms of whether or not the people who live locally to a transport station are financially able to use the facilities.

3.3.1 Comparative Data Analysis Findings

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate the needs and barriers women face as users of bike sharing services. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services. This analysis of the data collected via a variety of research methods will identify the key factors affecting women’s travel choices in relation to bike hire facilities.

User Satisfaction Questionnaires

The survey aimed to assess user perception about bicycle sharing services and the possible challenges and needs of users in terms of service accessibility, safety, impact. of social forces, and the effect of weather and local topography. Data for this Use Case were collected from France and the UK. The results indicate that the key factors affecting women’s travel choices with regards to using bike sharing facilities were.

- Age
- Level of income
- Safety and security
- Availability of child seats
- Proximity of docking stations
- Availability of bicycle network
- Presence of a cycle infrastructure
- Public awareness
- Weather

For more detailed results, and a full explanation of the methods please refer to D4.3 (Chapter 6).

Dynamic Argumentative Delphi Analysis Findings

Use Case 3 analysis regarding bicycle sharing services was carried out with the 97 DAD surveys completed up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 46 women, 33 men, 1 transsexual woman, 3 non-binary people and 14 who prefer not to answer (this number refers to French respondents. Under existing French legislation, we are not allowed to ask questions on sex, ethnicity etc.). For in depth detail on the methodology please see chapter 7 of D4.3.

The analysis of the DAD data highlighted the key factors affecting women’s travel choices in relation to women using bike sharing facilities highlighted were.

- Topography
- Weather and
- Family responsibilities
- Peer influence negative perceptions and insufficient infrastructures as top criteria.

Qualitative Data Analysis

A total of eleven participants took part in the interview aged between 25 and 64. Six participants were from France and the other five from the United Kingdom. 72.7% of participants had a master's degree and 18.2% had a doctorate degree. All participants reported using bike-sharing services, majority of the interviewees were female (72.7%), 72.7% of participants are aged between 18-34, and White (81.8%). 36.4% of the participants cycle between 30 and 35 minutes to work. 45.5% of them are in fulltime employment. Majority of the participants did not live with nor travel with dependents (See Annex 6 & 7 for full details and quotations extracted from interview/focus group data)

Summary of Findings

The interviewees expressed the feeling of freedom, convenience, and comfort as some of the benefits and opportunities offered by bike-sharing schemes. Bike-share was generally seen as giving users more freedom over their journeys, less restrictive, and a very convenient and quicker way to travel.

However, participants in the interview outlined several challenges of most of the schemes running currently, which limits its share of the urban modal split, and hindering growth, particularly for women users. They also proposed several measures to mitigate and address the outlined barriers to ensure growth and full participation from women and the general population. Figure 4 below presents the key barriers and participant's recommendations to address them.

3.3.2 Use Case III UK Interview Data

Sample characteristics

Five participants took part in the interview aged between 25 and 64. The majority of the interviewees were female (60.0%), 60.0% of participants were aged between 25 and 44. All participants reported using bike-sharing services, and white (60.0%). 20.0% of the participants cycle to work and cycle between 30 and 35 minutes to work. 57.1 % of them are in fulltime employment. None of the participants reported living with and travelling with dependents under five years.

Choice of Bike-share. In general, all the interviewees have either used bike-sharing services before or have had practical and management experience with bike-sharing services. The interview context meant that interviewees explained the reasons they cycle and how they benefit from cycling. The reason for the choice of shared bikes was found to centre on leisure, commuting, need to be active and environmental. Various aspects of bike-sharing such as cost of hiring, and freedom from the responsibility of storage and maintenance. Interviewees indicated that shared bikes are convenient and quicker. Bike-sharing is a perfect mobility option for completing the last leg of a mix-mode trip as well as for tourist and visitors.

Aside from the reported freedom and convenience of using bike-sharing services to meet their mobility need, Participants also identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services, which limits the use of the services, particularly among women. Barriers cited by participants include bikes unavailability or shortage at the stations, unsafe infrastructure, lack of appropriate bike accessories, and safety. A number of suggestions and recommendations address these barriers were similarly made to increase the ridership of bike-sharing services.

The section below presents the perceived barriers and mitigation measures.

Barriers

Accessibility & Spontaneity

The participants indicated their desire to cycle and use bike-sharing services, however, there was an indication that participants had concerns about some aspects of the bike-sharing services. There were doubts about the ability of the current bike-sharing services to replace the traditional mobility modes due to concerns about the level of reliability associated with some services. The unavailability of bikes at the stations when needed, the unavailability of vacant docking points at the stations to return bike, the distance to the nearest station, the location of the docking station and bicycle paths, and the level of safety and protection provided by the cycle infrastructure are some of the issue's users consider when planning a trip involving bike-sharing. There were concerns about the lack of real-time information on the availability or unavailability of bikes at the station on the operator's apps. In most cases participants will walk to an empty station after searching and walking to the station at the advice of the app. These and similar concerns limit the participation in bike-sharing services. For instance:

An operator of bike-sharing services in the UK indicated that complaints about the “lack of bikes” at the stations is the most received complaints they get from users of their services. In some instances, users reported walking for more than a mile to the nearest station to access a bike or having to cycle to another station far from their trip destination to return a bike after their trip because the station at their destination did not have a vacant docking point. Concerns raised about “Accessibility and Spontaneity” sustains the perception of ‘unreliability’ of bike-sharing services and have significant impact of user and potential user participation.

Safety & Security

The Safety and security of the user became up strongly as one of the major barriers and setbacks in the adoption and continual usage of the bike-sharing services. Participants had concerns with the safety level on a significant proportion of the bike infrastructure (stations and paths). Participants expressed worries about the aggressive driving behaviour of some drivers. Cycling on busy roads with heavy vehicular traffic, and paths and stations with inadequate lighting raises safety concerns for most users and a major cycling deterrent. There are also concerns about the safety of the infrastructure and whether they provide adequate level of protection for cyclist. This concern reinforces the assertion that women are more likely than men to experience and report a frightening situation.

Social Constraints

Women responsibility and travel patterns defined by the constructed societal norms and cultural constraints have created agenda difference in terms of how and where people actually travel to and purposes. This plays a significant role in the choice of transport by women. Most participants raised concerns about the absence carry baskets or racks on their services providers' bike fleet. Moreover, the lack of child seats and accessories for users with children and the inadequacy or discontinuity of the cycle infrastructure possess a major barrier to most users. Thus, some categories of people or potential users such as people travelling with children, shoppers and travellers with luggage who wishes to use bike-share services are excluded from the using this mobility option.

Weather & Topography

Weather and the topography of the terrain has been indicated as a major barrier to cycling and bike-share for users. While the issue of topography could be over with E-bikes, windy, rainy, and snowy weather tend to hinder the use of bike-share significantly.

Design & Functionality

The size, aesthetics and accessories of a bike are suggested to affect user perception and satisfaction of the services and have impact on the acceptance and adoption of bike sharing services. Some participants have concerns about the size and comfortability of the seats on most of the bikes as well. For instance, women prefer low frame or bikes with step through frames. Presented below are the concerns expressed by some participants.

Suggested Solutions

Participants raised several concerns and barriers to full participation in the use of bike-sharing services. These identified and perceived barriers particularly, among women have been discussed in the preceding sections of this report. This section presents and discusses participants' suggested solutions and requirements to address the barriers discussed above.

Accessibility & Spontaneity

Participant's needs and expectation to address the barriers to accessibility of bike-sharing services centres on the following critical issues include the siting station near users, increasing the number of docking points and bikes at each station, reducing the distance between stations, increase the quality and safety of the infrastructure such as paths stations etc. One participant suggested the possibility of reserving a bike on the apps for about 15 minutes before getting to the station to avoid the situation where the app indicates the availability of a bike, but one walks to an empty station.

Safety & Security

Participants were of the opinion that the designs of the bikes and most importantly the safe and protected infrastructure could eliminate most of the safety and security concerns of users and increase the use of the services more in future. If we can get the right infrastructure (safe, segregated and protected) then perhaps women can cycle without helmets as seen in the Netherlands. Some participant's views are presented below.

Social Constraint

Participants believe that the provision of child seat and accessories to support trips involving children and carrying goods is essential in ensuring the inclusivity of the bike-sharing services. Interviewees also underscores the importance of safe infrastructure and continuity in the cycle paths in promoting cycling among women. One participant was of the view that enabling cycling with children has the added advantage of introducing the children to cycling at younger age. Another participant suggested the provision of broader bicycle seats (plus size bike seat) to cater for plus-sized users.

Weather & Topography

The provision of electric bikes was generally suggested as a necessity in addressing the issue of terrain. Participants' opinions are presented below.

Design & Functionality

The design of bikes in terms of size, height, aesthetics and functionality is suggested to have influence on the decision to cycle. Interviewees suggested the design of lightweight and universal bikes (unisex design: low frame bikes) will ensure bikes are convenient for all sexes, particularly women users. A number of improvements were suggested to improve the design and functionality of the bikes.

- Design of bikes (size, height, baskets, aesthetics etc.)
- Larger and comfortable seats for women
- Low frame bikes for women especially women in skirt
- Bikes with covered chain
- Locks on bikes for multi-stop trips for shopping etc.
- Install alarm and GPS on bikes.

3.3.2.1 Key Findings Use Case III UK

- The key barriers to the use of bike-sharing services include.
 - o Unavailability of bikes at the stations
 - o Unavailability of docking point to return a bike after a trip.
 - o Distant docking station from users
 - o Busy roads and vehicular traffic
 - o Traffic safety and aggressive driving
 - o Inadequate and unsafe infrastructure
 - o Lack of accessories for transporting goods and travelling with children.
 - o Weather
 - o Unsuitable bikes (size, structure and seat size).
- The key suggestions improve bike-sharing services include.
 - o Implement dockless bike-sharing schemes.
 - o Safe and protected infrastructure (off-road infrastructure)
 - o Install alarm and GPS on bikes for bikes security and safety of users.
 - o Accessories for transporting goods and travelling with Children (carry basket, cargo and child seat)

- o Increase percentage of E-bikes in the fleet.
- o Improve the design of bikes (height, aesthetics, low frame, covered chains, large and comfortable seats).

3.3.3 Use Case III French Interview Data

Sample characteristics

Six participants took part in the interview aged between 25 and 54. The majority of the interviewees were female (83.3%), 50.0% of participants were aged between 25-34 and White (71.4%). 66.7% of the participants cycle to work and cycle between 30 and 35 minutes to work. 83.3 % of them are in fulltime employment. 33.3% of the participants reported living with and travelling with dependents under five years.

Choice of Bike-share.

In general, all the interviewees have used bike-sharing services before. The interview context meant that interviewees explained the reasons they cycle and how they benefit from cycling. The reason for the choice of shared bikes is demonstrated to be centered on the perception of “freedom”, “comfort” and satisfaction. Various aspects of bike-sharing such as cost of hiring, travel time and freedom from the responsibility of storage, maintenance and possible bike theft. Interviewees indicated that shared bikes are convenient because they are less restrictive, quicker and could be safer than walking and using the metro.

Aside from the reported freedom and convenience of using bike-sharing services to meet their mobility need, Participants also identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services and to increasing the use of the services, particularly among women. While some of the barriers cited centred on bikes availability, infrastructural limitations, lack of appropriate equipment and safety, several suggestions and recommendations were also made to address the barriers. The section below presents the perceived barriers and mitigation measures.

Barriers to Bike-sharing

Accessibility

The availability of bikes at the stations when needed, the location of the stations, the distance to the nearest station, and the type and quality of the cycle paths available are some of the issue's users must take into consideration when planning a trip involving bike-sharing. All interviewees had concerns about the availability of bikes at the stations and the condition of the available bikes if any. Interviewees enjoyed cycling and feel liberated using bike-sharing services. However, there was an indication that participants viewed some services as unreliable and not dependable for meeting mobility needs in an urgent and emergency situation; in terms of securing a bike and getting an empty dock when returning a bike at the end of the trip. For instance:

In some instances, users had concerns about the lack of stations in their neighbourhood, others reported travelling further from their trip destination to return a bike after their trip because the station at their destination did not have an empty dock to return the bike. The language used by interviewees to describe their experience and perception of bike-sharing services shows some

level of frustration and dissatisfaction with bike-sharing services, basing their views on knowledge and understanding of specific services.

Some participants said they were unwilling to use bike-sharing services to meet their mobility needs, especially for attending important appointment, because they could not guarantee to get to work or arrive for an appointment on time due the uncertainty of getting a bike for a trip. The perceived 'unreliability' of bike shares led one participant deciding not to use the services for important trips.

Safety and security

Some participants expressed several safety concerns, particularly traffic safety, harassment, inadequate lighting at the stations and the perception of safety at quieter stations and stations with insufficient lighting. Users expressed concerns about the behaviour of drivers and aggressive behaviour of other road users. Women were more likely to feel harassed or experience a frightening situation when cycling.

Social Constraint

Societal and cultural constraints as well as women responsibility and travel patterns and purposes play a significant role in the choice of transport. Some participants argued that the absence and/or size of the carry baskets are of particular importance for shopping trips and for travellers with luggage who wishes to use bike-share services.

Additionally, users with children and who wish to cycle with them considers the absence of child seat and the inadequacy or discontinuity of the cycle infrastructure. These raise safety concern for users with dependants who sees the infrastructure unsafe for cycling with kids.

Women fashion and concerns about appearance. For instance, wearing of skirts, high heeled shoes and carrying handbags limits their ability to cycle as women cannot cycle in high heels.

Weather and Topography

Weather and the topography of the terrain has been indicated as a major barrier to cycling and bike-share for users. Barring bad weather, some participants will always cycle or use bike-sharing services to meet their mobility needs.

The local topography of the terrain also poses a challenge to the use of bike-sharing services and to cycling in general. Some participants indicated they use electric bikes to overcome this discussed barrier, however, the scarcity of electric bikes limit the users in such instances. It was also noted that available electric bikes at the stations in most instances are either not charged or partially charged and do not have enough battery power to complete a trip.

Design & Functionality

The design of the bikes, equipment and facilities are argued to pose some level of challenge to users, particularly women. The size and design of the bike could be a significant barrier to women wishing to cycle. One participant suggested that the size and structure of the bikes are important indicators for inclusivity. The width of the bikes lanes similarly cited as barriers by some interviewees.

Suggested Solutions

This report has identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services and to increasing the use of the services, particularly among women. This section of findings discusses participants' suggested solutions to the barriers discussed above.

Accessibility

Participants suggested solution to addressing their concerns and challenges, mainly focusing on the accessibility of bike-sharing services centred on the following critical issues, including the number of bikes at each station, the distance between stations, increase of cycle infrastructure such as paths etc. One interviewee sees the challenges as having substantial inequalities implication. Another participant suggested the possibility of a user renting and unlocking more than one bike at the station for trips involving family and friends if he/she is the only account holder.

Safety & Security

Participants who are interested in using the services are of the opinion that the implementation of the following measures could mitigate the safety and security concerns of users and increase the use of the services more in future.

- Installation of side mirrors on bikes
- Provision of a helmet with bikes
- Improve the visibility at stations (improve lighting)
- The installation of emergency help button at stations
- The development of road user code of conduct to deter aggressive road user behaviour.
- Visibility of bikes (High visibility bikes)
- Building safe infrastructure and bike lanes

Social Constraint

Participants believed that the provision of good-sized carry baskets will help users wishing to use the services to meet their mobility needs for shopping trips and users with luggage. Interviewees also suggest the development of the cycle infrastructure to ensure the continuity of the cycle paths.

Again, several participants called for the supply of child seat at the stations for users with children who may wish to use the services with their children. One participant suggested the provision of a locker with a self-service detachable child seat at the stations for interested users to access when required. Another participant suggested the provision of broader bicycle seats (plus size bike seat) to cater for plus-sized users.

Weather & Topography

The provision of electric bikes was generally perceived as a necessity in addressing the issue of terrain and encouraging more women and older people to cycle. However, it is noted from the interviewees' submissions that the charging of the bikes is as important as the supply of the e-bikes.

Design of bikes

The interviewee, therefore, suggested lightweight and universal bike designs (unisex design: low frame bikes) to ensure bikes are convenient for all sexes, particularly women users. Wider bicycle lanes and paths are also recommended to allow for overtaking and prevent congestion on the cycle lanes. In support of inexperienced riders, participants suggested a number of improvements to the design and functionality of the bikes which, focused on improvements to weight, design, safety and comfort:

- Installation of side mirrors and indicators on the bikes to increase the confidence and comfort of riders.
- The provision of a detachable helmet for users: instead of users having to carry their helmet around.
- The installation of a self-service locker at the stations with a detachable child seat for interested users.

3.3.3.1 Key Findings Use Case III France

- The key barriers to the use of bike-sharing services include.
 - Unavailability of bikes at the stations
 - Unavailability of docking point to return a bike after a trip.
 - Distance of docking station from users
 - Distance between stations
 - Traffic safety and aggressive driver behaviour
 - Insufficient and unsafe infrastructure
 - Lack of accessories for transporting goods and travelling with children.
 - Hilly terrain
 - Unsuitable bikes (size, structure and seat size)
 - Heavy bikes
- The key suggestions improve bike-sharing services include.
 - Increase the number of stations, bikes and docking points.
 - The provision of safe and protected infrastructure (off-road infrastructure, increase width of lanes)
 - The provision of accessories for transporting goods and travelling with Children (carry basket, cargo and child seat)
 - Increase percentage of E-bikes in the fleet.
 - Improve the design of bikes (unisex design, low frame, lighter and smaller bikes, install side mirrors, detachable helmets and child seat)
 - Public sensitisation campaigns on cycling
 - Develop user code on conduct to address harassment and aggressive road user behaviour.

Social Media Data –

The Social media analysis on users of the Bike sharing service shows how that the debate on Twitter is quite politicized, both among men and women. Not much about the value of the service unfortunately, however in terms of gender difference it is worth noting that in tweets involving

the major's name, men speak of “fiasco”, displaying a more aggressive tone, while women's top co-occurring word is merci (“thanks”), displaying a kinder type of attitude.

Observational Data Findings

Observations were conducted based on ad hoc developed checklists were used for the evaluation of infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs as users of bike-sharing services around the following areas: (i) accessibility and spontaneity; (ii) safety and security; (iii) social constraints; (iv) weather and topography; (v) other. Observations allowed for the comparison of observation results between the bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III – France, UK), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility France.

Analysis of the observations indicated that the key factors affecting women's travel choices in relations to bike sharing facilities were.

- Other public modes of transport near the docking station.
- Public awareness
- Spontaneity
- Presence of a cycle infrastructure
- Personal safety
- Availability of safety equipment
- Availability of child seats

3.3.4 Comparison of results on the key factors affecting women's travel choices bike hire facilities.

Analysis of the quantitative data from the User satisfaction surveys the DAD and observations corroborated the following factors that are important for women using bike hire facilities.

- Safety and security – including the provision of safety equipment and personal safety.
- Availability of child seats
- The presence of cycle infrastructure
- Public awareness of the facilities

When examined together the interview and focus group data collected from both the UK and France corroborate the following key themes as barriers to women's use of bike sharing facilities.

- Unavailability of bikes at the station
- Unavailability of docking points to return bike after trip.
- Distant docking stations from user
- Traffic safety and aggressive driving
- Inadequate and unsafe infrastructure

When the recommendations made by participants were analysed together, they corroborated the following suggestions as methods which could increase women's use of bike sharing facilities in France and the UK.

- The availability of accessories for transporting goods and travelling with children.
- Increase the percentage of E-bikes in the fleet.
- Improve the design of bikes (height, low frame etc.).

3.4 Conclusions

The data analysis discussed above provides us with the following findings in relation to each of them. The key factors include those FC's that have been corroborated via other research methods have been listed below.

RQ1. What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?

The analysis of data from across the methodologies suggests that following key factors affect women's choices in relation to them as users of transport.

- Safety and security
- Costs
- Facilities for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of public service
- For AV's specifically simultaneity, trust in technology

RQ2. How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?

When we examine the key factors identified and corroborated by the DIAMOND projects multiple research method approach, it suggests that in the main the high-level factors are similar across all transport modes, and that women are in the main interested and focused on safety and security, costs, frequency, accessibility, availability, which should be understood in the context of the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines.

4. Summary of findings: Key Factors Influencing the Career Choices of Women in Relation to Working in Transport Sector

Themes identified in D3.1 related to the analysis of data collected have been identified as:

Socio Economic Conditions - Job segregation; Demand factors; policy and legal; Female facilities (toilets etc.);

Job Characteristics - HR policies recruitment, retention, promotion etc; training provision; terms and conditions, flexible working, safety, and security

Personal Circumstances – caring responsibilities; economic deprivation; location; access to transport

Individual Characteristics - Skills; Adaptability; Educational level/attainment; health status; Demographic (age, ethnicity etc.)

Figure 4 Use Case IV Themes Identified in D3.1

4.1 Use Case I Women employed across the transport sector

The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate women's needs as employees in the transport sector, and specifically to consider the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in the railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors.

- How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

Scoping Review Findings

The scoping review conducted for Use Case IV using the search terms outlined above in the methodology section, identified three main high-level fairness characteristics (FC's) or variables related to women's employment in the transport sector, **Capable of meeting required needs, Accessible, and Safe & Secure**. A second level of characteristic or variables were then identified and defined as a cluster of fairness characteristics (FC's) which are low level variables which can be operationalised as a method of assessing fairness for women employees in the transport sector. This section will now provide a synopsis of the findings gathered from the scoping review.

Employment within the worldwide transport sector, inclusive of all its complex dimensions; air, sea, road, rail, inland navigation, space and logistics – have traditionally been viewed as male dominated and as a result, transport policy has been male-oriented, devised by men and centred around male lifestyles (Buchmann 2013; Wright 2014).

The concept of job segregation by gender was supported by a pilot study conducted by the European Commission in 2017 which claimed that overall “...many transport firms and agencies need to up their game” (p. 10) in relation to the development of HR policies that support fair and equal employment for women. They discuss the requirement that in terms of positive actions to make jobs more attractive to women transport organisations should set up specific promotional schemes for women, present successful examples of women taking up previously male-dominated positions, improve the working environment and make any necessary changes in education and training to encourage more girls to follow STEM and engineering routes into employment (French and Strachan 2008; Astor et al. 2017; Giannelos et al. 2018).

One of the main themes emerging from the literature on women’s employment in the transport sector is based on the historical concept of occupational and job segregation (Corral and Isusi 2007; French and Strachan 2008; Wright 2014; Yerkes et al. 2017; Giannelos et al. 2018) based on a gendered notion of employment which dictates which jobs are acceptable and suitable for men or women and Corral and Isusi (2007) adding that the transport sector is one of the most “gender segregated sectors of the economy” (p. 4). French and Strachan (2008) report that very few transport organisations use “proactive strategies” (p. 86) to recruit, promote and retain women employees, particularly amongst the management roles. The idea that many transport organisations still have this view of outdated gender stereotypes becomes visible in the ways that certain vacant roles are advertised all have an impact on the likelihood of women applying for roles, particularly at a management level.

There are still many (men and women) who believe that there are certain roles and careers that are more suited to men than women. This gendered view of roles has a direct daily impact on women in the workplace in relation to their working conditions which can also result in a lack of specific policies to support women in the workplace (Astor et al. 2017, Giannelos et al. 2018). Yerkes et al. (2017) highlight this by discussing the impact on women returning to work from maternity leave and the ways in which career breaks disadvantage women in their long terms career goals. The study reports that in some cases within the transport sector women are returning to work on a part time “lower occupational status” (p. 477) which they claim is unfair and creates issues around both procedural and interactional justice for working mothers. Similar impacts are observed in other sectors, including female dominated professions such as nursing (e.g., McIntosh et al. 2012). French and Strachan (2008) report that their research shows a positive correlation with providing robust maternity, pregnancy and breastfeeding policies with the retention of female employees. Adams et al. (2000) also claim that many organisations were still unsure of employing married women as they are generally regarded as having less commitment to their careers, although such attitudes are likely to have change since then.

Job segregation is also highlighted by the current link between the male domination of the transport sector and the working practices operationalised in organisations, for example long working hours that are not always family friendly, particularly in the case of certain mobile professions that may require prolonged absences from home and an inflexible approach to work routines which does not provide opportunities to work from home or remotely for example (Wright 2014; Giannelos et al. 2018). Taking measures to create flexibility for all employees, providing the opportunity to reduce working hours when required and permanent contracts to improve job satisfaction, will not only attract more women to the sector, but it will also improve their ability to attract and

retain talent overall (French and Strachan 2008; Wright 2014; Astor et al. 2017; Giannelos et al. 2018).

In relation to employment in the transport industry, all people should have fair and equal opportunities to access all types (levels, occupations etc.) of employment and the relevant training and educational opportunities which would support their role and promotion in the industry (Corral and Isusi 2007; Giannelos et al. 2018). However, we can see from the actual employment patterns (outcomes) that this is usually not the case for many groups of women (e.g., those with dependent children etc.). There are barriers, lack of support etc. which mean women tend to be under-represented in many types and levels of jobs in the transport sector. French and Strachan (2008) state that providing equal opportunity training within transport organisations “was positively associated with the increased numbers of women across the various job areas” (p 87)

One factor which emerged from the literature as a barrier to women working in the transport sector was to a large extent based on a lack of family friendly working practices, such as providing flexible working, shift patterns and opportunities for home, remote or part time working (Wright 2014; Giannelos et al. 2018; Astor et al. 2017). Although this could be said to be a barrier for men as well as women, working women are still in the main, responsible for all family caring responsibilities (Wright 2014).

Women in the workplace in general face more discrimination than men, particularly in male dominated cultures such as the transport sector (Corral and Isusi 2007; Ancaes 2014; Giannelos et al. 2018). Sex discrimination and sexualised harassment in the workplace is also an additional challenge faced by women in the workplace and is based on a specific gendered culture existing in male dominated workplaces (Ancaes 2014; Wright 2014; Astor et al. 2017; Giannelos et al. 2018). A lack of policy to combat abuse and a perceived absence of support from employers to women experiencing such discrimination appears to be the cause of many women leaving their jobs in the industry (Astor et al. 2017).

A further theme to emerge from the literature was related to a lack of separate facilities for women in the workplace. The working environment in transport organisations tends to reflect the dominant male work force and as a result, women often have to adjust to a male-centred organisation of work, workplace culture and working conditions (Corral and Isusi 2007; Sicard 2012; Giannelos et al. 2018) A similar situation exists in relation to health and safety issues in the workplace, which are usually male centred and is reflected in a lack of female toilets and showers, provision of suitable female PPE and segregated changing rooms (Corral and Isusi 2007).

4.2.1 Comparative Data analysis Use Case IV

The interviews conducted were transcribed, coded and analysed (see Annex 5 for a list of the nodes already developed for coding which is being conducted using the NVivo software).

User Satisfaction Analysis

The User Satisfaction survey results obtained from employees across 3 data sets of Northern European, Southern European and Eastern European rail providers (Ireland, Spain and Poland). The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs

and perception by transport employees for fairness characteristics of the service in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features. The questionnaires tried to cover a number of areas including job segregation/gender balance in their country/community and recruitment and promotion that promotes equality and fairness for women in transport as well as rating overall satisfaction. The following is a summation of the main key findings (for more detailed findings, please refer to Chapter 6 of D4.3):

- Job segregation
- Income
- Rural or urban environment
- Affordable childcare services
- Cost of travel to work.
- Acceptance by male colleagues

Although Irish participants do not appear in Section 3, 4 nor 5, this company allowed us to gather additional UESI data to collaborate with DIAMOND broadening the data. In this way, this information was an opportunity to compare and validate the results coming from Spain and Poland.

Most people are reasonably satisfied with their work environment and their conditions of employment.

Analysis showed that the variables found to be relevant predictors were:

- The level of job segregation found in the context also in terms of access to different education (i.e., such education for technical qualifications and STEM careers),
- The protection offered by HR policies in their own organization, and the protection they offer against unfair dismissal.
- The ergonomics conditions of different workstations and positions, the facilities for both male and females and the capacity to meet specific personal needs of different employees such as the one determined by chronic illness and support for carer.
- Gender and Sector are significant variables in respect to organization inclusive satisfaction.
- The variables were very correlated to each other compared to Irish and Spanish sample.
- Among the socio-demographic variables: 'income', gender and environment were useful to explain the organization inclusive satisfaction.
- Different Individual characteristics were relevant to explain 'org. inclusive satisfaction' compared to Irish and FGC sample, such as 'Individual Illness affect', 'individual flexibilities for change', 'Ethnic affect' and 'individual experience in role'.
- Different Individual characteristics were relevant to explain 'org. inclusive satisfaction' compared to Irish and FGC sample, such as 'Individual Illness affect', 'individual flexibilities for change', 'Ethnic affect' and 'individual experience in role'.

Dynamic Argumentative Delphi Analysis

The Use case 4 analysis regarding employment was carried out with the 100 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020 (For full methodological and analytical information, see section 7 of D4.3).

For the aggregated analysis performed for this UC, the number of consistent respondents were 53 from a total of 100.

The results indicated that:

- Caring and parenting responsibilities
- Flexibility
- Job segregation
- Job recruitment
- Access to resources
- Rural or urban environment
- Terms and conditions
- Cost of childcare

Qualitative Data Analysis Findings

The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate women's needs as employees in the transport sector, and specifically to consider the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in the railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors (see **Annex 5 for a list of NVivo nodes created for Use Case IV**).

The research questions relating to Use Case IV are as follows.

- How different job characteristic, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

The following section will therefore set out a summary of the data analysis employed on the interview and focus group data collected from Spain, Ireland, Poland, Scotland and the UK for Use Case IV based on the two research questions above.

In total there were 46 participants who took part in the interview/focus group data collection.

- 4 participants were HR personnel.
- 15 participants from Poland
- 5 participants from Spain
- 22 participants from UK/Ireland/Scotland

The analysis is presented in relation to the Fairness Characteristics (FC's) for Use Case IV as set out in Work Package 3, Deliverable 3.1 and are divided under the individual FC headings.

An additional heading of 'Themes Emerging from the Data' has been added below which provides an overview of the reoccurring themes that were relevant to the participants, but which were not identified in the literature review. Fairness Characteristics identified in Work Package 3 but NOT found in the interview data have been highlighted.

To protect the anonymity of the participants who took part in the project, when direct quotations are used participants have been identified by their allocated pseudonym, their sex (F for female M for male), their job title and their country of origin to provide an intersectional focus, e.g., Fiona F Bus Driver Poland.

4.2.2 Factors affecting gender balance/female employability (Research Question 3)

The following section summarises the analysis in response to Research Question 3 (How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?). **(See Annex 8 for full details and quotations extracted from interview/focus group data).**

Socio Economic Conditions - Job segregation

Analysis of the research data suggests that job segregation has an impact on gender balance and female employability in the transport industry. According to some interviewees this job segregation is based upon traditional or historical ideas of 'men's jobs' and 'women's jobs'. The dominance of male employees was apparent across sectors and locations. Respondents noted majority female employment in HR, finance, marketing and clerical work, but indicated that women were less likely than men to be employed in front line jobs, such as driving, and engineering or IT jobs.

Despite gender imbalance in the industry and male dominance in certain roles several respondents did point out that gender should not be a requirement for jobs in the industry. Moreover, although there was almost majority agreement that job segregation was apparent in their organisation some respondents did point to evidence of progress with regard gender balance and female employability. However, they point out, this change is slow and has not resulted in gender balance in the industry yet. F

Furthermore, while there was evidence of the lack of women in 'traditionally male roles' in the industry respondents drew attention to the concentration of women in other occupations, such as in clerical jobs, in booking offices, commercial and marketing roles and HR roles.

Additionally, respondents provided evidence of not only role segregation according to gender but also hierarchical segregation, with the presence of 'a glass ceiling' and a lack of women in senior roles within their organisations. They suggested barriers exist which means that the further up the management chain you look the fewer women there are with examples of no women on management boards or in senior positions given. This lack of women in senior roles is problematic as respondents noted that women in senior roles, and more diverse roles, need to be more visible to make these positions seem more accessible to women, highlighting that they can progress and develop in their careers in the organisation and have a sense of 'belonging'.

However, a few respondents pointed out that there are females in senior positions in their organisation and welcomed the fact that they are supportive and encouraging. There was also evidence of male managers who were equally supportive and encouraging. Interviewees also pointed to the value of mentoring and suggested this was commonly used in many organisations to support women. Although the majority of these mentors are women there were reports of

male mentors, in part, however, due to there not being women in more senior roles. In addition, practices such as 'women in transport days', specific women in transport groups and educational events were cited as examples of support received that positively impact upon women employees and a more equal gender balance in the industry.

A few respondents discussed the efforts in place to address the lack of gender balance in the sector with regard job segregation, such as member organisations and advertising externally for promoted posts rather than only internally and highlighting women role models. Respondents did note however, that although there are attempts to change to a more inclusive and more gender balanced workforce, with diversity and inclusion given attention and comments such as the organisation being 'more open to change' or adopting 'present day thinking', job segregation in the transport sector persists and impacts upon gender balance in roles, across hierarchies, sectors and locations.

Socio-Economic Factors - Demand Factors

With regard demand factors that feature in the FC and their impact upon gender balance and employability in the industry vacancy characteristics and recruitment factors emerged as important. With regard vacancy characteristics, respondents suggested working hours, shift work and opportunities for progression were obstacles to gender balance and female employability. These issues are discussed in detail in other FC subsections. Furthermore, with regard recruitment factors, respondents noted that recruitment and selection procedures, selection preferences, method of recruitment and discrimination all impact upon gender balance and employability. Once again, these issues are discussed in detail in other FC subsections.

Socio- Economic Factors - Policy /legal

With regard policy/legal factors that impact on gender balance and female employability the research data underlined that there are policies in place that should in theory promote fairness in the workplace but that in reality they are often viewed as a 'tick box' exercise, with the work culture not reflecting the fair recruitment policy

Socio-Economic Factors - Female facilities

Another FC important in ensuring gender balance is work conditions and the data highlighted that the presence of appropriate female facilities was often lacking, making work conditions problematic and discriminatory for women. The lack of facilities was deemed to be a result of, and linked to, job segregation in the industry. Not only were toilet facilities inadequate, data revealed that showering facilities, sanitation provision and breast feeding/expressing milk were also problematic for women in certain roles in the industry.

Job Characteristics – Human Relations (HR) Policies – Recruitment, Retention, and Promotion

Recruitment

The research data highlighted that some recruitment practices employed by organisations may not be fair for women, with one interviewee even suggesting some men in her organisation are reluctant to employ women of childbearing age in case they become pregnant and take maternity

leave. Overall respondents suggested that the following are common in recruitment methods and practices and that they disadvantage women:

- unconscious bias
- conscious bias
- discrimination
- sexism
- a lack of fairness

The issues, with regard male colleagues in work, are discussed in detail below under FC Negative Attitudes of Male Colleagues.

Some interviewees expressed that ‘gender balanced panels’ and ‘unbiased questions’ would increase fairness at the point of recruitment and selection overcoming the above and expressed the desire for current practices to change. Moreover, there were calls for management and directors to understand that women can do jobs traditionally perceived as male.

Furthermore, one interviewee pointed out that she is exploring whether there is unintended bias against women inherent in the psychometric testing that train drivers undergo as part of the application process.

Despite this evidence the data also suggests that some steps are being taken to address current inequality at the point to recruitment and selection, with some organisations featuring female employees in their advertising recruitment campaigns and attempting to make their recruitment strategy gender neutral and unbiased to aid inclusion. Examples were noted of advertisements featuring female train drivers and tram drivers and one advert featuring two women job sharing a director level job in a company, to promote awareness of these opportunities for women. Interviewees highlighted the use of inclusive recruitment practices in their organisations. Moreover, in some cases, gender neutral adverts were created by removing ‘masculine’ language or by placing these adverts on platforms considered by the organisation to be more accessible to women, for example women’s magazines and an online forum for mothers. There was also evidence of unconscious bias training being delivered to managers and those involved in the recruitment and interviewing process.

Another strategy used by many of the organisations to promote gender balance and increase female employability involved attending schools, colleges, universities, and job fayres. This tactic is based around education and awareness, with many respondents suggesting that more education and communication regarding roles within the transport sector and their suitability for women is important to increase the numbers of women in the industry. It was noted by a few respondents that this education is essential because many women may not understand the nature of or requirements of work in the sector and believe they are not capable of the physical demands of certain roles.

However, this strategy is not seen as a quick fix, with several interviewees noting that the impact of such initiatives will take time, and that access to schools can be problematic. It is important to note that most organisations, across sectors and location, suggested they do not specifically target women for employment opportunities, suggesting this could be considered discriminatory and

stating they want the best person for the job, regardless of gender, and that competition for jobs should be fair. Organisations had strategies such as targets for diversity, rather than quotas, and equality plans to increase numbers of women employees.

Respondents pointed to the need to encourage more inclusive behaviours across the transport sector generally. Although, as stated, there were no calls for positive discrimination, they suggested that positive steps towards fairness in the sector can be achieved by:

- Providing 'an even playing field'
- managers 'not being part of the old boy's network'.
- attending 'the latest recruitment training'
- recruiting the 'right person for the job'
- specifically utilising recruitment campaigns featuring women in traditionally male roles, such as train drivers, to encourage women to apply.

Several interviewees suggested these methods have led to a greater intake of women while also benefitting the business at the same time.

Despite the majority of respondents suggesting that recruitment practices and a cultural shift regarding views of women in the industry are positive and accepted, some pointed to resistance or best practice not always being upheld by everyone who makes hiring decisions. However, it was pointed out that although this cultural shift will take time to develop the impact of younger people, and their ideas of fairness, entering the industry should result in change.

Overall, the data suggests that in most of the organisations represented by the respondent's steps are being taken to improve gender balance and female employability at the point of recruitment and selection.

Retention

With regard retention of employees, many respondents commented that their organisation actively seeks to retain all employees, both male and female. The data highlighted three main findings: the importance of equality of access to training; flexible working; and maternity leave terms and conditions. The first of these, training, is addressed in the subsection below [Training]. Flexibility is also addressed below [Flexible Working]. Therefore, the discussion here focusses on maternity leave terms and conditions. In general respondents noted that their organisation offered favourable terms and conditions with regards maternity leave, with strategies to support women such as fully supported maternity leave fully, option to return to work on part time basis, flexible working, and phased return to work offered.

One interesting and unique finding in an organisation involved sharing paternity leave and pay in order to remove any disadvantage for women taking maternity leave.

Overall, there were many examples of best practice and support offered regarding maternity leave. However, the data collected was limited to the UK and Ireland with very little information gathered from Spain and Poland regarding maternity leave. This should be followed up for consistency.

Promotion

Many respondents reported that there is equal access to promotion in their organisation. Indeed, there was one very positive example of women present across the hierarchy of the organisation with women present all the way up to managing director level.

Yet this example was unique in the data. Despite there being, in theory, equal access to promotion in their organisation gender segregation at promoted levels was apparent across organisations, sectors and locations. When asked why there are few women at senior levels respondents suggested men are more likely to achieve promotion. Respondents from Poland did report a few positive examples of promotion for women but ultimately, as in Ireland and the UK, there were few reports of women in senior positions.

According to the data generated in this study gender imbalance and female employability exists across the transport industry and across locations. HR policies are in place in organisations to promote equality of access to work and within work, yet despite this, recruitment practices and a 'glass ceiling' impact women in the industry. However, HR policy to aid retention of women, specifically maternity leave discussed here, is reported positively.

Job Characteristics - Terms and Conditions

The terms and conditions in any job are important to ensure equality and fairness. The research data examined here suggests that working hours and facilities impact upon gender balance and employability for women in the transport industry. As many FCs overlap discussion of the research data in relation to Terms and Conditions can be found elsewhere in this document: Facilities are examined in detail above under FC Female Facilities and working hours are examined below under FC Flexible Working.

Job Characteristics - Flexible Working

Analysis of the data highlighted that flexible working and caring/parenting responsibilities are linked and as such the research data overlaps regarding both areas. Flexible working, specifically with regard caring/parenting responsibilities, is examined in FC Caring/Parenting Responsibilities below. The focus here is on flexible working more generally.

Interestingly when interviewees were asked 'what would fairness for female employees in transport services look like?' flexibility was repeatedly mentioned as being key

Respondents offered examples of current flexible working practices in their organisation and implications for workers. However, overwhelmingly the data suggests that flexible working is only available for specific roles, and is mostly available for office-based roles:

The data highlighted that with regard flexibility only certain jobs, mostly office-based jobs, are compatible. Most interviewees pointed out that operational jobs are not compatible with flexibility (as pointed out above). However, there were a couple of exceptions where it was reported that operational jobs could be worked as job share. As one director pointed out, 'traditional arrangements' could be altered by 'thinking differently' about flexibility for all roles:

Job Characteristics - Training Provision

The data revealed several interesting points regarding training provision and gender balance. Firstly, generally there is equality of access to training, across sectors and locations, most usually paid for by employers. And secondly, evidence of a few organisations offering female specific training. Moreover, several respondents specifically pointed out that their training is paid for by their organisation.

One respondent reported that their practice of offering training ‘in-house’ or online is beneficial for the organisation and particularly beneficial for women with caring/parenting responsibilities. However, one respondent noted that in her organisation there is evidence women are not going for training as much as men:

Moreover, data revealed that training designed specifically for women was offered in a few of the organisations studied. One Irish organisation developed a programme to promote gender balance in the organisation, across frontline level and middle management level. The programme has been welcomed by participants. One other organisation also provided training, specifically for female managers, to aid progression.

Job Characteristics - Safety and Security

In terms of safety and security the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Job Characteristics - Negative Attitude of Male Colleagues

As examined in FC HR Policies - Recruitment above, the research data highlighted that at the point of recruitment and in work unconscious bias, conscious bias, discrimination, sexism, and a lack of fairness all impact upon gender balance and women’s employability in the industry. Examination of the data highlights such practices under the FC negative attitudes of male colleagues. Data suggests that many interviewees had experienced sexism and discrimination at work. Interviewees reported how they dealt with negative attitudes of male colleagues. This ranged from reporting such behaviour via official routes, personally challenging the behaviour to changing their language. Interestingly there were many examples given of interviewees who suggested you need a particular personality type to work in the industry, with traits like ‘thick skin’, ‘not taking things personally’ and ‘strength of character’ reported as being vital.

Personal Circumstances - Caring/Parenting Responsibilities

Numerous respondents reported that fairness in the transport industry is about flexibility, such as family friendly work hours, however the data suggests that many jobs in the sector are incompatible with such flexibility. (Flexible working is discussed fully in FC Flexible Working above) Overall, there was agreement from respondents that the nature of many roles in the transport industry, particularly engineering and operational roles, require shift work and working unsociable hours, and that while this may not be detrimental to women, or indeed men, without parenting or caring responsibilities, it does impact on gender balance and female employability when women have these responsibilities.

While it was agreed that it was discriminatory to suggest that women should provide the majority of childcare and caring in families the reality that these responsibilities fall more to women was recognised by interviewees. Evidence from the research data suggests that caring/parenting responsibilities impact upon gender balance and women's employability in the transport industry at the point of recruitment and selection. More generally regarding once employed in the industry, interviewees offered examples of the incompatibility of caring/parenting responsibilities and many roles:

So, fairness at work for women with caring responsibilities may not be limited to the type of work they do. However, several interviewees did highlight those caring responsibilities are impacted upon by more flexible working offered in certain roles and not in others. With women even moving positions, from frontline work to office work, in the same organisation to accommodate their caring responsibilities.

The data points to an incompatibility between childcare responsibilities and particular roles in the transport industry, that is front line, operational jobs specifically. Yet the experiences of participants in Poland suggest that this incompatibility can be overcome. The focus group participants discussed the importance of flexibility for those with caring responsibilities and highlighted that their organisation has a reputation for flexibility around this issue, offering job share and shift work that accommodates the childcare responsibilities of both men and women.

As pointed out in FC Flexible Working above the research data also highlights rare examples of measures put in place or suggestions going forward in other organisations out with Poland to increase the flexibility of operational jobs that traditionally have been less flexible.

As the data suggests focus group and interview data emphasised that both men and women have caring responsibilities. Moreover, the recent impact of the global pandemic, in particular the closing of childcare establishments and schools, has drawn attention to flexible work practises for individuals with caring responsibilities. The research data underlined that the measures put in place during the pandemic may lead to positive change in the transport sector going forwards.

Personal Circumstances - Economic Deprivation

In terms of economic deprivation, the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Residential Location/Work Distance

In terms of residential location/work distance the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Transport Access to Workplace

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics – Skills

The research data did not provide many insights into the FC Skills with regard gender balance, female employability or key factors influencing career choices for women. More generally the data highlighted that specialist skills impact the level or role undertaken by women, for example female engineers and females in middle management. These individuals, they suggest, possess academic qualifications that allow them to access these roles and/or join graduate programmes. However, many of the front line/operational roles are learned from within the organisation and the number of female apprentices appears to be low. Interestingly, one manager pointed out the emerging skills gap in the industry and the need to have a gender balanced workforce:

Individual Characteristics - Adaptability – Attitude to work

In terms of adaptability and attitude to work the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Educational Attainment

With regard FC Educational Attainment and gender balance and female employability the data highlighted that the lack of female role models, education and awareness for many jobs in the industry has an impact, resulting in fewer women than men in engineering and operational roles. This situation has led to a push from many organisations to educate females regarding job opportunities in the sector through contact with schools, colleges, universities and job fayres (as highlighted above in FC HR Policies – Recruitment above).

However, one interesting finding points to the job or organisation specificity of some jobs in the sector, meaning that ‘on the job learning’ is key.

Individual Characteristics - Health status and wellbeing

In terms of health status and wellbeing the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics – Demographic

In terms of the effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.) the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Research Question 3 Summary

How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?

To sum up, the job characteristics and contextual factors identified by the data as being important in terms of affecting gender balance and female employability (Research Question 3) in different areas in the transport sector were:

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors
- Policy and Legal
- Female Facilities
- HR Policies

- Terms and Conditions
- Flexible Working
- Training Provision
- Safety and Security
- Negative Attitude of Colleagues
- Caring/Parenting Responsibilities
- Skills
- Educational Attainment

The following Fairness Characteristics were not identified by participants in detail in the interviews. However, this may be due to time and subject discussion limitations in the interviews, rather than these not being important issues.

- Economic Deprivation
- Residential Location
- Transport Access
- Adaptability
- Health Status and Wellbeing
- Demographics – age, ethnicity etc.

Recommendations made by participants to enhance gender balance and female employability in the transport sector:

As evidenced above the research data suggests job segregation and lack of flexible working are among the biggest factors impacting gender balance and female employability in the sector. Respondents made recommendations to address these issues.

Regarding job segregation, to address the commonly reported theme that ‘you can’t be what you can’t see’ practices such as ‘women in transport days’, specific women in transport groups and educational events were cited as examples of support received that positively impact upon women employees and a more equal gender balance in the industry. Also, respondents noted the importance of education in schools, colleges and universities regarding the transport sector as a potential employer. Recommendations were also made to enhance flexible working across all job types in the sector.

“I think there are still some professions where women think ‘I wouldn’t be able to do that’. And when they suddenly see someone in a job ad and they see a woman doing it it’s a bit, what’s that saying, you can’t be what you can’t see. We need to see a lot more women in a lot more diverse roles and look at them and think ‘oh I can relate to that, maybe I could do that too, that looks like fun or interesting or challenging’.” Sarah F Director UK

“...for engineering, I think we need to go to the source. So, schools and colleges so that we get the fresh talent.” Samantha F Director UK

“They [women] are not aware at all, it’s not all just about dirty truck driving, the trucks now are really like, they are all IT, they have telematics and electronics. Our industry really needs to be pushing women forwards. The trade bodies should also be putting women forward, they are trying but it needs more than

a picture of a woman in a high viz and hard hat. Women cannot do this by ourselves we need the help of men; men need to understand the importance of females in the workplace.” Louise F Truck Director UK

Recommendations were also made to enhance flexible working across all job types in the sector:

“We have also introduced things like flexible working, and we introduced it a long time before COVID came and I am delighted to say that it enabled our business to do something amazing and keep going right from the start of lock down because all of our people were able to do flexible working. But we don’t just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers.” Naomi F Rail Director UK

And as this director pointed out, ‘traditional arrangements’ could be altered by ‘thinking differently’ about flexibility for all roles:

“There is not that thinking outside of the box (currently), well you know that could be done by two people it could be terms time it could be annualized hours, people are not thinking wider and that is why, you know it goes back to the traditional arrangements. I am seeing clients doing a complete U turn now and its whether that will happen with operational jobs. It is happening with office jobs. It’s how, you know, maybe could a job be done by one person doing two days and another three days, its thinking differently about things.” Frances F Rail Director UK

4.2.3 Key factors influencing career choices for women in transport (Research Question 4)

The following section set out the analysis in response to Research Question 4 (What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?) (See Annex 9 for full details and quotations extracted from interview/focus group data)

Socio Economic Conditions - Job segregation

In relation to increasing the participation of women employed in the transport sector a key factor for influencing women’s career choice is the concept of job segregation. Job segregation relates to the idea that there are jobs designated to either men or women only.

The data from our interviews suggest there was an overwhelming consensus that the industry, across job roles and sectors, is still viewed and experienced as a male dominated sector. Participants provided many specific examples from their own organisations.

One participant illustrated an apparent rationale for job segregation when discussing women applying for and working in the engineering department of a transport company claiming it was known to be a dirty job that requires strength. The ongoing workplace cultures that appear to still maintain job segregation amongst transport organisations was supported by examples of roles and departments that are still assumed by participants not to be suitable for women. Highlighting that within and across the transport sector there are still currently roles and departments that have no female employees, departments where women are not expected to be working and importantly where women are not expected to apply for roles.

Conversely these points above were refuted by women already working in the frontline of the transport sector who stated that they had not found any jobs they were prohibited from completing because of their sex and that in general there were always ways to work around obstacles to more equality in job access. The findings also reported that the majority of women who do work in the transport sector currently work in traditional female roles, with most female employees being office based in administrative roles etc.

The findings would indicate that there is a wider educational piece of work still required amongst and within transport organisations and importantly in schools and higher and further education to sign post the opportunities for young girls in STEM and engineering careers. The themes relating to education and the ongoing work by some transport organisations are discussed in detail below in their own section.

Socio Economic Conditions - Demand factors

When discussing participants' understanding of why women and girls are still so underrepresented in the transport sector, there were 3 main themes which emerged from the data which sit inside the FC demand factors, they were attracting women to the industry, recruitment processes, and processes put in place to retain women once they are employed.

In the first instance it was noted that young women and girls are not currently aware of the variety of roles available to women in the transport sector and that wider effort is required to engage young women and girls. In response to the current lack of female employees and in order to address the shortage of women employees many organisations have been attending open days at schools, career days at colleges and graduate recruitment events.

When discussing recruitment in more detail with participants, it emerged that the majority of organisations claim they currently run gender neutral recruitment campaigns which include images of women and men in roles and ensured that the language used in any advertising materials is also gender neutral by using a variety of software programmes available specifically to do so. However, when targeted recruitment for female employees was discussed as an option the majority of participants stated this was not something that they would support, with many claiming that it only adds 'a target' to the backs of women who have been recruited this way. One participant claimed their organisation had attempted to develop a recruitment campaign targeted at women, however, when pressed further the participant was unable to inform us of how successful that campaign had been in terms of female applicants for roles at that organisation.

Participants also highlighted that once a transport organisation has successfully employed women in frontline roles, they then had to ensure that an organisational culture was developed to support and maintain women in these roles. The importance of retaining female employees also highlighted the significance of female employees having female role models and/or mentors in the workplace as an important factor in their career choices.

With some female senior managers agreeing and claiming that they believed it was their responsibility to support the women coming after them in terms of employment.

However, when probed to explain how their organisation actively looked to retain female employees, some of the frontline employees were more negative in their experiences stating that there was no specific awareness of retaining women employees. One train driver claimed their organisation did not have enough female employees in the first instance to provide roles models or mentoring.

Socio-Economic Conditions- Policy and Legal

In order to explore the impact of employment policies and law across the partner states (UK Scotland Ireland Spain and Poland) with regards to influencing women's career choices, we asked participants "are current employment practices in your country fair for women".

The replies produced themes based on an acknowledgement that there are many policies currently in place but they are not all utilised consistently across all organisations, that they are not taken seriously by all organisations and are there as a form of a tick box exercise and importantly that the policies are being developed by men in board rooms who have no real knowledge or understanding of the experiences of women on the frontline, with the majority of replies from managers and frontline staff claiming that more needs to be done.

In interviews with HR personnel and others it was highlighted that in many circumstances the responsibility for local decisions such as availability of part time hours and flexible shifts was the responsibility of local managers and was not in fact a piece of written organisational policy. This raises questions regarding the movement of managers and what happens when after agreeing something at a local level they move out of that role and someone else moves into it. Would that mean all of the actions previously put in place disappear?

Socio-Economic Conditions - Female Facilities

One of the largest findings that emerged from the data which was shown to influence career choice for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport was related to the provision of female facilities. For the majority of participants this focused on a lack of spaces for women when they had to share toilet facilities with men or use the disabled toilets, therefore impacting on the access of disabled people to their own toilets.

With regards to women's concerns, one Spanish participant highlighted the importance for women to have access to clean and sanitary facilities during menstruation and also in relation to the time taken and frequency of these visits during a woman's menstrual cycle, which impact on the daily routines and duties of women specifically at this time. In terms of female drivers and access to female facilities on the road, one participant claimed that in their organisation there is an awareness that not all routes provide access to suitable facilities (approximately 30%) and that adjustments are made for female employees in relation to having men on this specific routes. The indication from other participants was that in their opinion many organisations have been remiss in taking cognisance of what women in the workplace require. This concept was supported by comments from Polish participants who discussed the experience of their own organisation and how no one had ever thought to include facilities for women in certain areas of the organisation.

The replies from across countries and particularly frontline employees supported this notion that currently it is assumed that needs of men and women in the workplace are equal and no additional measures for women are required. However, many of the participants when discussing women's toilets and facilities also discussed the current situation for men, which in the rail sector particularly appears to be just as unsatisfactory for men as women.

A lack of policy and spaces for nursing mothers with regards to breast feeding or expressing milk were raised by Spanish participants. However, in Poland it appears that at least one transport organisation already provides a certain degree of flexibility for nursing mothers.

As these findings highlight, the provision of female facilities is a major factor for women in relation to their career choices in terms of privacy, dignity and health. It would be hard to imagine any other employment sector that did not actively plan for or acknowledge the specific spaces and facilities female employees require to be able to be fully employed.

Job Characteristics - HR Policies

The discussions relating to demand factors and jobs segregation also covered many HR policies that support the inclusion of women therefore this section will discuss policies on access to training and promotion opportunities for women and how these affect the career choices of women.

With regards to equality of opportunity for women to access training provision, the majority of participants stated that across countries and organisations they had experienced no inequality and that men and women tended to have the same access to training within their own organisations. In relation to railways and road haulage this was supported by the additional caveats that all drivers had to complete the same level of driver training legally to be able to commence employment in the first place. This was supported by a coach driver who also highlighted that anyone who wished to become a driver must complete the same training which is legislative based.

However, when it comes to ongoing training whilst in employment it was noted that that some women perhaps do not always take advantage of training opportunities provided. However, it was also noted that not all training can be delivered locally and may entail days away from home which would cause additional stresses for parents or those with caring responsibilities. Overall, participants agreed that in general all training that was provided by their employer was not based on sex in anyway and both male and female employees were given equal opportunity to take part. With participants in Ireland highlighting the good work their organisation has been doing in reference to women focused training and supporting women into higher education.

In relation to promotion prospects, one participant from the rail industry reported that within their organisation to support women in their personal development and to assist them in promotion. When participants were asked if female employees had ever transferred from the traditional office roles to the frontline or be upskilled only two responded that they had, indicating lateral moves and opportunities within transport could be very limited, affecting women's choices in relation to careers.

Job Characteristics - Terms and Conditions

As was expected the data collected which related to the FC “Terms and Conditions” suggested that across countries and transport organisations, notions of equal pay for women were, in the main, not a key factor for women as legislation within Spain, Ireland, UK, Scotland and Poland prohibits any organisation from paying men more for the same role as women.

However, the impact of shift patterns on female employees, particularly those who have caring or parenting responsibilities, was identified as a key factor relating to women’s career choices under the FC “Terms and Conditions”. From an organisational perspective, participants at management and director level although, agreeing that shift work can be difficult for women and those men who have caring and parenting responsibilities, admitted that it was the nature of their business that dictated working hours. Whilst a member of HR staff pointed out that it would also not be a fair working environment if only women were allowed to take the 9am to 3pm shifts. Participants from Spain discussed their experiences of having reduced working hours, and policies already being in place. However, one participant did suggest that in their experience they had more flexibility in their previous role than in their current organisation. The data collected suggests that shift work which is inherent in all passenger transport systems is a major factor for women when deciding on career prospects, and importantly in this case it is also a factor for men particularly those with parenting or caring responsibilities.

Job Characteristics - Flexible working

The provision of flexible working or having access to flexible working was a theme which emerged across all employment FCs and in relation to both research questions related to women’s employment in the transport sector. One quote summed up the concept of flexible working particularly from a women’s perspective as being based on organisations acknowledging the differences between many women and men that impact on the daily lives of women and thus their working potential.

The data showed that both managers and frontline workers reported that it has traditionally been difficult to provide part time or flexibility within the transport sector, particularly in passenger transport, with claims that the business could not itself support part time arrangements. However, a further comment by a Business Services Director of a passenger transport organisation cited that they have been implementing flexible and job share opportunities for their staff, including train drivers for some time and in the main, it was working well and had been successfully received by staff. The data collected from Poland suggested that at least in one of the transport organisations work has been done to ensure that flexibility, especially for parents is being provided and is available for men and women.

COVID and remote working during the recent lock downs was also discussed in terms of how positive it was in showing that people, men and women, were still able to carry out their roles working flexible hours at home and not be based in an office. The data suggests that many participants are keen to maintain the working arrangements put in place during lock down, and that in some cases transport organisations have already seen the benefit of flexible and remote working.

Job Characteristics - Training Provision

Opportunities for further training and equal access to training was also a factor that was important to women when considering career choices in the transport sector and is discussed fully in the Job Characteristics - HR Policies above.

Job Characteristics - Safety and security

The safety and security theme included data on the provision of PPE designed for women and not a unisex design, additional provisions for lone working and training in protection and awareness. With regards to the provision of female designed PPE the data suggests that a majority of transport organisations are still providing what they refer to as unisex PPE which some frontline workers defined as “designed for men”. With one female engineer claiming they had to supply their own PPE equipment for their job and pay for it out of their own pocket. The impact of not providing suitably designed PPE, tools or uniforms for female staff was summed up in one comment by a train driver who stated simply that it showed female staff were not being valued.

Participants were asked directly “In what ways does your company promote a safe and secure working environment for women?” It appeared in some cases that this question itself encouraged managers to reflect on the current provisions of safety for women employees, with acknowledgements that there were no female specific safety policies in their organisation. One director stated quite clearly that in general there is a focus on the safety of passengers and how there until recently is the safety of female employees was not something they had considered. In Ireland there was also no acknowledgement that there were any specific policies in place for female specific safety.

A general lack of focus for female safety was also discussed by frontline workers during their interviews with train drivers and haulage drivers highlighting their own personal experiences of incidences where they felt unsafe being women. And one Spanish tram driver admitting that it was only very recently that their organisation provided some training in dealing with harassment at work.

Job Characteristics - Negative attitude of colleagues

A further factor that is important in relation to women’s career choices is the perceived reaction of their male colleagues to having women alongside them in the transport sector. This theme was reported from women and men working across all roles and sectors with directors, senior managers and frontline managers claiming the negative attitude of men towards women employees in the transport sector can still be found even in the board room.

Personal Circumstances - Caring/Parenting Responsibilities

The data collected showed that single largest factor to affect women and their career choices was in relation to their role as a parent or primary care giver. The effects on employment of being a parent or having caring responsibilities were reported in such wide depth that they cover all the FC’s highlighted here.

Personal Circumstances - Economic deprivation (living area social network etc)

In terms of economic deprivation, the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Transport access to workplace

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics – Skills

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Adaptability – Attitude to work

In terms of adaptability and attitude to work the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC. However, there are themes based on flexibility of working location and hours and the impact of shift work that can be read in other sections here.

Individual Characteristics - Educational attainment

In terms of educational attainment as a key factor for women when considering a career in the transport sector, it was noted across partner countries that this in the main related to a traditional low number of young females studying STEM or Technical subjects that underpin many transport sector roles.

However, one of the Polish participants raised an interesting concept with regards to education stating that there were no educational qualifications for their role and everything they learned was on the job and organisational specific. To address this situation many organisations stated that they now attend open days and career days at schools and colleges, accessing young people before they become graduates, to help direct and support girls into the sector.

Individual Characteristics - Health status and wellbeing.

In terms of health status and wellbeing the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Demographic (age ethnicity etc)

In terms of the effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.) the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Findings emerging from the data not included in FC's.

Findings which emerged from the data that were not previously accounted for in the FC's relating to the key factors influencing career choices for women, included:

The individual characteristics/personality of the women

Many participants when discussing women employed in the transport sector provided caveats to their statements suggesting that the current working environments and cultures in which they worked would not be attractive to all women. The reasons given were based on both structural and individual causes such as the existing male dominated organisational culture within the transport sector, woman having little or no existing credibility in the transport sector, workspaces being cold and dirty and the individual personality of some women who maybe were not “thick skinned” enough to deal with the environment.

The comments regarding individual personality traits, and thick skinned as being an attribute for women working in transport came from a variety of participants from across both frontline and management roles and came from mainly UK Scotland and Ireland.

A will to Change.

Many of the participants when discussing factors that influence women’s career choices in respect to employment in the transport sector claimed that was already an acknowledgement that things had to change to support women as employees in the sector and to encourage more women to come into the sector.

The requirement for more women in senior roles to help improve and promote female recruitment across the transport sector was discussed widely with multiple participants from across roles in the UK/Scotland claiming that currently the majority of senior executive board members in the sector were “male, pale and stale”, which according to the Oxford Dictionary of Human Resource Management (2017) refers to “a phrase uttered to condemn an organization for being dominated by white, middle-aged men. It is often used in relation to corporate board composition but can be applied to any collection of people that fails to reflect a diverse sex, racial, and age mix” (ibid 2017: online).

Research Question 4 Summary

What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

The following section set out the analysis in response to Research Question 4.

To sum up the key factors identified by the data as being important in relation to women’s career choices in the transport sector were:

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors – recruitment and retainment
- Policy and Legal – employment policies
- Female facilities
- HR Policies – training and promotion
- Terms and Conditions – equal pay, shift patterns,
- Flexible Working
- Safety and Security – PPE etc.
- Negative attitude of colleagues

- Caring and parenting responsibilities
- Educational Attainment

These Fairness Characteristics not found in the interview data. However, this may be due to time and subject discussion limitations in the interviews, rather than these not being important issues.

- Health status and wellbeing
- Demographics – age, ethnicity etc.
- Attitude to work
- Skills
- Transport Access to work
- Economic Deprivation

Additional themes extracted from the data not already recognised as fairness characteristics were:

- The individual characteristics/personality of the women
- There is an acknowledgement that more women need to be attracted to the sector and a will to change within the sector.

These issues can be considered during the further development of the fairness characteristics and toolbox.

Recommendations made by participants to encourage more women employees in the transport sector.

- Flexible working available for men and women
- More women in senior roles
- When recruiting take 5 male and 5 female for each role
- Input at school level to attract young girls and women to STEM

4. Conclusions

This report presented a definition of fairness as operationalised in the DIAMOND project and the results of a scoping review for each project Use Case. Based on the primary data collected in other parts of the project (especially in Work Packages 3 and 4 and associated Deliverables). These provide analytical and practical initial frameworks that can be adapted to specific organisational or contextual circumstances.

As stated at the beginning of this paper this deliverable was tasked with providing the answers to the following questions:

- What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
- How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?
- How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

The data analysis discussed above provides us with the following findings in relation to each of them. The key factors include those FC's that have been corroborated via other research methods have been listed below.

- **RQ1. What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?**

The analysis of data from across the methodologies suggests that following key factors affect women's choices in relation to them as users of transport.

- Safety and security
- Costs
- Facilities for infant feeding and changing.
- Operational hours and frequency of public service
- For AV's specifically simultaneity, trust in technology

- **RQ2. How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?**

When we examine the key factors identified and corroborated by the DIAMOND projects multiple research method approach, it suggests that in the main the high-level factors are similar across all transport modes, and that women are in the main interested and focused on safety and security, costs, frequency, accessibility, availability, which should be understood in the context of the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines.

- **RQ3. How different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?**

The triangulation of data analysis produced the following corroborated Fairness Characteristics.

that affect gender balance and female employability in different areas:

- Job Segregation
 - Demand Factors
 - Policy and Legal
 - Female Facilities
 - HR Policies
 - Terms and Conditions
 - Flexible Working
 - Training Provision
 - Safety and Security
 - Negative Attitude of Colleagues
 - Caring/Parenting Responsibilities
 - Skills
 - Educational Attainment
- **RQ4. What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?**

The triangulation of data analysis produced the following corroborated the Fairness Characteristics as key in influencing women's career choices.

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors – recruitment and retainment
- Policy and Legal – employment policies
- Female facilities
- HR Policies – training and promotion
- Terms and Conditions – equal pay, shift patterns,
- Flexible Working
- Safety and Security – Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) etc.
- Negative attitude of colleagues
- Caring and parenting responsibilities
- Educational Attainment

5. References

1. Adams, J., Greig, M., McQuaid, R. (2000) 'Mismatch unemployment and local labour-market efficiency: the role of employer and vacancy characteristics', *Environment and Planning A* (32) pp 1841 -1856 accessed [here](#)
2. Arksey, H. & O'Malley, L. (2005) 'Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 8 (1), pp19-32 accessed [here](#)
3. Astor, E., Onsaló, M., Perea, M. (2017) 'Women's career development in the construction industry across 15 years: main barriers', *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology* 15 (2) pp. 199-221
4. Basarić, A., Vujičić, A., Mitrović, J., Bogdanović, V., Nenad Saulić, N. (2016) 'Gender and Age Differences in the Travel Behaviour – A Novi Sad Case Study', *Transportation Research Procedia* (14) pp4324-4333 accessed [here](#)
5. Blair, N. Hine, J, Murtaza, S and Bukhari, A. (2013) 'Analysing the impact of network change on transport disadvantage: a GIS-based case study of Belfast,' *Journal of Transport Geography*, 31, pp. 192-200 accessed [here](#)
6. Blumenberg, E. (2004) 'Beyond the Spatial Mismatch: Welfare Recipients and Transportation Policy', *Journal of Planning Literature* (19) pp182-205 accessed [here](#)
7. Bowling, B. (2007) Fair and Effective Policing Methods: Towards 'Good Enough' Policing, *Journal of Scandinavian Studies in Criminology and Crime Prevention*, 8:sup1, 17-32, DOI: 10.1080/14043850701695023
8. Buchmann, C. (2013) CARS 2020: Action Plan for a competitive and sustainable automotive industry in Europe Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions accessed [here](#)
9. Bullock, C., Brereton, F. and Bailey, S. (2017) 'The Economic Contribution of Public Bike-share to the Sustainability and Efficient Functioning of Cities', *Sustainable Cities and Society* (28) pp76-87 access [here](#)
10. Creswell, J W and Creswell J D (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Fifth Edition. Sage. London.
11. Denzin, N.K. (2012) Triangulation 2.0, *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 6(2) 80–88 <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1558689812437186>
12. Chen, Z., van Lierop, D., and Ettema, D. (2020) 'Dockless bike sharing systems: what are the implications?' in *Transport Reviews*, 40 (3) pp333-353
13. Chowdhury, S. (2019) 'Role of Gender in the Ridership of Public Transport Routes Involving Transfers', *Transportation Research Record*, 2673(4), pp. 855–863 accessed [here](#)
14. Clark, B., Chatterjee, K. and Melia, S. (2016) 'Changes to commute mode: The role of life events, spatial context and environmental attitude', *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* (89) pp 89-105 accessed [here](#)
15. Corral, A. and Isusi, I. (2007) Innovative gender equality measures in the transport industry *European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions* accessed [here](#)
16. Couch, S. and Smalley, H. (2019) 'Encouraging Equitable Bikeshare: Implications of Docked and Dockless Models for Spatial Equity', *arXiv: Applications* accessed [here](#)

17. Earchy, J. (1998) *Usability Maturity Model: Lloyd's Register and the European Commission: London*
18. European Union Commission (2017) *Mobility and Transport, Women in transport* accessed [here](#)
19. Fincher, A.& Levin, G. (1997) *Project Management Maturity Model*. Project management institute 28th annual seminars & symposium, pp 1028-1035 Chicago, Illinois
20. Fishman E., Washington, S. and Haworth, N. (2013) 'Bike Share: A Synthesis of the Literature', *Transport Reviews* 33 (2) pp 148-165, accessed [here](#)
21. Fleming, M. (2000). 'Safety culture maturity model', *Offshore Technology Report-Health and Safety Executive OTH*.
22. French, E. and Strachan, G. (2008) 'Evaluating equal employment opportunity and its impact on the increased participation of men and women in the transport industry', *Transportation Research Part A*, 43, pp. 78-89 accessed [here](#)
23. Geurs, K.T., Boon, W. and Van Wee, B. (2009) 'Social Impacts of Transport: Literature Review and the State of the Practice of Transport Appraisal in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom', *Transport Reviews*, 29, 1, 69–90.
24. Giannelos, I., Smit, G., Lakamp, R., Gonzalez Martinez, A., Dorantes, L., Doll, C., Tanis, J., Vroonhof, P. and Perciaccante, F. (2008) *Business case to increase female employment in Transport* accessed [here](#)
25. Guenther, E. Humbert, A and Kelan. E. (2018) 'Gender Vs. Sex', *Oxford Research Encyclopaedia Business and Management* accessed [here](#)
26. Hail, Y. and McQuaid, R. (2021). 'The concept of fairness in relation to women transport users', *Sustainability*, 13, 5, 2919. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052919> accessed [here](#)
27. Hanson, S. (2010) Gender and mobility: 'New approaches for informing sustainability', in *Gender Place and Culture*, 1, pp. 5-23
28. Hefley, W.E., Curtis, B. Miller, S. & Konrad, M. (1995) 'People Capability Maturity Model incorporating human resources into process improvement programs'. Proceedings of the annual international symposium- *National Council on Systems Engineering* No 5 pp 559-566
29. Hosford, K. (2019) 'Who stands to benefit? Investigating equity in public bike share programs' in *Transportation Research Record* 2672(36) pp42–50 accessed [here](#)
30. Houston, D and Tilley, S (2016) 'The gender turnaround: Young women now travelling more than young men', *Journal of Transport Geography*, 54, pp. 349-358 accessed [here](#)
31. HSE (1999) *HSG48 Reducing error and influencing behaviour*, Norwich HMSO.
32. Lee, R., Sener, N. and Jones, N. (2017) 'Understanding the role of equity in active transportation planning in the United States', *Transport Review* 37 (20) pp211-226 accessed [here](#)
33. Levy, K. (2013) 'Travel choice reframed: "deep distribution" and gender in urban transport', *Environment and Urbanization*, 25(1), pp47–63 accessed [here](#)
34. Lucas, K., van Wee, B., & Maat, K. (2015). 'A method to evaluate equitable accessibility: Combining ethical theories and accessibility-based approaches', *Transportation*, 1–18. doi:10.1007/s11116-015-9585-2
35. Madariaga, I. (2013) 'From Women in Transport to Gender in Transport: Challenging Conceptual Frameworks for Improved Policy Making', *Journal of International Affairs* 67 (1) *The Gender Issue: Beyond Exclusion* (FALL/WINTER 2013), pp. 43-65

36. Martens K. (2012) 'Justice in transport as justice in accessibility: applying Walzer's 'Spheres of Justice' to the transport sector', *Transportation* (39) pp pages 1035–1053 accessed [here](#)
37. Mays N., Roberts E., Popay J. (2001) 'Synthesizing research evidence', in *Studying the Organisation and Delivery of Health Services: Research methods*, Fulop, N., Allen, P., Clarke, A., Black, N. (eds), Routledge: London; pp. 188–219.
38. McIntosh, B., McQuaid, R., Munro, A., and Dabir-Alai, P. (2012) 'Motherhood and its impact on career progression – the case of Scottish nurses 2000-2008', *Gender in Management*, 27, 5, 346-364.
39. McNeil, N., Broach, J. and Dill, J. (2018) *Breaking Barriers to Bike Share: Lessons on Bike Share Equity Strategic Plan Document* accessed [here](#)
40. McQuaid, R. (2009) 'A model of the travel to work limits of parents', *Research in Transportation Economics* pp1 -10 accessed [here](#)
41. McQuaid, R. and Chen, T. (2012) 'Commuting times – the role of gender, children and part time work', *Research in Transportation Economics*, 34, 66-73 accessed [here](#)
42. Munn, Z., Peters, M., Stern, C., Tufanaru, C. McArthur, C and Aromataris, E. (2018) 'Systematic review or scoping review? Guidance for authors when choosing between a systematic or scoping review approach', *BMC Medical Research Methodology* (18) 143 pp1-7 accessed [here](#)
43. Ogilvie, F. and Goodman, A. (2012) 'Inequalities in usage of a public bicycle sharing scheme: Socio-demographic predictors of uptake and usage of the London (UK) cycle hire scheme', *Preventative Medicine*, 5, pp. 40-45 accessed [here](#)
44. Oliveira, S. and Nisbett, R. (2018) 'Demographically diverse crowds are typically not much wiser than homogeneous crowds', *Psychological and Cognitive Sciences* 115 (9) pp2066-2071 accessed [here](#)
45. Patrykk, M.C., Curtis, B., Chrissis, M.B. & Weber, C.V. (1993) 'Capability Maturity Model, Version 1.1.' *IEEE Software* 10 (4) 18-27.
46. Pereira, R.H.M., Schwanen, T. and Banister, D. (2017) 'Distributive justice and equity in transportation', *Transport Reviews*, 37(2), 170-191.
47. Pflugfelder, E (2018) 'Autonomous Vehicles and Gender A Commentary', *Transfers* 8 (1) Accessed [here](#)
48. Pham, M., Rajić, A., Greig, J., Sargeant, J., Papadopoulos, A. and McEwen, S. (2014) 'A scoping review of scoping reviews: advancing the approach and enhancing the consistency' in *Research Synthesis Methods*, 5, pp. 371-385 accessed [here](#)
49. Poveda-Reyes, S., Malviya, A. K., García-Jiménez, E., Molero, G. D., Leva, M. C., & Santarremigia, F. E. (2021). Application of Mathematical and Computational Methods to Identify Women's Priorities in Transport. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2845. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052845>
50. Sánchez de Madariaga, I. (2013) 'From Women in Transport to Gender in Transport: Challenging the Conceptual Frameworks for Improved Policymaking', *Journal of International Affairs*, 67 (1) *The Gender Issue*: pp. 43-65 accessed [here](#)
51. Serna, A., Ruiz, T., Gerrikagoitia, J. and Arroy, R. (2019) Identification of Enablers and Barriers for Public Bike Share System Adoption using Social Media and Statistical Models, *Sustainability* (11) accessed [here](#)
52. Scott, J. (2018) *The Persistence of Gender Inequality How politics constructs gender, and gender constructs politics* accessed [here](#)

53. Social Exclusion Unit (2003) *Making the Connections: Final Report on Transport and Social Exclusion*. London: ODPM.
54. Sechrest, L. and Sidani, S. (1995) Quantitative and qualitative methods: Is There an Alternative?', *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 18 (1), pp. 77-87.
55. Strachan, G., Burgess, J. and Henderson, L. (2007) 'Equal Employment Opportunity Legislation and Policies: the Australian Experience', *Equal Opportunities International*, 26 (6) pp525–540 accessed [here](#)
56. Teschke, K., Chinn, A. and Brauer (2017) 'Proximity to four bikeway types and neighbourhood-level cycling mode share of male and female commuters', *The Journal of Transport and Land Use* 10 (1) pp 695-713 accessed [here](#)
57. Wang, K. and Akar, G. (2019) 'Gender gap generators for bike share ridership: Evidence from Citi Bike systems in New York', *Journal of Transport Geography*, 76, pp. 1 -9 accessed [here](#)
58. Wright, T. (2014) 'Gender, sexuality and male-dominated work: the intersection of long-hours working and domestic life', *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(6) pp. 985–1002 accessed [here](#)

Annex I Women as Users of Public Transport Scoping Review

Annex 2 Women as Users of Autonomous Cars Scoping Review

Annex 3 Women as Users of Bike Sharing Scoping Review

Annex 4 Women Employed in Transport Scoping Review

Annex 5 NVivo Codes Used for Use Case IV

Name	Description	Files	References
Additional Themes Emerging			
A will to change.			
Anonymous Applications and CV's			
Female HGV Drivers			
Male Pale and Stale			
More representation of women is needed.			
Personality Traits - thick skinned			
Speaking Up As A Woman			
Strategic Director Level			
What does fairness for women in employment look like			
COVID Replies			
Both home and office			
Challenges faced working at home.			
Challenges of working in usual location.			
How did your organisation support you?			
This participant is self-employed.			
What could your organisation have done better?			

Working from home			
Individual Characteristics			
Adaptability			
Demographics			
Economic deprivation			
Educational level or attainment			
Health Status and Well being			
Skills			
Job Characteristics			
Female facilities			
HR policies			
Are current employment practices fair for women			
No			
Yes			
Flexibility is required			
Promotion			
Recruitment			
All roles are advertised as gender neutral.			
Company attends career and education days to encourage employment.			

No Targeted Recruitment for Women			
Targeted Recruitment for women employees is used.			
Retention of women employees			
Be flexible.			
Maternity Leave			
We try to retain all employees			
Safety & security			
Additional Provisions for women			
Is the same for women and men			
PPE			
Terms and Conditions			
Family Friendly Work Hours are supported			
Shift work and Impacts on Women Employees			
Women and men have an equal rate of pay			
Training Provision			
Personal Circumstances			
Access to resources			
Barriers faced as employee			
Caring and or parenting responsibilities			

Economic deprivation			
Female Role models - support			
I have faced no barriers in my employment.			
Social or Cultural Barriers			
Support received.			
Recommendations made.			
Socio-economic conditions			
Demand factors			
Job segregation			
Examples of Male Dominated Sector			

Annex 6 Use Case III UK Interview Data

Sample characteristics

Five participants took part in the interview aged between 25 and 64. The majority of the interviewees were female (60.0%), 60.0% of participants were aged between 25 and 44. All participants reported using bike-sharing services, and white (60.0%). 20.0% of the participants cycle to work and cycle between 30 and 35 minutes to work. 57.1 % of them are in fulltime employment. None of the participants reported living with and travelling with dependents under five years.

Choice of Bike-share.

In general, all the interviewees have either used bike-sharing services before or have had practical and management experience with bike-sharing services. The interview context meant that interviewees explained the reasons they cycle and how they benefit from cycling. The reason for the choice of shared bikes was found to centre on leisure, commuting, need to be active and environmental. Various aspects of bike-sharing such as cost of hiring, and freedom from the responsibility of storage and maintenance. Interviewees indicated that shared bikes are convenient and quicker. Bike-sharing is a perfect mobility option for completing the last leg of a mix-mode trip as well as for tourist and visitors.

“I cycled from my area into the city centre. Cut across Gorgie Road, Princess Street, and Nicholson Street and back. So, it is enjoyable”. (Female, 35-44, UK)

“And talking about bikes sharing services, yes, I've used one of the Edinburgh cycle companies that does bike sharing, which is really good. And I've had a good experience ... cycling is good, and I really like it I wish I can cycle more often than it is currently”. (Female, 25-34, UK)

“So, the bikes I find easier to use than I may be expected. In terms of how they worked, some bikes you cannot adjust or lay? I wasn't sure some people have told me that they were quite heavy”. (Female, 35-44, UK)

“Rather, than having to buy a bike they can try our bikes ... and some people use it for commuting now to go into work, etc. But also, a little leisure use as well.” (Male, 55-64, UK)

“I realized that it was not just about cycling, it was about actual active travel and basically the environment, the urban environment, improving it for people rather than it being completely dominated by cars. I think the best side, from my experience is that you can actually use it when you go to visit somewhere where you would not normally, ... people who are visiting, I think it is really a good thing. Obviously, in places where there is a lot of tourism, Copenhagen has a lot of tourists, Amsterdam has a lot of tourists. It's obviously a big thing there. So, I think for mixed mode journeys. I think it really comes into its own. ... I can see myself actually using such a facility in that way. ... cycle to the station here, leave my bike, and then go into Manchester, and then continue my journey on a bike-share at the other end.” (Male, 55-64, UK)

Aside from the reported freedom and convenience of using bike-sharing services to meet their mobility need, Participants also identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services, which limits the use of the services, particularly among women. Barriers cited by participants include bikes unavailability or shortage at the stations, unsafe infrastructure, lack of appropriate bike accessories, and safety. A number of suggestions and recommendations address these barriers were similarly made to increase the ridership of bike-sharing services. The section below presents the perceived barriers and mitigation measures.

Accessibility & Spontaneity

The participants indicated their desire to cycle and use bike-sharing services, however, there was an indication that participants had concerns about some aspects of the bike-sharing services. There were doubts about the ability of the current bike-sharing services to replace the traditional mobility modes due to concerns about the level of reliability associated with some services. The unavailability of bikes at the stations when needed, the unavailability of vacant docking points at the stations to return bike, the distance to the nearest station, the location of the docking station and bicycle paths, and the level of safety and protection provided by the cycle infrastructure are some of the issue's users consider when planning a trip involving bike-sharing. There were concerns about the lack of real-time information on the availability or unavailability of bikes at the station on the operator's apps. In most cases participants will walk to an empty station after searching and walking to the station at the advice of the app. These and similar concerns limit the participation in bike-sharing services. For instance.

“There are many at time even when the weather is good during summer, when I try to find a bike location, you search and find one but by the time you get there you will not see the bike, and this is discouraging. You can only search for a bike on the app but the cant reserve it”. (Female, 35-44 UK)

“The bikes are not well maintained sometimes you get there, and the bikes are looking very dirty. You have to clean it out yourself.”

“The downside or the difficulties would be sometimes when you don't go through the docking stations quite in time you might not find the female bikes which are very much comfortable in terms of seating”. (Female, 25-34 UK)

An operator of bike-sharing services in the UK indicated that complaints about the “lack of bikes” at the stations is the most received complaints the get from users of their services.

“The most recent complaint is really been mostly getting through is probably tend to be lack of bikes ... often, I've got emails talking about there is no bikes in this area, no bikes there. So that is one of concerns they raised the most to me”. (Male, 55-64 UK)

In some instances, users reported walking for more than a mile to the nearest station to access a bike or having to cycle to another station far from their trip destination to return a bike after their trip because the station at their destination did not have a vacant docking point.

“Problem I used to have was that where I used to leave there were no bikes available around, so I need to walk like for an extra mile. And sometimes I might be unlucky before I get there the people that live close

by must have gotten the bikes. So, I think just eat didn't have enough locations close to each neighbourhood". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"The there is a problem I have had with docked bike sharing, where there wasn't anywhere to leave the bike when I got to my destination. ... So, I had to go and find another place to dock it and then walk back. ... And I think it's an obstacle that's particularly a problem with docked bike sharing systems". (Male, 55-64 UK)

"But if you're looking to have a cycle, a hirer points near your home, and one near your school or nursery, and one near your shops, then that doesn't necessarily exist in more rural areas, or in the outskirts of the cities or towns, they tend to be concentrated more in city centre, with some outliers". (Female, 35-44 UK)

Concerns raised about "Accessibility and Spontaneity" sustains the perception of 'unreliability' of bike-sharing services and have significant impact of user and potential user participation.

Safety & Security

The Safety and security of the user became up strongly as one of the major barriers and setbacks in the adoption and continual usage of the bike-sharing services. Participants had concerns with the safety.

Level on a significant proportion of the bike infrastructure (stations and paths). Participants expressed worries about the aggressive driving behaviour of some drivers. Cycling on busy roads with heavy vehicular traffic, and paths and stations with inadequate lighting raises safety concerns for most users and a major cycling deterrent. There is also concerns about the safety of the infrastructure and whether they provide adequate level of protection for cyclist. This concern reinforces the assertion that women are more likely than men to experience and report a frightening situation.

"For my personal experience, I don't know that there is necessarily a specific safety concern with the bikes themselves. It's more about the infrastructure that is in place." (Female, 35-44 UK)

"Busy main roads with heavy traffic, a lot of aggressive driving and so on. So, I started to become active as a result of that as an activist. I bought a video camera and started to report drivers to the police and that didn't work so I started complaining to the police. It's really only the motor vehicles and the lack of protected infrastructure. That is the obstacle for me. ... the big thing there is just traffic. It is motor vehicles where I live, most of the roads are dominated by motor vehicles." (Male, 55-64 UK)

Social Constraints

Women responsibility and travel patterns defined by the constructed societal norms and cultural constraints have created agenda difference in terms of how and where people actually travel to and purposes. This plays a significant role in the choice of transport by women. Most participants raised concerns about the absence carry baskets or racks on their services providers' bike fleet. Moreover, the lack of child seats and accessories for users with children and the inadequacy or discontinuity of the cycle infrastructure possess a major barrier to most users. Thus, some categories of people or potential users such as people travelling with children, shoppers and travellers with luggage who wishes to use bike-share services are excluded from the using this mobility option.

“So, you know, those sorts of gendered societal norms, I think, have a massive impact. ... if you're thinking about some of the other roles that women tend to have in society, in terms of childcare and shopping and all that kind of thing, then I think that presents a different need. The bikes may not necessarily be suitable for because they do not have provision for children or you know, carrying, a lot of shopping”. (Female, 35-44)

“Women sometimes are more concerned about things like their hair being affected when they wear a helmet, that sort of thing.” (Male, 55-64 UK)

Weather & Topography

Weather and the topography of the terrain has been indicated as a major barrier to cycling and bike-share for users. While the issue of topography could be over with E-bikes, windy, rainy, and snowy weather tend to hinder the use of bike-share significantly.

“If available, daily use. Unless it’s raining.” (Female, 35-44)

“If it’s not raining, I try to travel by bike as often as possible”. (Female, 25-34)

“The new electric bikes, I'll say, obviously, if they kick in, when there's a slope. ... there is no confirmed data to put out, but I will imagine, more females are now probably using the bikes because of this. Topography is having a significant impact on cycling”. (Male, 55-64)

Design & Functionality

The size, aesthetics and accessories of a bike are suggested to affect user perception and satisfaction of the services and have impact on the acceptance and adoption of bike sharing services. Some participants have concerns about the size and comfortability of the seats on most of the bikes as well.

For instance, women prefer low frame or bikes with step through frames. Presented below are the concerns expressed by some participants.

“the seats were too small, they didn’t make the seat like more comfortable, just a tiny seat. And when you sit on it for too long, your butt starts to hurt because some of us are a little big on the plus size”. (Female, 45-54)

“Also imagine, the looks of the bikes as well, there are a lot of people who are happy with the aesthetics, they will be happy to be seen on that type of bike, does the bike look suitable? Does it have facility sometimes, they want to carry things when you might want a basket or something outside of shopping basket as possible? “It is a bike issue, our bikes, you don't have to wear a helmet, it is recommended, but you don't have to have one or so. So, some systems, I think they do have to include a helmet with the bike, and they can just take it off. So, some people might feel that it's better”. (Male, 55-64 UK)

“Obviously, one of the things that is good about most of those bike shares is this, they tend to be stepped through frame, which means it doesn't matter what kind of clothes you're wearing, you can still use them.

And then close chains and that sort of thing. So, the design of the bicycle, I think, is quite important”.
(Male, 55-64 UK)

Themes and Fairness Characteristics

The table below is a summary of the fairness characteristics identified from the responses of the interviewees as well as the barriers.

Main Category	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC
User Barriers	Accessibility & Spontaneity	Proximity to docking stations (walking time) Unavailability of bikes at the stations Lack of empty docking points at the stations to return bike. Cost (High charges after first hour) Location of stations not suitable for suburban trips Entry barriers (download an app, online registration, credit/debit card and familiarity with the system)
	Safety & Security	Lack of maintenance (cleanliness of the bikes) Safety helmet (locked on bikes) Busy roads/vehicular traffic Aggressive driving Traffic safety Convenience Lack of decent and protective cycle infrastructure Isolated infrastructure
	Social Constraints	Limited/Lack of female bikes (bikes with low frame) Lack of child seat and accessories to support trips involving children. Lack of accessories for carrying things and for shopping.

	Weather & Topography	Weather Topography
	Design & Functionality	Seats are too small and too hard/uncomfortable (some seats are not conducive for every person)

Figure 5 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics

Suggested Solutions

Participants raised several concerns and barriers to full participation in the use of bike-sharing services. These identified and perceived barriers particularly, among women have been discussed in the preceding section and table I of this report. This section presents and discusses participants' suggested solutions and requirements to address the barriers discussed above. Similar to the preceding section, the interviewee's suggestions are discussed under the following themes.

Accessibility & Spontaneity

Participant's needs and expectation to address the barriers to accessibility of bike-sharing services centres on the following critical issues include the siting station in close proximity to users, increasing the number of docking points and bikes at each station, reducing the distance between stations, increase the quality and safety of the infrastructure such as paths stations etc. One participant suggested the possibility of reserving a bike on the apps for about 15 minutes before getting to the station to avoid the situation where the app indicates the availability of a bike, but one walks to an empty station.

"If you can acquire a bike before you get to the location, you might leave your house having at the back of mind that you are going to get a bike but before you get there, the bike. ... They should be able to hold it for about 10 minutes and if you are not there to claim it, it is gone." (Female, 35-44, UK)

"But if you're looking to have a cycle, a hirer points near your home, and one near your school or nursery, and one near your shops, then that doesn't necessarily exist in more rural areas, or in the outskirts of the cities or towns, they tend to be concentrated more in city centre, with some outliers". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"I think there are lots and lots of things that might be relevant, but the infrastructure is such a big thing that it overshadows everything else. Nothing will happen until we have the infrastructure, we will never get the increase in cycling that we need." (Male, 55-64 UK)

"So, think it should be no close for everyone it should be reachable, so they need to check these bikes are place the distances should considered." (Female, 25-34 UK)

Safety & Security

Participants were of the opinion that the designs of the bikes and most importantly the safe and protected infrastructure could eliminate most of the safety and security concerns of users and increase the use of the services more in future. If we can get the right infrastructure (safe,

segregated and protected) then perhaps women can cycle without helmets as seen in the Netherlands. Some participant's views are presented below.

"In terms of cycling with children, you don't want to be going on roads at all, or you may only want to be going on very quiet roads depending on the skill level of the child that you're cycling with". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"So having routes that are well lit, protected, comfortable, direct, all the sort of standard things that we want out of cycle infrastructure. I think those are the things that would enable women to cycle as well as men. "women sometimes are more concerned about things like their hair being affected when they wear a helmet, that sort of thing. ... In the Netherlands, you never see people in helmets, and they have the best safety record in the world. So those issues are sort of linked to this lack of infrastructure thing". Male, 55-64 UK)

"It is a bike issue, our bikes, you don't have to, wear a helmet, it is recommended, but you don't have to have one or so. So, some systems, I think they do have to include a helmet with the bike." (Male, 55-64 UK)

Social Constraint

Participants believe that the provision of child seat and accessories to support trips involving children and carrying goods is essential in ensuring the inclusivity of the bike-sharing services. Interviewees also underscore the importance of safe infrastructure and continuity in the cycle paths in promoting cycling among women. One participant was of the view that enabling cycling with children has the added advantage of introducing the children to cycling at younger age. Another participant suggested the provision of broader bicycle seats (plus size bike seat) to cater for plus-sized users.

"At the moment, they're really aimed at people just doing an A to B journey without any additional baggage or children to be responsible for. In terms of cycling with children, you don't want to be going on roads at all, or you may only want to be going on very quiet roads depending on the skill level of the child that you're cycling with". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"To provide them carry bags or carriage because most women would like to go shopping or for those that have kids if you want to ride now and maybe just take your kids to a shopping mall or maybe take your kids to the park". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"I think people need to see more other people doing this riding bicycles, in normal clothes without lycra, or helmets, or all of these other things. In just the same way that they would walk somewhere, or even go in the car. And the more that that is seen, then, the more it will be normalized. And people will see that is something that they could do as well." "Women sometimes are more concerned about things like their hair being affected when they wear a helmet, that sort of thing, ..., in the Netherlands, you never see people in helmets, and they have the best safety record in the world. So, you know, those issues are sort of linked to this lack of infrastructure". (Male, 35-44 UK)

"Women are doing more of the childcare and much more of the childcare than men so taking children to school, if we could enable children to be taken to school, using bicycles, and walking and scooting and so on, without fear of traffic, then that would make a huge difference. And that difference would affect women more than men because just because of the way the society is set up. I think that is number one. It also

has the advantage, of course, that it introduces people to active travel at a young age. And that's the key to getting the change that we need". (Male, 55-64 UK)

"In term of social cultural constraints, I think people should be more enlightened, that it is a good way of exercising and for general wellbeing". (Female, 25-34 UK)

Weather & Topography

The provision of electric bikes was generally suggested as a necessity in addressing the issue of terrain. Participants' opinions are presented below.

"So, I think with those, it's about the main set, I suppose typography to a certain extent can be dealt with through electric bikes, which obviously makes it much easier to cycle through challenging terrain and hilly places". (Female, 35-64 UK)

"With the terrain, I think that is where the electric bike comes in. When you are approaching a hill, you actually use the electric bike to go further". (Female, 35-64 UK)

"The electric bike is certainly, the effort under pedal and get all hot and sweaty, is taken out. So, we would have thought that would help female use of the scheme". (Male, 55-64 UK)

"Probably a significant percentage of the bicycles I see now, maybe approaching 50% actually have electric assist. So, hills just cease to be an issue if you've got electrical assist." (Male, 55-64 UK)

Design & Functionality

The design of bikes in terms of size, height, aesthetics and functionality is suggested to have influence on the decision to cycle. Interviewees suggested the design of lightweight and universal bikes (unisex design: low frame bikes) will ensure bikes are convenient for all sexes, particularly women users. A number of improvements were suggested to improve the design and functionality of the bikes.

- Design of bikes (size, height, baskets, aesthetics etc.)
- Larger and comfortable seats for women
- Low frame bikes for women especially women in skirt
- Bikes with covered chain
- Locks on bikes for multi-stop trips for shopping etc.
- Install alarm and GPS on bikes.

"In terms of the seats: I think everybody should feel more comfortable by having a bigger seat. So just make all of them bigger is better". (Female, 35-44 UK)

"I would recommend there should be more of female bikes. Female bikes are those ones whose seat is well bigger ... for example, the female seats are more comfortable than the narrower seats. (Female, 25-34 UK)

“Well, it's difficult for me to answer that, because I'm not a woman. So, I don't have obviously, one of the things that is good about most of those bike shares is this, they tend to be stepped through frame, which means it doesn't matter what kind of clothes you're wearing, you can still use them. And then close chains and that sort of thing. So, the design of the bicycle I think it is quite important”. (Male, 55-64 UK)

“Also imagine, the looks of the bikes as well, there are a lot of people who are happy with the aesthetics, they will be happy to be seen on that type of bike, does the bike look suitable? Does it have facility sometimes, they want to carry things when you might want a basket or something outside of shopping basket as possible?” (Male, 55-64 UK)

Themes and Fairness Characteristics

The table below is a summary of the fairness characteristics identified from the responses of the interviewees as well as the needs to address the barriers.

Main Category	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC
User Needs	Accessibility & Spontaneity	Easy access: proximity of stations More bikes and location Ability to secure a bike before getting to the station (15 minutes reserve time) Price more affordable. Map of local path and infrastructure for cyclist More female bikes (low frame bikes)
	Safety & Security	Security of bikes and users (Alarm, GPS) Safe infrastructure (off-road paths and clearly indicated on-road lanes) Provision of helmet
	Social Constraints	Sensitization campaigns and education on cycling Carry baskets or carriage for shoppers. Child seat

	Weather & Topography	E-bikes for hilly terrain
	Design & Functionality	<p>Design of bikes (size, height, baskets, aesthetics etc.)</p> <p>Larger and comfortable seats for women</p> <p>Low frame bikes for women especially women in skirt</p> <p>Covered bike chain.</p> <p>Locks on bikes when you stop for shopping etc.</p> <p>Install alarm and GPS on bikes.</p>

Figure 6 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics

Annex 7 Use Case III France Interviews

Sample characteristics

Six participants took part in the interview aged between 25 and 54. The majority of the interviewees were female (83.3%), 50.0% of participants were aged between 25-34 and White (71.4%). 66.7% of the participants cycle to work and cycle between 30 and 35 minutes to work. 83.3 % of them are in fulltime employment. 33.3% of the participants reported living with and travelling with dependents under five years.

Choice of Bike-share.

In general, all the interviewees have used bike-sharing services before. The interview context meant that interviewees explained the reasons they cycle and how they benefit from cycling. The reason for the choice of shared bikes is demonstrated to be centered on the perception of “freedom”, “comfort” and satisfaction. Various aspects of bike-sharing such as cost of hiring, travel time and freedom from the responsibility of storage, maintenance and possible bike theft. Interviewees indicated that shared bikes are convenient because they are less restrictive, quicker and could be safer than walking and using the metro.

“I try to travel by bike as often as possible, using a vélib because I don’t have my own bike. I use it to go to work every day. Vélib offers huge freedom. It’s great. For me, it means being rid of all restrictions. ... But overall, I feel better on a bike than on foot or on the metro”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“It’s really a mode of transport that brings lots of joy, the feeling of being free when you cycle. ... I think the thing that is good about Vélib, is that I’m not scared of getting my bike stolen”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“And I remember the freedom when I finally took the plunge. And seeing Paris from another perspective. Seeing the city in the open air... whereas on the metro you don’t see anything... And cycling has made me walk more, it’s made me want to be outside. Bike theft is another benefit of Vélib”. (Female, 45-54, France)

“I cycle on a daily basis... I loved cycling, cutting down my journey times, and it’s also really nice. I started using it for transport on a daily basis. It’s a mode of transport I really like and which does me good. It put me in a good mood, like a good dose of oxygen, before getting to work in the morning”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“A friend of mine tells me and I think the same, “riding is safer than walking and taking the metro”. Because people more difficult for people to touch or stop you”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Aside from the reported freedom and convenience of using bike-sharing services to meet their mobility need, Participants also identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services and to increasing the use of the services, particularly among women. While some of the barriers cited centered on bikes availability, infrastructural limitations, lack of appropriate equipment and safety, several suggestions were also made to address the barriers. The section below presents the perceived barriers and mitigation measures.

Barriers to Bike-sharing Accessibility

The availability of bikes at the stations when needed, the location of the stations, the distance to the nearest station, and the type and quality of the cycle paths available are some of the issues users have to take into consideration when planning a trip involving bike-sharing. All interviewees had concerns about the availability of bikes at the stations and the condition of the available bikes if any. Interviewees enjoyed cycling and feel liberated using bike-sharing services. However, there was an indication that participants viewed some services as unreliable and not dependable for meeting mobility needs in an urgent and emergency situation; in terms of securing a bike and getting an empty dock when returning a bike at the end of the trip. For instance.

“The real problem is the lack of available bikes. If you’re up high (like in the east and north of Paris), there aren’t any. The stations are either empty or there aren’t enough of them”. (Female, 35-44, France)

“But the other thing that is very important in terms of inclusivity is where you place your station and where the service can go”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“My biggest problem is availability, and whether they are usable. If the bike’s got a flat or when you take it, the gears skip, or the breaks don’t work... It’s a handy service but I don’t really trust it. I always leave pretty early so I have the metro as a back-up option for arriving on time”. (Female, 45-54, France)

In some instances, users had concerns about the lack of stations in their neighbourhood, others reported travelling further from their trip destination to return a bike after their trip because the station at their destination did not have an empty dock to return the bike.

“But the other thing that is very important in terms of inclusivity is where you place your station and where the service can go”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“Yesterday, I had to go to 4 stations to find space to return the bike. And I found one pretty far away, for getting home it’s a real problem”. (Male, 35-44, France)

The language used by interviewees to describe their experience and perception of bike-sharing services show some level of frustration and dissatisfaction with bike-sharing services, basing their views on knowledge and understanding of specific services. The following statement reflects the sentiment of some users.

“Sometimes I get really stressed. When going a long way, I couldn’t find a bike, and sometimes I had to change bikes 5 times, because they weren’t any good ... Sometimes I have to go to three stations to find an electric bike that’s charged”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“For example, sometimes I go out with my helmet, but then I can’t find a Vélib and I end up carrying my helmet around all day”. (Female, 35-44, France)

Some participants said they were unwilling to use bike-sharing services to meet their mobility needs, especially for attending important appointment, because they could not guarantee to get to work or arrive for an appointment on time due the uncertainty of getting a bike for a trip. The

perceived 'unreliability' of bike shares led one participant deciding not to use the services for important trips.

"I never use Vélib when I have an appointment. ... I often have to go around 3 or 4 stations before finding one, otherwise I take the metro". (Female, 45-54, France)

Safety and security

Some participants expressed several safety concerns, particularly traffic safety, harassment, inadequate lighting at the stations and the perception of safety at quieter stations and stations with insufficient lighting. Users expressed concerns about the behaviour of drivers and aggressive behaviour of other road users. Women were more likely to feel harassed or experience a frightening situation when cycling.

"My main concern is my safety. Most of the time especially in Paris, it is still dangerous. Because cars don't really care about you, everybody is in hurry". (Female, 25-34, France)

"I don't have any problems on a bike, except road users being aggressive with each other. ... you get called a "bitch". (Female, 25-34, France)

"At the start, I didn't go home too late by bike, but it was more about safety (on the road), due to the lack of lighting". (Female, 25-34, France)

"And when someone is in a car, they don't always see the vélibs at night. Not visible enough at night. ... I've seen incidents of harassment". (Male, 35-44, France)

Social Constraint

Societal and cultural constraints as well as women responsibility and travel patterns and purposes play a significant role in the choice of transport. Some participants argued that the absence and/or size of the carry baskets are of particular importance for shopping trips and for travellers with luggage who wishes to use bike-share services.

Additionally, users with children and who wish to cycle with them considers the absence of child seat and the inadequacy or discontinuity of the cycle infrastructure. These raise safety concern for users with dependants who sees the infrastructure unsafe for cycling with kids.

Women fashion and concerns about appearance. For instance, wearing of skirts, high heeled shoes and carrying handbags limits their ability to cycle as women cannot cycle in high heels.

"But my concern is about riding comfortably and safely but most of the time, women outfit doesn't go with that. ... the thing with outfit is that you need to carry it all the time. So, you cannot have a very small purse, just like some women have. Because you need to carry your helmet you need to carry your other shoes, etc." (Female, 25-34, France)

"The baskets aren't always particularly practical for bags, particularly for women, there's not enough space and there's also a risk of theft". (Female, 25-34, France)

“It’s not possible to take kids on a vélib (designed for single-person use). And the infrastructure isn’t safe enough to take kids, there’s not enough continuity between cycle paths. If there were baby seats on vélibs, I don’t know, but as soon as I bought my bike, I really wanted a seat for my daughter for getting around on the weekend!” (Female, 25-34, France)

Weather and Topography

Weather and the topography of the terrain has been indicated as a major barrier to cycling and bike-share for users. Barring bad weather, some participants will always cycle or use bike-sharing services to meet their mobility needs.

“If it’s not raining, I try to travel by bike as often as possible”. (Female, 25-34, France)

The local topography of the terrain also poses a challenge to the use of bike-sharing services and to cycling in general. Some participants indicated they use electric bikes to overcome this discussed barrier, however, the scarcity of electric bikes limit the users in such instances. It was also noted that available electric bikes at the stations in most instances are either not charged or partially charged and do not have enough battery power to complete a trip.

“Living at the top of a hill in Paris, it’s difficult to get down, there are little or no bikes. In the centre, there are lots of stations, but there’s not much on the hill. To go back up I try to use a charged electric bike. But they’re fairly rare. So sometimes I start with a basic bike, then take an electric bike when I find one. Sometimes I have to go to three stations to find an electric bike that is charged”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“I don’t take the electric vélibs, because the biggest risk is that it won’t work!” (Female, 45-54, France)

Design & Functionality

The design of the bikes, equipment and facilities are argued to pose some level of challenge to users, particularly women. The size and design of the bike could be a significant barrier to women wishing to cycle. One participant suggested that the size and structure of the bikes are important indicators for inclusivity. The width of the bikes lanes similarly cited as barriers by some interviewees.

“It’s also because the cycle paths aren’t practical because you can’t overtake. So, people get angry. If someone is going a bit slowly, especially a woman, they can create a traffic jam”. (Female, 45-54, France)

“The bikes are a bit heavy; they might be a bit easier to use if they were improved.” (Male, 35-44, France)

“So, when we talk about women, of course, and we talk about bikes, the design of the bike itself is very important ... you need to have a low structure, it has to fit any size, because sometimes women are smaller. So, it needs to fit any size. And this also, in terms of inclusivity also include people of small sizes, but also children”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Themes and Fairness Characteristics

The table below is a summary of the fairness characteristics identified from the responses of the interviewees as well as the barriers.

Main Category	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC
User Barriers	Accessibility & Spontaneity	<p>Shortage of bikes at that station when needed.</p> <p>Unavailability of a vacant dock at the stations for those returning bikes.</p> <p>Lack of continuity of bicycle paths</p> <p>Distance to docking stations.</p> <p>Density of stations</p> <p>Distance between stations</p> <p>Insufficient infrastructure</p>
	Safety & Security	<p>Rudeness and dangerous behaviour of other road users</p> <p>Aggressive driver and road user behaviour</p> <p>Harassment</p> <p>Visibility at stations (Darkness at some station)</p> <p>Quite stations at night</p> <p>Poor maintained bikes (Damaged bikes)</p> <p>Absence of hand sanitiser at docking stations</p>
	Social Constraints	<p>Lack of changing facilities for sweaty riders</p> <p>Design of bikes (skirt wearers)</p> <p>Inability to travel with children (lack of child seat)</p> <p>Inability to travel in a group (insufficient bikes at the station)</p>
	Weather & Topography	Hilly Terrain
	Design & Functionality	<p>Heavy Bikes</p> <p>Small baskets for riders with luggage</p>

		Lack of child seat
--	--	--------------------

Figure 7 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics

Suggested Solutions

This report has identified a wide range of perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services and to increasing the use of the services, particularly among women. This section of findings discusses participants' suggested solutions to the barriers discussed above.

Accessibility

Participants suggested solution to addressing their concerns and challenges, mainly focusing on the accessibility of bike-sharing services centred on the following critical issues, including the number of bikes at each station, the distance between stations, increase of cycle infrastructure such as paths etc. One interviewee sees the challenges as having substantial inequalities implication. Another percipient suggested the possibility of a user renting and unlocking more than one bike at the station for trips involving family and friends if he/she is the only account holder.

“Work on geography and the number of bikes at each station. How do they decide how many bikes to have in each station, and how many stations in each area? It creates some serious inequalities! Stations could be closer together for places women use the most”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“The increased number of cycle paths is really reassuring for that. Now I don't feel unsafe at all with my lights. Everything is fine on the route I take”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“And sees the increase in cycle paths as a good thing! ... There need to be more nearby and more stations in these areas”. (Female, 35-44, France)

“Allow one user to unlock several bikes, at this stage, one phone and one accounts for one bike ... maybe not all your children have accounts, it will be nice that you can say I want to two bikes, four bikes, etc, and rent bikes for your children or family”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Safety & Security

Participants who are interested in using the services are of the opinion that the implementation of the following measures could mitigate the safety and security concerns of users and increase the use of the services more in future.

- Installation of side mirrors on bikes
- Provision of a helmet with bikes
- Improve the visibility at stations (improve lighting)
- The installation of emergency help button at stations
- The development of road user code of conduct to deter aggressive road user behaviour.
- Visibility of bikes (High visibility bikes)
- Building safe infrastructure and bike lanes

“In terms of security is just all about the infrastructure, building safe bike lanes, that is the most important thing”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“It would be good to have helmets available alongside the bikes. “For example, at each station, in dark streets, lighting that makes the area less creepy. And why not an emergency help button!” (Female, 35-44, France)

“The stations are really, really, really, really dark. Better lighting for these spaces”. (Male, 35-44, France)

“At some bus stops, there is hydroalcoholic gel; it would be good to have that at Vélib stations during Covid”. (Male, 35-44, France)

Social Constraint

Participants believed that the provision of good-sized carry baskets will help users wishing to use the services to meet their mobility needs for shopping trips and users with luggage. Interviewees also suggest the development of the cycle infrastructure to ensure the continuity of the cycle paths.

Again, several participants called for the supply of child seat at the stations for users with children who may wish to use the services with their children. One participant suggested the provision of a locker with a self-service detachable child seat at the stations for interested users to access when required. Another participant suggested the provision of broader bicycle seats (plus size bike seat) to cater for plus-sized users.

“Having a locker with self-service seats that can be attached. You could try automatic lockers ... That would be cool because you’d have the choice!” (Female, 35-44, France)

“And maybe we could have accessories that you could rent, maybe not on all the bikes, but some bike stations could have accessories, like a baby seat. ... if we think about that, we could also include cargo bikes. In cargo bike, you can place children but also packs and luggage etc. This would also increase the inclusivity and attract more people to replace all the modes by bike-share”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Weather & Topography

The provision of electric bikes was generally perceived as a necessity in addressing the issue of terrain and encouraging more women and older people to cycle. However, it is noted from the interviewees’ submissions that the charging of the bikes is as important as the supply of the e-bikes.

“And the third thing and that's we are convinced that electric bikes and electric shared bikes are one of the main way to include more women in the cycle schemes than before”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Design of bikes

The interviewee, therefore, suggested lightweight and universal bike designs (unisex design: low frame bikes) to ensure bikes are convenient for all sexes, particularly women users. Wider bicycle lanes and paths are also recommended to allow for overtaking and prevent congestion on the cycle lanes. In support of inexperienced riders, participants suggested a number of improvements

to the design and functionality of the bikes which, focused on improvements to weight, design, safety and comfort:

Installation of side mirrors and indicators on the bikes to increase the confidence and comfort of riders.

- The provision of a detachable helmet for users: instead of users having to carry their helmet around.
- The installation of a self-service locker at the stations with a detachable child seat for interested users.

“The bikes are a bit heavy; they might be a bit easier to use if they were improved”. (Male, 35-44, France)

“ So, I chose a bike with a low frame to make getting onto the bike easier and also for the baby seat so I can keep my balance. People often suggest this type of bike to women”. (Female, 25-34, France)

“There need to be wider cycle lanes to avoid traffic jams. “If bikes need to use pavements, it’s bad for pedestrians. Talks about the issue of theft, wouldn’t mind if the helmet was attached to the Vélib by a cord. “For example, sometimes I go out with my helmet, but then I can’t find a Vélib, and I end up carrying my helmet around all day”. (Female, 35-44, France)

“It would be good to have a wing-mirror or indicator on the bikes; you need to be very confident to stick your arm out when turning in terms of how comfortable you feel on a bike”. (Female, 25-34, France)

Themes and Fairness Characteristics

The table below is a summary of the fairness characteristics identified from the responses of the interviewees as well as the needs to address the barriers.

Main Category	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC
User Needs	Accessibility & Spontaneity	Bikes available all the time for those who need it. Availability of vacant docking stations at all the time for those returning bikes. Increase bicycle lanes and paths. Wider bicycle paths Cycling training school Need for comprehensive cycle routes and maps.
	Safety & Security	Visibility at the stations (lighting) Emergency button at stations

		<p>Helmet supply with bikes</p> <p>Safety on Roads</p> <p>Visibility of bikes</p> <p>Drivers and other road users looking out for and paying attention to cyclists.</p> <p>Deterring aggressive behaviour</p> <p>Driver and road user code of behaviour</p> <p>Improvement of car user behaviour towards cyclist methods</p> <p>Hand sanitiser at docking stations</p> <p>Building safe infrastructure and bike lanes</p>
	Social Constraints	<p>Changing facilities</p> <p>Child seats</p> <p>Large baskets</p> <p>Public sensitisation</p> <p>Introduce cycling training and education in schools.</p>
	Weather & Topography	<p>Electric bikes</p>
	Design & Functionality	<p>Lighter Bikes</p> <p>Unisex bike design</p> <p>A locker with a self-service child seat that can be attached at stations.</p> <p>Side mirrors</p>

Figure 8 Use Case III Fairness Characteristics France

Annex 8 Use Case IV Question 3 Interviews

The research questions relating to Use Case IV are as follows.

- How different job characteristic, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

The following section will therefore set out a summary of the data analysis employed on the interview and focus group data collected from Spain, Ireland, Poland, Scotland and the UK for Use Case IV based on the two research questions above.

In total there were 46 participants who took part in the interview/focus group data collection.

- 4 participants were HR personnel.
- 15 participants from Poland
- 5 participants from Spain
- 22 participants from UK/Ireland/Scotland

To protect the anonymity of the participants who took part in the project, when direct quotations are used participants have been identified by their allocated pseudonym, their sex (F for female M for male), their job title and their country of origin to provide an intersectional focus, e.g., Fiona F Bus Driver Poland.

- **Research Question: How different job characteristics and/or contextual factors in the transport sector may affect gender balance and/or female employability in different areas.**

The following section will set out the analysis in response to Research Question 3.

Socio Economic Conditions - Job segregation

Analysis of the research data suggests that job segregation has an impact on gender balance and female employability in the transport industry. According to some interviewees this job segregation is based upon traditional or historical ideas of ‘men’s jobs’ and ‘women’s jobs’. The dominance of male employees was apparent across sectors and locations. Respondents noted majority female employment in HR, finance, marketing and clerical work, but indicated that women were less likely than men to be employed in front line jobs, such as driving, and engineering or IT jobs. The male dominance of the industry and lack of gender diversity is highlighted by these respondents:

“We are a very heavily male driven company; we are a developer driven company so that’s still quite male oriented.” Sarah F Director UK

“I was chair of XX for 5 years and I had an all-male cast.” Crystal F Director UK

“The organisation historically was male dominated; female drivers were unheard of... I feel like over the years the men really dominated the organisation and also because traditionally the engineering role, train driver role, the inspectors, the signalling role, all those railway focused jobs, they were targeted at males predominantly.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“Engineering is traditionally a, and I am making generalisations here, tends to be a more male sector and from my experience, from the survey we ran with women in Rail, that absolutely its dominated by men, I think the percentages are something like 12% women 88% men so there is a lot of work to be done addressing that gender imbalance. That is across the rail sector in all roles.” Sharon F Manager UK

“...we do need to be more diverse, you know, in every aspect because it's as an organisation we are not very diverse at all, especially in engineering. I mean just to give you, you know, an estimate, we've got over 600 engineers working in the engineering department and only four are female” Samantha F Director UK

“The condition of gender is not a requirement in any job. Calls for employment are open to everyone, regardless of gender. Everyone is trained to do the same kind of work. They say that the regulations guarantee full equality between the two genders, but in reality, in the engineering department they are all men.” Billy M Ticket Inspector Spain

“I first came in through finance, and when I came into IT at first, I was the only female there. When I left the IT department there were no more females in the entire department, there are 12 people there... I cannot believe that there are no females suitable for a job there.” Tina F Manager Ireland

These last two statements also point out that gender should not be a requirement for jobs in the industry. Despite almost majority agreement that job segregation was apparent in their organisation some respondents did point to evidence of progress with regard gender balance and female employability. However, they point out, this change is slow and has not resulted in gender balance in the industry yet. For example:

“[this] is an organisation that has been very parochial for a long time and we're only starting to turn a corner in terms of, you know present day thinking, more open to change. Shaun M Manager Ireland

“There have never been any impediments for women to work in the Railways, they have always had the opportunity to work in all jobs. It is true that there were no women who applied for these jobs. Over time, there has been a change in the roles of society, and little by little women have been incorporated into a multitude of positions in XX. As far as female train drivers are concerned, the first female train driver started in 1990 and now there are still only about twenty female drivers.” Matias M Spain

“Women are still in the minority, absolutely in the minority within rail as a sector. Crystal F Director UK

While there was evidence of the lack of women in ‘traditionally male roles’ in the industry respondents drew attention to the concentration of women in other occupations:

“Other areas, I mean head office, you know you've got females there in commercial and marketing roles and finance, in finance I've seen a lot of um recruitment focused on females. But you know the core ScotRail operations is, you know the operation side, which is your drivers and your engineering team which is still unfortunately the figures are quite low.” Samantha F Director UK

As this female rail employee pointed out:

“[in my station] there is one female train driver and there are about 60 drivers in total. There are no female... driver manager, there are 3 station managers one is female, there is a district manager who is a man, there is one female station controller [out of a total of 8]. So, the majority of the female staff either work in the booking office or in some clerical capacity behind scenes.”

Irene F Manager Ireland

I think initially engineering was seen very much as a male dominated thing to do it's like traditionally, they always say HR directors are always women, customer experience directors are always women, that is so true. I am in a meeting they say to me do you need anything to take notes. They presume I am secretarial support. They have done that all of my career. One man said, 'how can a wee girl like you be running this?' ... I think that is something that we need to change in the rail industry, it needs to be the right person for the job rather than gender.” Crystal F Director UK

Furthermore, respondents provided evidence of not only role segregation according to gender but also hierarchical segregation, with the presence of 'a glass ceiling' and a lack of women in senior roles within their organisations.

“...talking to the women within the women and mobility group, for example, there are still barriers, there is still a glass ceiling and the higher we look up the management chain the fewer women are present”.
Sarah F Director UK

“...as for the topic of women in top management, I just checked and there are no women on the management board any longer.” Arek M Tram Operator Poland

This lack of women in senior roles is problematic as respondents noted that women in senior roles, and more diverse roles, need to be more visible to make these positions seem more accessible to women:

“I think there are still some professions where women think 'I wouldn't be able to do that'. And when they suddenly see someone in a job ad and they see a woman doing it it's a bit, what's that saying, you can't be what you can't see. We need to see a lot more women in a lot more diverse roles and look at them and think 'oh I can relate to that, maybe I could do that too, that looks like fun or interesting or challenging'.” Sarah F Director UK

“...it's always sort of hard when you're in a workplace where you know there's no other females and you know you just sometimes feel that, so how am I going to develop my career? How am I going to? There's nobody to look up to, so you know, you, you just don't, you just don't have that feeling of belonging that you that you belong there.” Samantha F Director UK

However, a few respondents pointed out that there are females in senior positions in their organisation and welcomed the fact that they are supportive and encouraging. There was also evidence of male managers who were equally supportive and encouraging. Interviewees also pointed to the value of mentoring and suggested this was commonly used in many organisations to support women. Although the majority of these mentors are women there were reports of male mentors, in part due to there not being women in more senior roles. In addition, practices

such as ‘women in transport days’, specific women in transport groups and educational events were cited as examples of support received that positively impact upon women employees and a more equal gender balance in the industry.

“I think it is a responsibility of us all that have had successful careers as women to coach, to mentor to bring women along with us... I have got their back and I am saying, well I will rock the boat for you. I am in that position where I am able to do that... I respect the people who came before me and cleared the way for me, I can only do the same for them.” Naomi F Director UK

A few respondents discussed the efforts in place to address the lack of gender balance in the sector with regard job segregation, such as member organisations and advertising:

“When the media don’t portray the sector well, when you have people working who are “pale, male, stale” middle to old age, how attractive is that? When I first started, I only knew one other woman who was a transport manager and now we have groups like Women n Transport who are trying to promote women ...” Louise F Director UK

“I think that in transport we are run by an aging male denomination, but they are not going to last forever. I think when the younger people come through things will change naturally. The younger generation are more aware of fairness, but it’s about time. Our industry has something to do re changing the industry, you know if there are women role models, well put them out there... it’s only really in the last five years that we’ve actually started to advertise externally as well as internally. I think it a very positive step.” Shaun M Manager Ireland

Respondents did note that although there are attempts to change to a more inclusive and more gender balanced workforce, with diversity and inclusion given attention and comments such as the organisation being ‘more open to change’ or adopting ‘present day thinking’, job segregation in the transport sector persists and impacts upon gender balance in roles, across hierarchies, sectors and locations.

Socio-Economic Factors - Demand Factors

With regard demand factors that feature in the FC and their impact upon gender balance and employability in the industry vacancy characteristics and recruitment factors emerged as important. With regard vacancy characteristics, respondents suggested working hours, shift work and opportunities for progression were obstacles to gender balance and female employability. These issues are discussed in detail in other FC subsections. Furthermore, with regard recruitment factors, respondents noted that recruitment and selection procedures, selection preferences, method of recruitment and discrimination all impact upon gender balance and employability Once again, these issues are discussed in detail in other FC subsections.

Socio- Economic Factors - Policy /legal

With regard policy/legal factors that impact on gender balance and female employability the research data underlined that there are policies in place that should in theory promote fairness in the workplace but that in reality they are often viewed as a ‘tick box’ exercise. Also, as this manager points out, policy for fair recruitment may be in place but the work culture may not reflect this:

“... I think you can absolutely create policy around very tangible tasks like recruitment, and I think that's all really important. But it's. . . you recruit people in? But how then do you try and change that habit - shift in that culture where that person is sitting in a boardroom and going “What like what I'm? I'm surrounded by dinosaurs here. What's going on?” Elaine F HR Ireland

Socio-Economic Factors - Female facilities

Another FC important in ensuring gender balance is work conditions and the data highlighted that the presence of appropriate female facilities was often lacking, making work conditions problematic and discriminatory for women. The lack of facilities was deemed to be a result of job segregation in the industry, as this interviewee pointed out:

“I think it was a historical thing, where we are going back to the argument that the rail sector is male dominated and it tended to be, it was quite rare 20 years ago for a female to be out on site, as horrible as that sounds its true...one of the issues is still changing facilities out on site for females, loo facilities for females and it still is an issue in this day and age would you believe it?” Sharon F Manager UK

Not only were toilet facilities inadequate, data revealed that showering facilities, sanitation provision and breast feeding/expressing milk were also problematic for women in certain roles in the industry.

Job Characteristics – Human Relations (HR) Policies – Recruitment, Retention, and Promotion

Recruitment

The research data highlighted that some recruitment practices employed by organisations may not be fair for women, with one interviewee even suggesting some men in her organisation are reluctant to employ women of childbearing age in case they become pregnant and take maternity leave. Overall respondents suggested that the following are common in recruitment methods and practices and that they disadvantage women:

- unconscious bias
- conscious bias
- discrimination
- sexism
- a lack of fairness

The issues, with regard male colleagues in work, are discussed in detail below under FC Negative Attitudes of Male Colleagues. Some interviewees expressed that ‘gender balanced panels’ and ‘unbiased questions’ would increase fairness at the point of recruitment and selection overcoming the above and expressed the desire for current practices to change. Moreover, there were calls for management and directors to understand that women can do jobs traditionally perceived as male, as this statement highlights:

“I think just the initial, the very basic stage of who we interview or who interviews the candidates is not right in my in my head because... I remember being part of the interview panel for the apprentices and I was the first female engineer to be part of that panel, and when I looked at that panel there were three engineers, again all white all male, and the questions that they were asking... the young students who were coming in, it was very much focused on or like you know ‘have you worked on a car?’ or, you know, ‘have you worked in the garage?’ or things which females would probably have difficulty answering.” Samantha F Director UK

Furthermore, one interviewee pointed out that she is exploring whether there is unintended bias against women inherent in the psychometric testing that train drivers undergo as part of the application process. (Naomi F Rail Director UK)

Despite this evidence the data also suggests that some steps are being taken to address current inequality at the point to recruitment and selection, with some organisations featuring female employees in their advertising recruitment campaigns and attempting to make their recruitment strategy gender neutral and unbiased to aid inclusion. Examples were noted of advertisements featuring female train drivers and tram drivers and one advert featuring two women job sharing a director level job in a company, to promote awareness of these opportunities for women. Interviewees highlighted these inclusive practices in their organisations:

“Recruitment campaigns are neutral, no gender-specific profiles are sought.” Billy M Rail Ticket Inspector Spain

“I mean in my experience, when I have seen job adverts, or I have been made aware of jobs or my colleagues applying for them I just feel that the process has always been very fair, very transparent, there’s never been any language that would discriminate against a male or a female, be it a part time worker, shared hours, that sort of thing... it’s very inclusive.” Lisa F Manager Ireland

“There are also advertising spots in the trams. Women are shown driving trams in these spots.” Teodor M Tram Driver Poland

“...sometimes a female image is helpful, it helps young females think ‘I never even thought I could be a train driver, that has never even occurred to me’. It’s almost stereotypical. It’s ingrained, like pink for a girl and blue for a boy, I mean why is that?” Frances F Director UK

“There is a lot of work ongoing just now in terms of sort of inclusion and making sure we are doing all the right things in terms of ethnic minorities women all that stuff to try and make sure that ads are worded accordingly so that you know there is no gender bias or any other kind of bias in the adverts... so if you are advertising for an engineer for instance, which is traditionally a male dominated industry, you want the visuals to have females and minority groups present.” Christine F Director UK

Moreover, in some cases, gender neutral adverts were created by removing ‘masculine’ language or by placing these adverts on platforms considered by the organisation to be more accessible to women, for example women’s magazines and an online forum. This rail director described strategies in her organisation to overcome unconscious bias and to produce adverts that are gender neutral:

“... all the speakers at the graduate program, every time they were referring to employees kept referring to them in the male sense. So, when the managers would speak, they were speaking about him, he, it was all he. So, the vernacular is still very much male. So, what we tried to do was just before the drive and interviews and the apprentice interviews we ran an unconscious bias training to try and make people aware of their biases and to be really watching out for them. And we also had the gender decoder for the ads... to run the gender decoder to make sure to make the language more feminine... the decoder will scan your ad and it will come out, it's predominantly masculine, it's predominantly female and it will highlight all the words that are masculine or feminine, or it will come back and say your ad is neutral.” Lorna F Director Ireland

Another strategy used by many of the organisations to promote gender balance and increase female employability involved attending schools, colleges, universities, and job fayres. This tactic is based around education and awareness, with many respondents suggesting that more education and communication regarding roles within the transport sector and their suitability for women is important to increase the numbers of women in the industry. For example:

“...for engineering, I think we need to go to the to the source. So, schools and colleges so that we get the fresh talent.” Samantha F Director UK

“We do visit local schools; we go to tell them about our services and such and we also go into one school to judge their engineering competitions, but I am not sure we ever go in to sell the company as an employer. We do have work experience pupils come in every year, they are in the office and in the workshop.” Justine F Manager UK

“We do stuff with schools and colleges, not as much as I would like us to do. Actually, our employees tend to be the best ambassadors for that. We do send them out and we send our existing apprentices back to schools to say, ‘this is what it is like for us’.” Naomi F Director UK

“We do loads of things, first of all we get very involved in local schools at a young age we go in and talk about the rail sector as a whole and we go in and talk about the opportunities that are available. Somebody goes into a school, say primary 6-7 [age 10-11] and run a session all about the rail sector and what we do, what the roles are out on site and what the roles are in the office. So that is one of the ways, we start off quite young quite early with young people for them to consider a career in rail and what the options are.” Sharon F Manager UK

The success of this initiative is described below:

“We get lots of feedback from teachers in particular, asking for repeat days or more information or individuals asking if they can come, I think there was some primary 7 [age 11] pupils came in, I think they may have had parents working with us and they came in and did a day at work with mum or dad, so they could see, that was done via the links with schools and there was definitely follow ups, and it was seen very positively.” Sharon F Manager UK

It was noted by a few respondents that this education is essential because many women may not understand the nature of or requirements of work in the sector and believe they are not capable of the physical demands of certain roles. For example:

“They [women] are not aware at all, it’s not all just about dirty truck driving, the trucks now are really like, they are all IT, they have telematics and electronics. Our industry really needs to be pushing women forwards. The trade bodies should also be putting women forward, they are trying but it needs more than a picture of a woman in a high viz and hard hat. Women cannot do this by ourselves we need the help of men; men need to understand the importance of females in the workplace.” Louise F Director UK

“I think most women also don’t think they are strong enough for these roles... To be honest it’s a technique thing, so again that would be engagement and communication. I have asked my company to make a video. I know a female driver who is about a size 8 and can couple 10 trains in half the time it takes a man, make a video of her doing it and women looking in can see it.” Hannah F Driver UK

However, this strategy is not seen as a quick fix, several interviewees noted that the impact of such initiatives will take time, and that access to schools can be problematic:

“... well to attract women actually, you need to go right into schools... And when you go into schools they don’t really know about transport, they don’t, they don’t know about they don’t even think about how goods get from A to B and that includes the teachers. So, when you go into schools now, it’s getting down to that level and it’s going to take quite a time for it to come.” Louise F Director UK

“It’s getting access to the schools, finding ways to get access into schools you know to get people like me in to talk to them and unless it’s facilitated in some way a lot of schools won’t get it. The schools use a known contact as its easier they don’t have the time to go looking for people so there needs to be a better way to get engagement with the school.” Frances F Director UK

Moreover, despite positive outcomes reported from utilising these strategies one respondent noted that:

“We have attended job fairs at schools and colleagues, and I made sure that our promotion material had plenty pictures of women working on buses, but we have never received any engagement from girls at all at these things. Generally, the girls showed no interest at all.” Nancy F Bus HR Supervisor UK

Most organisations, across sectors and location, suggested they do not specifically target women for employment opportunities, suggesting this could be considered discriminatory and stating they want the best person for the job, regardless of gender, and that competition for jobs should be fair. Organisations had strategies such as targets for diversity, rather than quotas, and equality plans to increase numbers of women employees.

Respondents pointed to the need to encourage more inclusive behaviours across the transport sector generally. Although, as stated, there were no calls for positive discrimination, they suggested that positive steps towards fairness in the sector can be achieved by:

- Providing ‘an even playing field’
- managers ‘not being part of the old boy’s network’.
- attending ‘the latest recruitment training’
- recruiting the ‘right person for the job’

- specifically utilising recruitment campaigns featuring women in traditionally male roles, such as train drivers, to encourage women to apply.

Several interviewees suggested these methods have led to a greater intake of women while also benefitting the business at the same time.

Despite the majority of respondents suggesting that recruitment practices and a cultural shift regarding views of women in the industry are positive and accepted, some pointed to resistance or best practice not always being upheld. For example:

“... I think you can absolutely create policy around very tangible tasks like recruitment, and I think that's all really important. But it's... you recruit people in? But how then do you try and change that habit, shift in that culture, where that person is sitting in a boardroom and going ‘What, like what, I'm surrounded by dinosaurs here. What's going on?’” Elaine F HR Ireland

And, as this manager pointed out, best practice within his company is not always adhered to by all managers making hiring decisions:

“...because like I have done all the latest training and I've seen what's out there but saying it on paper and actually practicing it now are actually different things for different managers. So I mean I would be very much by the book on an awful lot these things, so when I'm running an interview or when I'm advertising a job or when I'm speaking to someone, it's as they should be done, and it is the company bringing the best practice. I know for a fact managers of other locations would not be that way but that's a culture thing and that is slowly changing.” Shaun M Manager Ireland

This culture change may reflect changing demographics and heightened awareness of women working in the industry, as one manager noted:

“I think that in transport we are run by an aging male denomination, but they are not going to last forever. I think when the younger people come through things will change naturally. The younger generation are more aware of fairness, but it's about time. Our industry has something to do regarding changing the industry.” Louise F Director UK

The data suggests that in most of the organisations represented by the respondent's steps are being taken to improve gender balance and female employability at the point of recruitment and selection.

Retention

With regard retention of employees, many respondents commented that their organisation actively seeks to retain all employees, both male and female. The data highlighted three main findings: the importance of equality of access to training; flexible working; and maternity leave terms and conditions. The first of these, training, is addressed in the subsection below [Training]. Flexibility is also addressed below [Flexible Working]. Therefore, the discussion here focusses on maternity leave terms and conditions. In general respondents noted that their organisation offered favourable terms and conditions with regards maternity leave.

“...if we see someone who has potential, we develop a path for them, maternity leave fully supported and can come back part time.” Nancy F HR Supervisor UK

“What we try to do is, we try to be fair with our policies. And what that means is, people returning from maternity leave, we say ‘I see no reason why I cannot find a role for you to do. It might not be what you are doing now, but I am going to guarantee that when you return, we will have a place for you on the pay that you are on now, and that what means is that I can make it more flexible for you, cutting hours, working in a different way.’” Naomi F Director UK

“We have got a phased return, there will be a back to work interview with the operations support manager and they will chat about how they feel about it all, some of them are happy to come back and just go for it, others are looking for a little longer or part time etc.” Caroline F Director UK

“My maternity leave was extremely favourable with fully paid conditions, it’s fairer than some organisations. It was never a doubt that I was ever going to have to take a step back.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“You can go off, you can take your maternity, you can take parental leave there’s absolutely no problem, you can take term time.” Agnes F Manager Ireland

“I think its split now so you can actually decide what way it’s going to be between the couple. Like our HR policies they do tend to stay in line with best practice, legislations etc.” Shaun M Manager Ireland

One interesting and unique finding is outlined below, a strategy to share paternity leave and pay was introduced in this organisation:

“Basically, what happens now is a woman goes off to have a baby, she doesn’t have to be our employee, but at the minute you can share your maternity leave. But a lot of organisations expect you to share it with no money. What we have said in our organisation if you are sharing your partners maternity pay, we are going pay you like a woman, you get full pay for 6 months half pay for three months and statutory for the final three months. So, we treat you as if you are a woman. People are like well that just helps men does it not? Well it does and it doesn’t, what it does is that when you come in for an interview for a job and you sit down as a woman the interviewer isn’t thinking oh she is going to off and I will need to find a replacement for her, now if you are a man they are thinking ‘oh his partner may get pregnant and I am going to have to...’ and suddenly it’s made it a much more even playing field because it doesn’t matter what gender you are.” Naomi F Director UK

As these quotes illustrate there were many examples of best practice, support offered, and options to return part time, if preferred, regarding maternity leave. However, the data collected was limited to the UK and Ireland with very little information gathered from Spain and Poland regarding maternity leave. This should be followed up for consistency.

Promotion

Many respondents reported that there is equal access to promotion in their organisation. Indeed, there was one very positive example of women present across the hierarchy of the organisation:

“All our training and promotion options are open and available to all employees regardless of their gender. As I said my line manager is a woman, her manager is a woman, and our MD is a woman. We had a female MD many, many years ago who started in the cash office of the organisation...” Justine F Bus Manager UK

Yet this example was unique in the data. Despite there being, in theory, equal access to promotion in their organisation gender segregation at promoted levels was apparent across organisations, sectors and locations:

“So, I can see that they are trying, I can see that we do encourage women to apply for jobs and I currently applied for two different roles at the minute, I’d be very surprised if I get one of them. But one of them is a district managers role and there are say seven district managers in XX and one of them is a woman and she’s a lady who’s retiring, so I don’t know who’s going to get the job it would be nice if there was a lady district manager.” Irene F Manager Ireland

“...but when you look at the people who are getting promoted or the people who are in senior management or people of influence, a lot of them are male, pale and stale.” Crystal F Director UK

“What I see more is that the higher up you go the less women you see. So, there’s, I don’t know if there’s still so much an issue going in, but there’s definitely an issue as you go higher up the hierarchy. That’s for sure.” Sarah F Director UK

When asked why there are few women at senior levels respondents suggested men are more likely to achieve promotion. For example:

“You just always feel if you if all you see are sort of, you know white male in the high post and the natural feeling that you get is you know those roles are reserved for them. And again people try and associate a role with a certain sort of personality or whether it be, you know, being a depo manager who has to be assertive and aggressive, or you have to be a white male, really tall, really charismatic, and only then you get a managing director or director's role.” Samantha F Director UK

“When I came in (to the organisation) I had this perception that it was a male dominated organization and that it would have been very difficult for me, I always felt very ambitious, I wanted to grow, and I wanted to progress. I went for promotions and I kind of found myself always surrounded by men because they were the ones that were progressing and moving within the organisation.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“If a man went for a transport managers job and a woman went for a transport managers job, the man would get it 90% of the time. When I passed my CPC, I went for a couple of jobs and I know that there was only a couple of men and myself in for one role, and both times the men got the job... It’s still a male dominated industry, there are still old-fashioned ideas within the industry that it should be male dominated, women are alright to drive but not all right to manage.” Erin F Truck Manager UK

Respondents from Poland did report a few positive examples of promotion for women but ultimately, as in Ireland and the UK, there were few reports of women in senior positions:

“Out of thirty traffic supervision employees there is one woman. And she was also promoted... She is the cherry among this group, but she is well received by her colleagues, and she is doing well... and at the same time, here in our company, it also showed that women are able to work in such positions”. Leon M Transport Coordinator Poland

“I was promoted from a team that was a typical male team. I was the last person to join this team. The guys taught me everything, then I worked with them and later they chose me as their manager... despite the fact that I became manager, they continued to treat me as the colleague I had been. And it’s like that up to now, we work so well and there are no clashes or problems.” Magda F Passenger Information Poland

“Not only in Warsaw, but in urban transport companies in the whole of Poland the management is made up of men. Recently a woman became Managing Director of XX for the first time, but before that, since 1992, there was no woman in this position. Other directors, be it investment or transport directors - are all men. Look at the boards of operators - let’s say XX or XX - I don’t see women there... Sure, women get promoted a lot. Of course, largely thanks to competence. Sometimes, if they are not promoted, they are simply weaker competently... but when it comes to most important managers - be it in XX or other directors in Warsaw, in the Tri-City, in Poznań - they are all men. So perhaps the men in the highest management levels feel that only a man can deal with something like transport. Perhaps these are just my ideas, but I have the impression that, like in other industries, it is a bit of a ‘glass ceiling’.” Maria F Communications Poland

According to the data generated in this study gender imbalance and female employability exists across the transport industry and across locations. HR policies are in place in organisations to promote equality of access to work and within work, yet despite this, recruitment practices and a ‘glass ceiling’ impact women in the industry. However, HR policy to aid retention of women, specifically maternity leave discussed here, is reported positively.

Job Characteristics - Terms and Conditions

The terms and conditions in any job are important to ensure equality and fairness. The research data examined here suggests that working hours and facilities impact upon gender balance and employability for women in the transport industry. As many FCs overlap discussion of the research data in relation to Terms and Conditions can be found elsewhere in this document: Facilities are examined in detail above under FC Female Facilities and working hours are examined below under FC Flexible Working.

Job Characteristics - Flexible Working

Analysis of the data highlighted that flexible working and caring/parenting responsibilities are linked and as such the research data overlaps regarding both areas. Flexible working, specifically with regard caring/parenting responsibilities, is examined in FC Caring/Parenting Responsibilities below. The focus here is on flexible working more generally.

Interestingly when interviewees were asked ‘what would fairness for female employees in transport services look like?’ flexibility was repeatedly mentioned as being key:

“I think more part time opportunities, more flexibility.” Nancy F HR Supervisor Uk

“Facilities, toilets and showers etc. Flexibility and family friendly working hours, they are available but really difficult to get.” Justine F Manager UK

“Facilities, toilets etc. flexible working and family friendly working conditions.” Louise F Truck Director UK

Respondents offered examples of current flexible working practices in their organisation and implications for workers:

“There were people who moved from another carrier to us, precisely because there was this flexibility.” Patryk M Supervisor Spain

“The ease of work-life balance and timetables has contributed to improving the presence of women.” Sofia F Rail Driver Spain

“...what we say to all of our people is that if you are working from home flexibly in that way what we want you to do is don't worry if you have to go and pick the kids up from school, go and pick them up, then you have to do his tea and do some homework, so when he has gone to bed do a couple of hours then. As long as you get the work out, unless there is a deadline, it doesn't matter when you do the work.” Naomi F Director UK

“[The] benefits that you get being a woman in the transport sector, a lot of the perks you get are also family friendly now, there has been support, and COVID has proven what I have said all along, you can actually get more from people if you give them an environment that they want to work in. Giving people flexibility to do their job on a four-day week, for example, is key for me, or just saying to somebody, ‘I really don't care what you are doing on a day but as long as you have done it and done it to the best of your ability’. You could have done it in two hours you can do it in seven hours, but the flexibility for me to be able to work at home and be with my kids is phenomenal because I have not had that for a long, long time.” Crystal F Director UK

However, overwhelmingly the data suggests that flexible working is only available for specific roles, and is mostly available for office-based roles:

“We try to be flexible in working time but with the type of work we do, you know the work content is the work content. If we can get two part time workers that would be fine. But we don't have as many part time opportunities as full time.” Nancy F Bus HR Supervisor UK

“[With regard] flexible working and part time working opportunities, what tends to happen you see is a role that is 35 hours a week and it must be done by shifts and it must be done by one person and that's it.” Frances F Director UK

“Now there is, at the moment anyway, there is working from home options for one day a week or whatever, but I believe that that policy is going to be enhanced and made more available. There's only certain types of roles that can do it, it's generally the office kind of roles, you couldn't really do it if you're a train driver.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“I think I was lucky I started this role part time and its very flexible. I needed the flexibility when I started as my kids were small. They are very flexible here and so long as I do the work required, I can be flexible

in my start and finishing times. I know that probably isn't the case for women drivers etc. it's more difficult when they work shift patterns." Justine F Manager UK

"... in terms of the management team three of the 5 are women, in the office its 50/50 and from the engineering side of it we have no females. In driving we have about 15% women and that is number 1 would like to get up. Engineering particularly. It seems to be the shifts and its dirty work as well... Engineering do day shift, back shift, night shift. Drivers do crazy shifts, they work 2 days of early shifts, 2 days of middle shifts and one late shift a week... That would kill me, I couldn't do it. The old timers who have been there forever want to keep it. The new people are pushing for change. We do have some family friendly working, but you really have to have a good reason to access it as you know our business is shift work." Caroline F Director UK

"... we need flexibility, but it is hard in our industry." Louise F Director UK

The data highlighted that with regard flexibility only certain jobs, mostly office-based jobs, are compatible. Most interviewees pointed out that operational jobs are not compatible with flexibility (as pointed out above). However, there were a couple of exceptions where it was reported that operational jobs could be worked as job share, for example:

"We have also introduced things like flexible working, and we introduced it a long time before COVID came and I am delighted to say that it enabled our business to do something amazing and keep going right from the start of lock down because all of our people were able to do flexible working. But we don't just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers." Naomi F Director UK

And as this director pointed out, 'traditional arrangements' could be altered by 'thinking differently' about flexibility for all roles:

"There is not that thinking outside of the box, well you know that could be done by two people it could be terms time it could be annualized hours, people are not thinking wider and that is why, you know it goes back to the traditional arrangements. I am seeing clients doing a complete U turn now and its whether that will happen with operational jobs. It is happening with office jobs. It's how, you know, maybe could a job be done by one person doing two days and another three days, its thinking differently about things." Frances F Director UK

Job Characteristics - Training Provision

The data revealed several interesting points regarding training provision and gender balance. Firstly, generally there is equality of access to training, across sectors and locations, most usually paid for by employers. And secondly, evidence of a few organisations offering female specific training. With regard equality of access to training the following was reported:

"I would say that yes there is equal access to training". Erin F Manager UK

"All our training and promotion options are open and available to all employees regardless of their gender." Justine F Manager UK

“Another thing that is common and the same for all of us, is that everyone can obtain qualifications for every type of vehicle. There are no restrictions.” Arek M Tram Operator Poland

“...even though we don't have many female engineers, you know, we still provide equal opportunities for everybody for, you know, developing themselves. So, we offer training for pretty much for everybody who is part of engineering.” Samantha F Director UK

“All the necessary mechanisms have been put in place to level the playing field for both men and women... Both genders have equal access to training and promotion.” Lucia F Rail Operator Spain

“...the training is all the same, everybody has it, men and woman... Everybody is the same with training there is none of this ‘well you can't get it because you are a man or a woman’ kind of thing. We have to keep up with our training.” Theresa F Operator UK

Moreover, several respondents specifically pointed out that their training is paid for by their organisation:

“I am doing the IRO degree at XX which is all entirely sponsored by XX, I am not paying for it. I am getting paid while doing it.” Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

“...anything that I have requested in terms of training has been accepted and paid for, which is good.” Agnes F Manager Ireland

“XX have funded a lot of my studies and you know, I'm a psychologist and did a masters and more psychology. So basically, all my education has kind of been funded.” Lorna F Director Ireland

One respondent reported that their practice of offering training ‘in-house’ or online is beneficial for the organisation and particularly beneficial for women with caring/parenting responsibilities:

“So we have done a lot of learning like this (online), so on every one of our sites we have WebEx so people can travel less which means that if it's a woman learning to be a train driver, or a train operative, she doesn't have to think ‘I have to get childcare’, maybe be away for three days training. What she is doing (is) going into her normal workplace and learning what she needs to there. She can do all the traction stuff in the depot and she doesn't have to spend time away from home. Why wouldn't you do that? It's cheaper, it's better, they are able to do their training faster as they are travelling less. It's cheaper for us, why wouldn't we do that.” Naomi F Director UK

However, one respondent noted that in her organisation there is evidence women are not going for training as much as men:

“...one of the issues I have is that the men are very ambitious and want to do all the training, but in many circumstances the women aren't as ambitious and don't want to do the training. And that is a real problem, even when you say, ‘look I really need you to do that training’ and they won't. I think its fear.” Louise F Director UK

Moreover, data revealed that training designed specifically for women was offered in a few of the organisations studied. One Irish organisation developed a programme to promote gender balance

in the organisation, across frontline level and middle management level. The programme has been welcomed by participants:

“They had a (training) programme actually in XX that I was part of as it happens and that was designed specifically for women.” Agnes F Manager Ireland

“XX actually have a woman in leadership program and I think they have done over a number of years... I do think that they are trying to encourage women and network women through the organisation but yes, it’s definitely something the women need but then men need it too or some of the men.” Irene F Manager Ireland

“...there has been a program for female leadership of the future, for the organization... and it was like if you’re interested in developing your career as a female leader of the future for XX, you had to write a bit about yourself and why you would be right for the role and they selected about 15-20 women from the organisation and put us on these programmes where you’re given intensive leadership coaching and I got a place on the program, which was really positive.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“I was on the very first women in leadership program that we ran in 2001, which was with our then Equality Officer, so I suppose it has a special place in my heart seeing how it's kind of took me, a girl from, you know, a pretty impoverished background, no third level education, and kind of brought me into that world of opportunity and kind of you know set me on a great path... It was a women specific certificate in business management.” Lorna F Director Ireland

Another organisation also provided training, specifically for female managers, to aid progression:

“I think I've been very lucky that all my line managers throughout my career have been really, really supportive and one specific programme that XX launched... it was around providing coaching to the senior female managers who, you know, who they thought were ready to sort of progress or take the next step in their career. And that really helped as well.” Samantha F Director UK

Job Characteristics - Safety and Security

In terms of safety and security the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Job Characteristics - Negative Attitude of Male Colleagues

As examined in FC HR Policies - Recruitment above, the research data highlighted that at the point of recruitment and in work unconscious bias, conscious bias, discrimination, sexism, and a lack of fairness all impact upon gender balance and women’s employability in the industry. Examination of the data highlights such practices under the FC negative attitudes of male colleagues. Data suggests that many interviewees experienced sexism and discrimination at work. Some experiences include:

“...the only thing I used to have that drove me absolutely insane was if we were in a meeting because I was the female, I was assumed to be the tea maker and tidy up. It drove me crazy until I refused.” Sharon F Manager UK

“...as my role progressed I still kind of felt like I was perceived to be the girl to take the minutes at the meetings, when in actual fact I was probably the contract manager responsible for everything everyone was doing around the table at the time.” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“Women are still in the minority, absolutely in the minority within rail as a sector...I am in a meeting they say to me ‘do you need anything to take notes?’ They presume I am secretarial support. They have done that all of my career. One man said, ‘How can a wee girl like you be running this?’” Crystal F Director UK

“I was one of only three women drivers at my depot out of 60 drivers when I first started. I was warned about one of the others as being ‘she is always pregnant, and she is never at work, she is lazy’ and all that type of thing. And it wasn’t that at all, she had three kids, but I was told she was work shy, she wasn’t work shy she was just married and started her family. I was warned straight away. And then I was asked ‘how long is it until you are going to be off and get pregnant then?’ Not by management, by the other drivers, and I thought that is not OK, “oh you are married are you, well you won’t be around long then” and you know it’s all of this stuff.” Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

“It seems to me that these situations occur more often at lower levels. I mean drivers in particular, rather than office workers. Maybe because their approach and attitude is changing more slowly. I know of one such case, an argument between our female instructor and a male driver. The driver was from a different company. Basically, he said “I will not obey your commands.” But in our work the supervisors sometimes have to give out orders to drivers from other companies and sometimes they get: “you are not from our company, so I will not follow your instructions”. Here, an additional argument was that “you are a woman”, but that was one incident in two years, so is that a lot or a little?” Patryk M Supervisor Poland

“I am also quite sensitive to this type of behaviour. It just irritates me enormously and seems extremely unprofessional to me as well. If someone is in a much, much higher position than me and our relationship is completely asymmetrical, and they use diminutives, caressing terms or inappropriate statements directed at me, it is completely unacceptable to me... Sexism as a phenomenon is quite firmly established in our Polish society and in fact it is an almost everyday phenomenon - I believe.” Maria F Communications Poland

However, Maria continues:

“Such situations do happen, but not too often. There are tons of colleagues who try to maintain a supportive, professional attitude and I have great working relations with most of the guys whom I contact on a daily basis.” Maria F Communications Poland

Interviewees reported how they dealt with negative attitudes of male colleagues. This ranged from reporting such behaviour via official routes, personally challenging the behaviour to changing their language. Interestingly there were many examples given of interviewees who suggested you need a particular personality type to work in the industry, with traits like ‘thick skin’, ‘not taking things personally’ and ‘strength of character’ reported as being vital.

“There were sexism issues in the past, and this resulted in the employer creating a code of ethics. Every lady can submit comments, regarding mobbing, harassment, discrimination etc. It may be incognito; it may be with name and surname.” Arek M Tram Operator Poland

“I have quite a thick skin, so I don’t take these things too personally. Most of the time I think it’s funny which I think has helped me deal with it. I do tend to be a bit more up front than many women are, and

I will just say 'that is not OK and legally you can't say that to me, and you can get yourself in a lot of trouble'. Most of the time they will just back up and say, 'Oh I am really sorry I didn't mean it THAT way.'
Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

"...you have to have broad shoulders, an open mind, thick skin, almost to the point sometimes that you felt you had to be one of the boys and put up with a lot of things that maybe now I wouldn't put up with you know... you need a thick skin and be one of the boys." Erin F Manager UK

"I think, you have to be quite a thick-skinned individual... You couldn't be a snowflake let's put it that way... I am comfortable in that, but I can see other women being totally intimidated by that. I think it takes a certain kind of person." Frances F Director UK

"I look back and see that I tried to be accepted as one of the boys and talk that talk and make sure that any of the jokes that were given were not offensive to me and grow that thick skin. I am naturally thick skinned, and I am not a girly girl by any manner or means but looking back I have given up a lot of what makes me a woman or makes me feminine." Hannah F Driver UK

"I think credibility is a massive thing, showing value in the work you do, having to prove yourself almost. Having to work twice as hard as a man. Resilience is also a big thing; you have to have a thick skin. Being able to brush off the comments and be able to give as good as you get almost... I think that is pretty much it, the (male) culture is a big thing, you know there are some of my friends who I know would not survive a week here they cannot believe some of the stories I tell them, it's not for the faint hearted. You need to be a strong person; you know to deal with it. I am sure the culture has got better, but I am sure it's going to take a lot to change that unfortunately." Nancy F HR Supervisor UK

"I do think though from my experience in the organisation you need to be able to hold your own and have a strength about yourself. I would never really have been one to shy away from confrontation but if there was an issue that needed to be dealt with, I'd no problem in discussing it or pointing it out at a meeting, regardless of the level I'm interacting with... I don't know if it's strength, but you have to be able to hold your own, yeah have thick skin, because it can be intimidating if you're in a room full of men which I have been, it can be intimidating if you allow it to be." Siobhan F Director Ireland

"I have noticed that women (colleagues from work) change a lot, they try to catch up in some way, they somehow give in and change their current habits. If someone did not use profanity - then they start to use it. This is characteristic of the way drivers communicate, but it is slowly changing.... That there is a sexist approach between men and women and there is a lot of profanity." Teodor M Tram Driver Poland

Personal Circumstances - Caring/Parenting Responsibilities

Numerous respondents reported that fairness in the transport industry is about flexibility, such as family friendly work hours, however the data suggests that many jobs in the sector are incompatible with such flexibility. (Flexible working is discussed fully in FC Flexible Working above) Overall, there was agreement from respondents that the nature of many roles in the transport industry, particularly engineering and operational roles, require shift work and working unsociable hours, and that while this may not be detrimental to women, or indeed men, without parenting or caring responsibilities, it does impact on gender balance and female employability when women have these responsibilities. As this interviewee replied when asked if current employment practices are successful in respect to fairness for women in the transport sector:

“No, the lack of flexibility for working parents and mothers, caring responsibilities etcetera. It is a fact of life that women have more caring responsibilities than men, so their earning potential is low. I think as great as it is that XX have put forward support structures for women, I think the uptake is lower than they would like. I think there is a lack of communication internally about what support is available... Women in general being the care givers makes it more difficult. But unfortunately, if you don’t show up to drive the train, the train doesn’t go. There has to be reliability I suppose.” Grace F Rail Train Driver (Trainer) UK

While it was agreed that it was discriminatory to suggest that women should provide the majority of childcare and caring in families the reality that these responsibilities fall more to women was recognised by interviewees. Evidence from the research data suggests that caring/parenting responsibilities impact upon gender balance and women’s employability in the transport industry, for example, at the point of recruitment and selection:

“...you know it’s an illegal question to ask, ‘do you have kids, are your married?’ You know anything like that. I think a lot of women have become more conservative in their CVs to try and keep the detail low and they don’t have a risk factor. A lot of men are still reluctant to take women on who are of childbearing age in case they get pregnant.” Crystal F Director UK

More generally regarding once employed in the industry, interviewees offered examples of the incompatibility of caring/parenting responsibilities and many roles:

“Engineering do day shift, back shift night shift, drivers do crazy shifts they work 2 days of early shifts, 2 days of middle shifts and one late shift a week. So instead of having a week and a week and a week they do it day by day. That would kill me, I couldn’t do it. The old timers who have been there forever want to keep it. The new people are pushing for change. We do have some family friendly working, but you really have to have a good reason to access it as you know our business is shift work.” Caroline F Director UK

“We do have family friendly policies... I still think because its shift work it is hard to fit your family. I am lucky it’s just me and the dog, but I still find it difficult to fit in time to see my (adult children) family. Before this I used to work 9 – 3 to suit the kids when they were small and with this industry you can’t do that. You can’t do half a run, it’s impossible I don’t see how you can do it... it’s not the company it’s the job... if I am in London and need to be back for the kids for a certain time, then I can’t do the London run. So, to be honest I don’t think it’s a job you can go into if you have personal commitments, personally I don’t think so.” Theresa F Operator UK

“I don’t have children and that is something we need to speak up about, particularly in freight. You know not having children is a factor, I can work night shifts and I have got a great roster and most women would love it, but it is still very different, and I appreciate that I have a totally different set of circumstances and its, its different for women with kids.” Hannah F Operator UK

Moreover, this interviewee pointed out that she experienced discrimination in the form of gender-based assumptions around childcare as a board member when a senior male colleague suggested:

“... ‘would you be willing to give up your seat on the board because I know that you have children and it might be too much for you take on board’, to allow him to sit on the board. But he didn’t ask any males, not one, but he asked me. And he used the card, you are a mother, you have kids, and this might be too

much for you. He thought it was ok to say that, and that was only a couple of years ago. So, it wasn't 10 or 15 years ago." Crystal F Director UK

So, fairness at work for women with caring responsibilities may not be limited to the type of work they do. However, several interviewees did highlight those caring responsibilities are impacted upon by more flexible working offered in certain roles and not in others:

"I think I was lucky when I started this role (office based), part time and its very flexible. I needed the flexibility when I started as my kids were small. They are very flexible here and so long as I do the work required, I can be flexible in my start and finishing times. I know that probably isn't the case for women driver's etcetera. It's more difficult when they work shift patterns." Justine F Manager UK

With women even moving positions, from frontline work to office work, in the same organisation to accommodate their caring responsibilities:

"...sometimes what I've noticed is maybe frontline women will look for an office job day job, kind of they'll come out of the frontline when they do have children." Lorna F Director Ireland

The above data points to an incompatibility between childcare responsibilities and particular roles in the transport industry, that is front line, operational jobs specifically. Yet the experiences of participants in Poland suggest that this incompatibility can be overcome. The focus group participants discussed the importance of flexibility for those with caring responsibilities and highlighted that their organisation has a reputation for flexibility around this issue, offering job share and shift work that accommodates the childcare responsibilities of both men and women:

"There were people who moved from another carrier to us, precisely because there was this flexibility... Due to the scale of our company we can have a very personal approach to our employees. For example, a married couple works for us, and the schedules of mother and father are adapted to their needs, so that it is possible to take care of the child... Another thing is that at our depot... We can make a pair with another employee and arrange shifts. So we don't have to work two shifts - morning and afternoon. We can choose a person who wants to do only the afternoon and then I can do the morning shift only, then we are a complete pair. And the person who arranges the schedules does it in a way that lets me take the morning trams and my partner the afternoon ones... So that then I finish work at 3 p.m. and can pick up the children from kindergarten and school. Gentlemen, too, because not only ladies take care of children. Fathers do too. I think it is more an issue for women, because of the image of the woman being the one who takes care of children. But if a man asked for this, he would probably receive it, our schedules are quite flexible." Patryk M Transport Coordinator Supervisor Poland

"I know a few cases where a person actually drives, let's say, only in the morning, and in the afternoon, he takes care of his child." Keir M Operator Poland

"I have two young children... I worked like this for a year and a half (temporary job share) and the manager kind of helped me find my replacement who would only work for the second shift." Petronela F Tram Operator Poland

As pointed out in FC Flexible Working above the research data also highlights rare examples of measures put in place or suggestions going forward in other organisations out with Poland to increase the flexibility of operational jobs that traditionally have been less flexible.

“... we don’t just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers.” Naomi F Director UK

“There is not that thinking outside of the box, well you know that could be done by two people it could be terms time it could be annualized hours, people are not thinking wider and that is why, you know it goes back to the traditional arrangements. I am seeing clients doing a complete U turn now and its whether that will happen with operational jobs. It is happening with office jobs. It’s how, you know, maybe could a job be done by one person doing two days and another three days, its thinking differently about things.” Frances F Director UK

As the above evidence suggests focus group and interview data emphasises that both men and women have caring responsibilities.

“... it’s not just women it’s men as well have other caring commitments, we are finding it now with COVID, it might be childcare, it might be elderly parents it might be someone infirm or disabled at home...” Crystal F Director UK

“In my company there is such a possibility when it comes to establishing a schedule or agreeing on changes there, but it is a privilege for every employee - I mean about drivers - regardless of gender. I believe that this is the direction in which it should go, because on the other hand, if this is meant only for women - men also raise children, men also have some responsibilities, some in the morning, some in the afternoon - then it could cause unnecessary conflicts... everyone has this opportunity, everyone can get along. There are people who are active in the morning, there are people who are active in the afternoon, there are people who have plans in the morning, some people who have plans in the afternoon. And there are people who don’t care, and they go in the morning and in the afternoon - it makes no difference to them.” Leon M Multi-Modal Transport Coordinator Poland

“Make sure that co-workers do not ridicule any man for asking for reduced working hours in order to meet the needs of their children. Among men, there are colleagues who laugh at those who have taken reduced working hours.” Samuel M Engineer Spain

“...working late at night and working weekends, it’s not sociable hours if you have a family. But then it’s not fair to only give females the Monday to Friday 9 to 5 roles. So it needs to be equal.” Nancy F Bus HR Supervisor UK

Moreover, the recent impact of the global pandemic, in particular the closing of childcare establishments and schools, has drawn attention to flexible work practises for individuals with caring responsibilities. The research data underlined that the measures put in place during the pandemic may lead to positive change in the transport sector, for example:

“... we need to make the sector as flexible and as supportive as possible for females who have families, and do I think that happens? No I don’t. Across the board, no. I do however think that COVID will have a positive impact on, a great catalyst on, highlighting flexible working and all these things that allow women

to carry on at home and allow them to carry on looking after their families. So I think it (COVID adaptations) may be a benefit.” Sharon F Multi-Modal Manager UK

“But now more children are going back to school it’s causing them (employees) a child-minding concern and that is for both men and women. So what we are doing is working with them to enable them to work and follow social distancing rules, enable them to go on to a shift pattern that is cost effective for us and also works for their childcare. There is no point in pissing them off, and saying no go back to the same shifts you were on, we have a business to run... the only way we can run our business is if our people are there and our people can only be there (work) if they have child care and we have got to understand that some people don’t think like that and haven’t changed how their business works and think, you know sod childcare, you have to be there (work) forget about that, and we have said that is not how we are thinking about things, let’s work together and lets find a solution. It’s ongoing we are not there yet.” Naomi F Rail Director UK

Personal Circumstances - Economic Deprivation

In terms of economic deprivation, the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Residential Location/Work Distance

In terms of residential location/work distance the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Transport Access to Workplace

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC

Individual Characteristics – Skills

The research data did not provide many insights into the FC Skills with regard gender balance, female employability or key factors influencing career choices for women. More generally the data highlighted that specialist skills impact the level or role undertaken by women, for example female engineers and females in middle management. These individuals, they suggest, possess academic qualifications that allow them to access these roles and/or join graduate programmes. However, many of the front line/operational roles are learned from within the organisation and the number of female apprentices appears to be low. Interestingly, one manager pointed out the emerging skills gap in the industry and the need to have a gender balanced workforce:

“There is an emerging skills gap because a lot of the people are like me, when you go into the rail sector it tends to be a job for life. So you have a whole host of people who have 20-, 30- and 40-years' service that are coming to the end of their careers and nowadays young people don’t seem to do that so ... We need to attract the best graduates out of university, the best apprentices and that is not gender specific but if you are missing out a whole sector of females then you are only getting half the pool.” Sharon F Multi Modal Manager UK

Individual Characteristics - Adaptability – Attitude to work

In terms of adaptability and attitude to work the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Educational Attainment

With regard FC Educational Attainment and gender balance and female employability the data highlighted that the lack of female role models, education and awareness for many jobs in the industry has an impact, resulting in fewer women than men in engineering and operational roles. This situation has led to a push from many organisations to educate females regarding job opportunities in the sector through contact with schools, colleges, universities and job fayres (as highlighted above in FC HR Policies – Recruitment above). For example:

“There is no cultural predisposition on the part of women to study engineering, there is a mental framework, caused by a lack of references of women working in the sector”. Lucia F Rail Operator Spain

“It’s getting access to the schools, finding ways to get access into schools you know to get people like me in to talk to them and unless it’s facilitated in some way a lot of schools won’t get it.” Frances F Rail Director UK

However, one interesting finding points to the job or organisation specificity of some jobs in the sector, meaning that ‘on the job learning’ is key:

“...when I started working in the place where I work now, the things I learnt here were impossible to learn at any university, no one in fact, from the outside, who came, would be able to do it, because it is a job that is specific to the XX, there are dedicated programmes. And really only by sitting at the desk and being tutored by someone who knows them, can one learn the job. Magda F Multi Modal Passenger Information Poland

Individual Characteristics - Health status and wellbeing

In terms of health status and wellbeing the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics – Demographic

In terms of the effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.) the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Recommendations made by participants to enhance gender balance and female employability in the transport sector:

As evidenced above research data suggests job segregation and lack of flexible working are among the biggest factors impacting gender balance and female employability in the sector. Respondents made recommendations to address these issues.

Regarding job segregation, to address the commonly reported theme that ‘you can’t be what you can’t see’ practices such as ‘women in transport days’, specific women in transport groups and educational events were cited as examples of support received that positively impact upon women employees and a more equal gender balance in the industry. Also, respondents noted the

importance of education in schools, colleges and universities regarding the transport sector as a potential employer.

“I think there are still some professions where women think ‘I wouldn’t be able to do that’. And when they suddenly see someone in a job ad and they see a woman doing it it’s a bit, what’s that saying, you can’t be what you can’t see. We need to see a lot more women in a lot more diverse roles and look at them and think ‘oh I can relate to that, maybe I could do that too, that looks like fun or interesting or challenging’.” Sarah F Director UK

“...for engineering, I think we need to go to the to the source. So, schools and colleges so that we get the fresh talent.” Samantha F Director UK

“They [women] are not aware at all, it’s not all just about dirty truck driving, the trucks now are really like, they are all IT, they have telematics and electronics. Our industry really needs to be pushing women forwards. The trade bodies should also be putting women forward, they are trying but it needs more than a picture of a woman in a high viz and hard hat. Women cannot do this by ourselves we need the help of men; men need to understand the importance of females in the workplace.” Louise F Truck Director UK

Recommendations were also made to enhance flexible working across all job types in the sector:

“We have also introduced things like flexible working, and we introduced it a long time before COVID came and I am delighted to say that it enabled our business to do something amazing and keep going right from the start of lock down because all of our people were able to do flexible working. But we don’t just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers.” Naomi F Rail Director UK

And as this director pointed out, ‘traditional arrangements’ could be altered by ‘thinking differently’ about flexibility for all roles:

“There is not that thinking outside of the box (currently), well you know that could be done by two people it could be terms time it could be annualized hours, people are not thinking wider and that is why, you know it goes back to the traditional arrangements. I am seeing clients doing a complete U turn now and its whether that will happen with operational jobs. It is happening with office jobs. It’s how, you know, maybe could a job be done by one person doing two days and another three days, its thinking differently about things.” Frances F Rail Director UK

Annex 9 Use Case IV Question 4 Interviews

Research Question 4: What are the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

The following section set out the analysis in response to Research Question 4.

Socio Economic Conditions - Job segregation

In relation to increasing the participation of women employed in the transport sector a key factor for influencing women's career choice is the concept of job segregation. Job segregation relates to the idea that there are jobs designated to either men or women only.

The data from our interviews suggest there was an overwhelming consensus that the industry, across job roles and sectors, is still viewed and experienced as a male dominated sector. Participants provided many specific examples from their own organisations:

“Women are still in the minority, absolutely in the minority within rail as a sector”. Crystal F Director UK

“It's still a male dominated industry, there are still old-fashioned ideas within the industry”. Erin F Lorry Driver UK

“They say that the regulations guarantee full equality between the two genders, but in reality, in the engineering department they are all men”. Samuel M Engineer Spain

With examples of job segregation still in place provided from across countries:

“Out of thirty traffic supervision employees there is one woman”. Leon M Transport Coordinator Poland

“The new promotion of train drivers has proposed that at least 40% of new hires should be women, as they are the least represented gender in this category of work”. Billy M Ticket Inspector Spain

As this data was received via a secondary organisation who conducted the focus groups in Spain, and provided us with a report in English, we were not unfortunately able to probe this reply any further to ascertain how this proposal has been working.

One participant illustrated an apparent rationale for job segregation when discussing women applying for and working in the engineering department of a transport company:

“It seems to me that this is an area in which a woman is unlikely to be successful precisely because it is a dirty job, it is a job that requires strength, requires some knowledge. Well, of course, this is not something that no one is able to achieve, but this part rather, I think, is and will remain closed to women for a long time”. Leon M Transport Coordinator Poland

The ongoing workplace cultures that appear to still maintain job segregation amongst transport organisations was supported by examples of roles and departments that are still assumed by participants not to be suitable for women.

“It’s not just our industry, elsewhere too there are typically male areas, where it is difficult to find a woman, I don’t know if anyone has ever seen a female mechanic?” Magda F Office Worker Poland

“I suppose the traffic control office they are the hub of the business. There has never been a female in there and that is probably because it is quite a difficult environment to go into for a female. Historically it’s always been the men, it’s quite fast paced”. Caroline Managing Director Uk

Highlighting that within and across the transport sector there are still currently roles and departments that have no female employees, departments where women are not expected to be working and importantly where women are not expected to apply for roles.

Conversely the points above were refuted by women already working in the frontline of the transport sector who stated that they had not found any jobs they were prohibited from completing because of their sex and that in general there were always ways to work around obstacles to more equality in job access.

“You find different ways of doing that job that makes it easier for you strength wise. And you find you way around it instead of not doing it, if you know what I mean”. Erin F Lorry Driver UK

The findings also reported that the majority of women who do work in the transport sector currently work in traditional female roles, with most female employees being office based in administrative roles etc.

“HR directors are always women; customer experience directors are always women that is so true”. Crystal F Director UK

“When I left the IT department there were no more females in the entire department there are 12 people there”. Tina F Manager Ireland

The findings above would indicate that there is a wider educational piece of work still required amongst and within transport organisations and importantly in schools and higher and further education to sign post the opportunities for young girls in STEM and engineering careers. The themes relating to education and the ongoing work by some transport organisations are discussed in detail below in their own section.

Socio Economic Conditions - Demand factors

When discussing participants’ understanding of why women and girls are still so underrepresented in the transport sector, there were 3 main themes which emerged from the data which sit inside the FC demand factors, they were attracting women to the industry, recruitment processes, and processes put in place to retain women once they are employed.

In the first instance it was noted that young women and girls are not currently aware of the variety of roles available to women in the transport sector and that wider effort is required to engage young women and girls:

“I think that the understanding about what the job is, is not really there. There needs to be better communication about the possibilities of roles within rail and explanations of what the job (of a driver) is for women to be interested in doing the job”. Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

“Our industry really needs to be pushing women forwards. The trade bodies should also be putting women forward. They are trying but it needs more than a picture of a woman in a high viz [high-visibility jacket] and hard hat. Women cannot do this by ourselves we need the help of men; men need to understand the importance of females in the workplace... And then I have had ‘well look the door is open, the door is open for women and they don’t want to walk through then it’s their fault’. And I am like yes, the door maybe open but there is no open sign on it, or anyone saying the green light to allow women to come in”. Louise F Managing Director UK

“We need to attract the best graduates out of university, the best apprentices and that is not gender specific but if you are missing out a whole sector of females then you are only getting half the pool”. Sharon F Manager Ireland

In response to the current lack of female employees and in order to address the shortage of women employees they have been attending open days at schools, career days at colleges and graduate recruitment events. (This is discussed further below).

When discussing recruitment in more detail with participants, it emerged that the majority of organisations claim they currently run gender neutral recruitment campaigns which include images of women and men in roles and ensured that the language used in any advertising materials is also gender neutral by using a variety of software programmes available specifically to do so.

However, when targeted recruitment for female employees was discussed as an option the majority of participants stated this was not something that they would support, with many claiming that it only adds ‘a target’ to the backs of women who have been recruited this way.

“I am not sure I would be comfortable doing that. I mean that is discriminatory, isn’t it? What you want is the best person for the job and whatever you do you want that to be the attraction”. Caroline F Managing Director UK

“It’s not about positive discrimination because that last thing you want as a woman is that target on your back... anybody who came in under that scheme would automatically have that target on their back”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

One participant claimed their organisation had attempted to develop a recruitment campaign targeted at women:

“...I know they have in the past. I had a conversation about it recently, and he told me about the company trying to get females to apply and they did the same thing that TFL (Transport for London) did and used the back pages of VOGUE and other women’s magazines to get the particular demographic...they also did something with Mumsnet online forum”. Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

However, when pressed further the participant was unable to inform us of how successful that campaign had been in terms of female applicants for roles at that organisation.

As stated above, participants also highlighted that once a transport organisation has successfully employed women in frontline roles, they then had to ensure that an organisational culture was developed to support and maintain women in these roles:

“Your question to me was how do you recruit women, but it’s not only about recruiting people it’s how do you work as a company. You could have a brilliant recruitment process that is going to target women, you might choose to sponsor something and get involved with women, fabulous. But when you employ them and they come to work for you, if you haven’t got an engaging workforce and culture, they just come in the front door and out the back door. So, all the investment you made in recruitment policies is a waste”.
Louise F Managing Director Transport Consultant UK

The importance of retaining female employees also highlighted the significance of female employees having female role models and/or mentors in the workplace as an important factor in their career choices, based on:

“...what’s that saying, you can’t be what you can’t see”. Sarah F Director UK

“We have got to get more women in and more women in senior roles, the very senior females' leaders we have are some of the best leaders, somehow or other we need to get more females in and address the balance”. Frances F Managing Director UK

With some female senior managers agreeing and claiming that they believed it was their responsibility to support the women coming after them in terms of employment.

“I think it is a responsibility of us all that have had successful careers as women to coach, to mentor to bring women along with us... I am in that position where I am able to [do] that and it’s a responsibility for those who, I respect the people who came before me and cleared the way for me, I can only do the same for them”. Naomi F Director UK

However, when probed to explain how their organisation actively looked to retain female employees, some of the frontline employees were more negative in their experiences stating that there was no specific awareness of retaining women employees:

“Well, they don’t, we are no different to the men. At the end of the day, they say that if you want to leave then leave, there are plenty to fill your role”. Theresa F Coach Driver UK

One train driver claimed their organisation did not have enough female employees in the first instance to provide roles models or mentoring:

“There are certain groups looking at that, but the problem is when you do not have many women in these positions to start with, then it dilutes it even more”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

“I look at the next rung of potential management and I don’t know any women in any of those positions in the company.” Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

Socio-Economic Conditions- Policy and Legal

In order to explore the impact of employment policies and law across the partner states (UK Scotland Ireland Spain and Poland) with regards to influencing women’s career choices, we asked participants “are current employment practices in your country fair for women”.

The replies produced themes based on an acknowledgement that there are many policies currently in place but they are not all utilised consistently across all organisations, that they are not taken seriously by all organisations and are there as a form of a tick box exercise and importantly that the policies are being developed by men in board rooms who have no real knowledge or understanding of the experiences of women on the frontline, with the majority of replies from managers and frontline staff claiming that more needs to be done.

“...they are only there in case someone wants to take you to court”. Louise F Managing Director UK

“You need to engage your staff if you want honest feedback and if the people that don’t understand the job are the ones discussing and creating policy are not going to get it right. It’s going to look good, and they are going to have a diversity policy in place, and if they do it well, they might even get an award or two out of it. But will actually make things any better? I think we are still a long way from making those types of changes that are required. You know you can even see where organisations have taken two or three women who are saying the right thing, the promote them into positions, but if they are the women who want to say the right things and keep that new position you are still not get that change”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

In interviews with HR personnel and others it was highlighted that in many circumstances the responsibility for local decisions such as availability of part time hours and flexible shifts was the responsibility of local managers and was not in fact a piece of written organisational policy.

“So, I said there is a bit of a gap there. Probably more of a process that’s documented, but less so a policy, if you got me?” Elaine F HR Ireland

This raises questions regarding the movement of managers and what happens when after agreeing something at a local level they move out of that role and someone else moves into it. Would that mean all of the actions previously put in place disappear?

Socio-Economic Conditions - Female Facilities

One of the largest findings that emerged from the data which was shown to influence career choice for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport was related to the provision of female facilities. For the majority of participants this focused on a lack of spaces for women when they had to share toilet facilities with men or use the disabled toilets, therefore impacting on the access of disabled people to their own toilets.

“There is only one place that I go to that has a woman’s toilet. I am an advocate for trying to get women into freight, genuinely it’s a great place to be and its great people, however, that is not something I would wish to share with women”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

With regards to women’s concerns, one Spanish participant highlighted the importance for women to have access to clean and sanitary facilities during menstruation and also in relation to the time

taken and frequency of these visits during a woman's menstrual cycle, which impact on the daily routines and duties of women specifically at this time.

"For women, having menstruation at work due to the hygienic state of the bathrooms and the complexity of carrying out the service. [is a concern] They need a reserve person, who can cover their position in certain seasons, and who can go to the bathroom as long as they deem appropriate". Sofia F Train Driver Spain

In terms of female drivers and access to female facilities on the road, one participant claimed that in their organisation there is an awareness that not all routes provide access to suitable facilities (approximately 30%) and that adjustments are made for female employees.

"The schedules are adjusted so that women don't have to be drivers on lines, where the infrastructure is inadequate". Patryk M Transport Coordinator Poland

The indication from other participants was that in their opinion many organisations have been remiss in taking cognisance of what women in the workplace require.

"More thought for females in the workplace" Nancy F HR UK

This concept was supported by comments from Polish participants who discussed the experience of their own organisation and how no one had ever thought to include facilities for women in certain areas of the organisation.

"[Toilets] which at that time had to be adapted to the cloakrooms so that a woman could also work there, because nobody had even thought about it before, there was no such need". Leon M Multi-Modal Transport Coordinator Poland

The replies from across countries and particularly frontline employees supported this notion that currently it is assumed that needs of men and women in the workplace are equal and no additional measures for women are required.

"When I was out on the road (she now works local runs only) It was really difficult from a woman's point of view at the services. The majority of services were male only they didn't even have showers or anything for women. I did find that difficult and I did have a few run ins with service staff, saying look you know I am a driver, I am driving this lorry and I am as equal as any man who walks in here and I am entitled to have the same facilities. I was told it is not economically viable to provide them because it would be a room sitting doing nothing waiting on the odd woman who might come in. So, I just ended up using the men's facilities and hoping no men would come in". Erin F Lorry Driver UK

However, many of the participants when discussing women's toilets and facilities also discussed the current situation for men, which in the rail sector particularly appears to be just as unsatisfactory for men as women.

"Until we make our industry more standard, good practice, good conditions for all we won't attract more women". Louise F Managing Director Transport Consultant UK

“Some of the things that can be improved to bring women into the industry can also be improved for men, the toilet facilities for men are also not great, we don’t have toilets on the train...you can be on your train for 10 hours. Men probably don’t like having to use bushes they would probably like something more convenient in this day and age. But for women, that is not practical or convenient. You get to the point where you are scared to drink...” Hannah F Train Driver UK

“I think that difficulty we have got is that men can pee into a bottle standing up, it’s not ideal, it’s really not ideal... but we have to start thinking differently to say women have periods how do they deal with that when they are out driving...I wish it was different but it’s not. We really need to find a way to sort the toilet problem, or we are never going to get equality in the rail industry”. Naomi F Director UK

A lack of policy and spaces for nursing mothers with regards to breast feeding or expressing milk were raised by Spanish participants

“With maternity, it is also complicated to go to work. The breaks are complicated, and sometimes, you need to remove your milk. This was a taboo for people, as they had no place to do it and not enough time to do it. These are women's difficulties, which are not taken into account when it comes to work”. Sofia F Train Driver Spain

However, in Poland it appears that at least one transport organisation already provides a certain degree of flexibility for nursing mothers.

“There is something like a schedule for a nursing mother. It's not available for men. It's not necessarily only for nursing mothers”. Arek M Tram Driver Poland

As these findings highlight, the provision of female facilities is a major factor for women in relation to their career choices in terms of privacy, dignity and health. It would be hard to imagine any other employment sector that did not actively plan for or acknowledge the specific spaces and facilities female employees require to be able to be fully employed.

Job Characteristics - HR Policies

The discussions above relating to demand factors and jobs segregation also covered many HR policies that support the inclusion of women therefore this section will discuss policies on access to training and promotion opportunities for women and how these affect the career choices of women.

With regards to equality of opportunity for women to access training provision, the majority of participants stated that across countries and organisations they had experienced no inequality and that men and women tended to have the same access to training within their own organisations. In relation to railways and road haulage this was supported by the additional caveats that all drivers had to complete the same level of driver training legally to be able to commence employment in the first place.

“I am fortunate as a train driver that you do need to pass all the same tests pass all the training so once you become a train driver all your colleagues know that you are there on merit, so there is already that respect and train driving is quite unique in that”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

This was supported by a coach driver who also highlighted that anyone who wished to become a driver must complete the same training which is legislative based.

“Yes, I mean the training is all the same, everybody has it, men and woman. We have to have our CPC we need training and that is updated [as drivers] We have to keep up with our training”. Theresa F Coach Driver UK

However, when it comes to ongoing training whilst in employment it was noted that that some women perhaps do not always take advantage of training opportunities provided.

“One of the issues I have is that the men are very ambitious and want to do all the training but in many circumstances the women aren’t as ambitious and don’t want to do the training. And that is a real problem, even when you say look, I really need you to do that training and they won’t. I think its fear “If you look at our senior management level there is probably only one female, are we saying that there are no other female capable to be at that level? I don’t think this is the case, but I think it’s a legacy of previous cultural situation that is to be challenged.” Louise F Managing Director UK

Whilst statements like the one below highlights that not all training can be delivered locally and may entail days away from home which would cause additional stresses for parents or those with caring responsibilities.

“So, people can travel less which means that if it’s a woman learning to be a train driver, or a train operative, she doesn’t have to think I have to get childcare, maybe be away for three days training what she is doing going into her normal workplace and learning what she needs to there.” Naomi F Business Services Director UK

However, overall participants agreed that in general all training that was provided by their employer was not based on sex in anyway and both male and female employees were given equal opportunity to take part.

“Training is always organized generally for employees, there is no driver-driver division. Even on the contract, I have information that I am a driver. The gender is not provided. So, we’re just treated as employees”. Petronela F Tram Driver Poland

With participants in Ireland highlighting the work their organisation has done in reference to women focused training and supporting women into higher education.

“Look I think there’s a number of initiatives that they have specifically aimed at women. They set up a kind of an upskilling group, so they picked I think about 20 women from around the company and they sent them to XX on a course and then they introduce them to different training packages to try and help them in their careers”. Shaun M Manager Ireland

“Any of my colleagues that I know of that have gone for further education, they’ve done it successfully and it’s been fair. I have certainly not heard of anybody being rejected”. Agnes F Project Manager Ireland

“Everyone is trained to do the same kind of work”. Samuel M Engineer Spain

In relation to promotion prospects, one participant from the rail industry reported that within their organisation to support women in their personal development and to assist them in promotion.

“We have started doing a programme called step up which is just for women. There are three different levels to that, there is step up the basic level for women who have never had a supervisory role or a managerial role, then they have two more one for management level and one for director level so there is constant female development. It is only women who are invited to that”. Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

However, when this participant was pressed to explore female promotion directly within their organisation, they responded that.

“I want to say yes, but in reality, when I look around, I am the only woman in the training department. I am the only woman in the policy team. I look at the next rung of potential management and I don’t know any women in any of those positions in the company”. Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

When participants were asked if female employees had ever transferred from the traditional office roles to the frontline or be upskilled only two responded that they had, indicating lateral moves and opportunities within transport could be very limited, affecting women’s choices in relation to careers.

“We had a female MD many, many years ago who started in the cash office of the organisation and that wasn’t yesterday”. Justine F Manager UK

“We have taken from within our organisation so a woman who worked in stores said I would really like to be an engineer. So, we said it’s an awful lot less pay, and she said yes that is the problem I don’t think I can do it from that perspective. So, we said OK what we will do is keep your pay the same until you have caught up if that allows you to do that. So, she said Ok”. Naomi F Business Services Director UK

Job Characteristics - Terms and Conditions

As was expected the data collected which related to the FC “Terms and Conditions” suggested that across countries and transport organisations, notions of equal pay for women were, in the main, not a key factor for women as legislation within Spain, Ireland, UK, Scotland and Poland prohibits any organisation from paying men more for the same role as women.

“All the necessary mechanisms have been put in place to level the playing field for both men and women... the salary is also equalised”. Sofia F Train Driver Spain

“All my drivers are on the same rate of pay; all my engineers are on the same rate of pay so if a female came in, they would be on the same rate of pay. It’s about where they are on the skills set and training”. Caroline F Managing Director UK

However, the impact of shift patterns on female employees, particularly those who have caring or parenting responsibilities, was identified as a key factor relating to women’s career choices under the FC “Terms and Conditions”.

“...for me, for me it is shift work, so there is no comfort. We are treated the same. And we work in night and afternoon shifts. So, when it comes to our case, unfortunately we do not have any such distinction that the woman does not have to come for the night shift or come home late”. Beatrice F Ticket Inspector Poland

“Engineering do day shift, back shift night shift, drivers do crazy shifts they work 2 days of early shifts, 2 days of middle shifts and one late shift a week. So instead of having a week and a week and a week they do it day by day. We do have some family friendly working, but you really have to have a good reason to access it as you know our business is shift work”. Caroline F Managing Director UK

From an organisational perspective, participants at management and director level although, agreeing that shift work can be difficult for women and those men who have caring and parenting responsibilities, admitted that it was the nature of their business that dictated working hours.

“You can’t just say to a woman well ok you drive the lorry 9 -3, you can’t do that you don’t know what is going to happen in the day”. Louise Managing Director Transport Consultant UK

Whilst a member of HR staff pointed out that it would also not be a fair working environment if only women were allowed to

“And working late at night and working weekends, it’s not sociable hours if you have a family. But then it’s not fair to only give females the Monday to Friday 9 to 5 roles”. Nancy F HR UK

Participants from Spain discussed their experiences of having reduced working hours, and policies already being in place. However, one participant did suggest that in their experience they had more flexibility in their previous role than their current role.

“...go to work between 8 and 9 in the morning and finish his day between 17 and 18. The company offers few options for flexibility”. Samuel M Engineer Spain

The data collected suggests that shift work which is inherent in all passenger transport systems is a major factor for women when deciding on career prospects, and importantly in this case it is also a factor for men particularly those with parenting or caring responsibilities.

Job Characteristics - Flexible working

The provision of flexible working or having access to flexible working was a theme which emerged across all employment FC’s and in relation to both research questions related to women’s employment in the transport sector. One quote summed up the concept of flexible working particularly from a women’s perspective as being based on organisations acknowledging the differences between many women and men that impact on the daily lives of women and thus their working potential.

“I think there are, still we still need education for, you know, male managers so they know about periods menopause etc. You know things that can cause behavioural changes in women so that is a big thing”. Nancy F HR UK

Which was supported by a further participant who stated that.

“it’s about treating women when things happen in their life differently to men, so only women can have babies, that is true, but men can now get paternity leave so it’s trying to treat each group equally but reflecting that fact that women have slightly different challenges they maybe have elderly care or having babies and coming back again”. Frances F Managing Director UK

The data showed that both managers and frontline workers reported that it has traditionally been difficult to provide part time or flexibility within the transport sector, particularly in passenger transport, with claims that the business could not itself support part time arrangements.

“We try to be flexible in working time but with the type of work we do, you know the work content is the work content. If we can get two part time workers that would be fine. But we don’t have as many part time opportunities as full time”. Nancy F HR UK

“it’s not the company it’s the job. You can’t do half a run, it’s impossible. Because you are out you can’t get that, if I am in London and need to be back for the kids for a certain time, then I can’t do the London run. So, to be honest I don’t think it’s a job you can go into if you have personal commitments, personally I don’t think so”. Theresa F Coach Driver UK

“Flexible working is the way it’s going to go. For women flexible working and job share that is absolutely what women are looking for and increasingly what men are looking for as well” Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

However, a further comment by a Business Services Director of a passenger transport organisation cited that they have been implementing flexible and job share opportunities for their staff, including train drivers for some time and in the main, it was working well and had been successfully received by staff.

“...we don’t just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers. Now I have to say not one of our female train drivers has taken it up, but it’s there for everybody and they have that option. Actually, we have had 4 men take it up in job share because they are getting near retirement, they want to continue with their skills but don’t want to work full time”. Naomi F Business Services Director UK

The data collected from Poland suggested that at least in one of the transport organisations work has been done to ensure that flexibility, especially for parents is being provided and is available for men and women.

“Due to the scale of our company, we can have a very personal approach to our employees. For example, a married couple works for us, and the schedules of mother and father are adapted to their needs, so that it is possible to take care of the child. There were people who moved from another carrier to us, precisely because there was this flexibility.” Patryk M Transport Coordinator Poland

COVID and remote working during the recent lock downs was also discussed in terms of how positive it was in showing that people, men and women, were still able to carry out their roles working flexible hours at home and not be based in an office. The data suggests that many participants are keen to maintain the working arrangements put in place during lock down, and

that in some cases transport organisations have already seen the benefit of flexible and remote working.

“I believe that there’s nothing official or formal yet, but I understand that the company are in the process of drafting some working from home policies, so there might be an opportunity in the future even beyond Covid. Now there is at the moment anyway, there is working from home options for one day a week or whatever, but I believe that that policy is going to be enhanced and made more available. I think Covid, this situation, has been an opportunity for companies to actually see that people can be trusted, you don’t need to have them in your direct eyeline all the time, the work is being done”. Siobhan F Director Ireland

“But now what we have been saying all along is actually, you don’t have to be in an office sitting across from each other across a table every day in London. You can be just as effective in any virtual community. I think more and more people are realizing that now. My CEO came on to a call the other day to say that he understands that a lot of people are going to be apprehensive about going back to work in offices and he wants us to think about flexible working much more going forward because he said I will be working more flexibly than I ever thought before”. Crystal F Director UK

Job Characteristics - Training Provision

Opportunities for further training and equal access to training was also a factor that was important to women when considering career choices in the transport sector and is discussed fully in the Job Characteristics - HR Policies above.

Job Characteristics - Safety and security

The safety and security theme included data on the provision of PPE designed for women and not unisex, additional provisions for lone working and training in protection and awareness.

With regards to the provision of female designed PPE the data suggests that a majority of transport organisations are still providing what they refer to as unisex PPE which some frontline workers defined as “designed for men”

“The drivers uniform for example is unisex, but they mean it’s made for men. The uniform does not fit the way it’s supposed to, my safety boots don’t fit the way they are supposed to, they are men’s boots and that is not fair on women”. Grace F Train Driver (Trainer) UK

“Because the issue wasn’t particularly that the PPE was, it was just made for a man, so it’s made in a different way. So, for example I needed to go up a size in a jacket because I have boobs, you know so...so there is lots of things like that those suppliers are tackling now. I think females are really welcoming of that, they are more comfortable and safer with PPE suited to them”. Sharon F Manager UK

With one female engineer claiming they had to supply their own PPE equipment for their job and pay for it out of their own pocket.

“No so I had to get myself a young boy (laughs). Yeah, so that is not perfect”. Samantha F Engineering Director UK

The impact of not providing suitably designed PPE, tools or uniforms for female staff was summed up in one comment by a train driver who stated simply.

“If you are not worth the investment in a female specific uniform, do you really think you are valued?”
Hannah F Train Driver UK

Participants were asked directly “In what ways does your company promote a safe and secure working environment for women?”. Some appeared to have encourage managers to reflect on the current provisions of safety for women employees, with acknowledgements that there were no female specific safety policies in their organisation.

“With train operators and a lot of the safety issues have still to be addressed I get that”. Crystal F Director UK

One director stated quite clearly that in general there is a focus on the safety of passengers and how there until recently is the safety of female employees was not something they had considered.

“That was something we discussed the other day, I am involved the equality diversity and inclusion forum for the rail industry. And there was an update from the rail delivery group who was talking to us about safety on the railway for women. This was passengers, I was absolutely astounded that so many women suffer sexual assaults on the network”. Naomi F Business Services Director UK

In Ireland there was also no acknowledgement that there were any specific policies in place for female specific safety.

“Safety is one of the company core values because we are a railway and safety is at the heart of that. We have a really good safe track record, there hasn’t been anything in a long time. I’m not aware of any issue that could single out women safety”. Siobhan F Director Ireland

A general lack of focus for female safety was also discussed by frontline workers during their interviews with train drivers and haulage drivers highlighting their own personal experiences of incidences where they felt unsafe being women.

“I would say there is nothing in place from a woman’s perspective in the industry, not in road haulage. I think you have to be a particularly strong woman to cope if you ask me. I have had people make advances and deal with that on my own, when I was on long distance I had to park up, so I tried to make sure w here I parked up was an area that was safe”. Erin F Lorry Driver UK

“In my job I can be on a train for 11 hours on my own, I can be in sidings where there is no locks on the doors, I could be in my office on my own or out in the yard on my own, so yes, its things like that, I mean even at Scot Rail if you were on the last train you would be coming back, we are diver only in most of Scotland, so you would be getting to the end of your journey with god knows who on your train. I have come across it a few times you are walking through your train, and you come across somebody that has been stabbed and you are dealing with that on your own. You know that would put a lot of women and men off the job”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

And one Spanish tram driver admitting that it was only very recently that their organisation provided some training in dealing with harassment at work.

“This year, for the first time, workers have been trained in the area of harassment at work”. Sofia F Train Driver Spain

Job Characteristics - Negative attitude of colleagues

A further factor that is important in relation to women’s career choices is the perceived reaction of their male colleagues to having women alongside them in the transport sector. This theme was reported from women and men working across all roles and sectors with directors, senior managers and frontline managers claiming the negative attitude of men towards women employees in the transport sector can still be found even in the board room.

“I am in a meeting they say to me do you need anything to take notes. They presume I am secretarial support. They have done that all of my career. One man said how can a wee girl like you be running this. It’s been an evolution for XX they are going in the right direction one of the reasons I joined is because of the CEO”. Crystal F Director UK

“There are no female engineers or mechanics there haven’t been since I started here. There was a young female apprentice many years back and I heard that she left as the guys were not very nice to her”. Justine F Manager UK

“I worked for XX I went on the pay roll and my mentor who was a female left and the boys all ganged up on me because I was trying to implement change, you know proper business change and one day my business director came in and said you what we need to let you go, the guys just don’t like you. And that wasn’t just about me being a woman, that was about me being a strong woman and there is a difference. It was interesting that I did nothing wrong, I was bringing best practice to a business that needed it and they just didn’t want to hear it, particularly from a woman”. Frances F Director UK

In Poland, a participant revealed a similar story suggesting the negative attitude of males to female employees mirrors the wider sexism prevalent within and across Polish society.

“Sexism as a phenomenon is quite firmly established in our Polish society and in fact it is an almost everyday phenomenon. There are a few people I have mixed feelings. When I am working with some guy, and cooperation isn’t going well, because, unfortunately, he is makes me feel that he is talking with a woman, which makes me angry terribly. Such situations do happen, but not too often”. Mia F Office Worker Poland

“...probably a year or two ago, one of the female drivers expressed a desire to move to the workshop department. The company did not create any problems either. She was transferred ...however, she encountered a lot of resistance from other colleagues. They had to break a certain barrier and such a stereotype in their male environment - it was an intrusion”. Leon M Multi-Modal Transport Coordinator Poland

“It seems to me that these situations occur more often at lower levels. I mean drivers in particular, rather than office workers. I know of one such case, an argument between our female instructor and a male driver. The driver was from a different company. Basically, he said "I will not obey your commands." But in our work the supervisors sometimes have to give out orders to drivers from other companies and sometimes they get: "you are not from our company, so I will not follow your instructions". Here, an additional

argument was that "you are a woman", but that was one incident in two years, so is that a lot or a little?"
 Patryk M Transport Coordinator Poland

"I had a conversation with xx and we were saying like how do you get behind that? How do you change the mindset of a man in a boardroom to say 'no'? It's not cool. That behaviour is not cool because they don't even realize they're doing it". Elaine F HR Ireland

Personal Circumstances - Caring/Parenting Responsibilities

The data collected showed that single largest factor to affect women and their career choices was in relation to their role as a parent or primary care giver. The effects on employment of being a parent or having caring responsibilities were reported in such wide depth that they cover all the FC's highlighted here.

Personal Circumstances - Economic deprivation (living area social network etc)

In terms of economic deprivation, the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Personal Circumstances - Transport access to workplace

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics – Skills

In terms of transport access to work place the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Adaptability – Attitude to work

In terms of adaptability and attitude to work the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC. However, there are themes based on flexibility of working location and hours and the impact of shift work that can be read in other sections here.

Individual Characteristics - Educational attainment

In terms of educational attainment as a key factor for women when considering a career in the transport sector, it was noted across partner countries that this in the main related to a traditional low number of young females studying STEM or Technical subjects that underpin many transport sector roles.

"There is no cultural predisposition on the part of women to study engineering, there is a mental framework, caused by a lack of references of women working in the sector". Lucía F Spain

"Well, here you need to educate yourself in this direction. Rather, car and technical education is completely dominated by men. Therefore, there is no way for someone to learn this profession". Leon M Multi-Modal Transport Coordinator Poland

“The social and cultural barriers are related to education, as there are usually more women in engineering careers, so the likelihood of more women working in the transport sector is already reduced from the beginning”. Samuel M Engineer Spain

However, one of the Polish participants raised an interesting concept with regards to education stating that there were no educational qualifications for their role and everything they learned was on the job and organisational specific.

“Maybe there are no social or cultural barriers, but when I started working in the place where I work now, the things I learnt here were impossible to learn at any university, no one in fact, from the outside, who came, would be able to do it, because it is a job that is specific to the ZTM, there are dedicated programs. And really only by sitting at the desk and being tutored by someone who knows them, can one learn the job. So, it's really just a matter of wanting to do it”. Magda F Passenger Information Poland

To address this situation many organisations stated that they now attend open days and career days at schools and colleges, accessing young people before they become graduates, to help direct and support girls into the sector.

“It’s getting access to the schools, finding ways to get access into schools you know to get people like me in to talk to them and unless it’s facilitated in some way a lot of schools won’t get it”. Frances F Managing Director UK

“To attract women actually you need to go right into schools. And when you go into schools they don’t really know about transport, they don’t, they don’t know about they don’t even think about how goods get from A to B and that includes the teachers. So, when you go into schools now, it’s getting down to that level and it’s going to take quite a time for it to come”. Louise F Managing Director Transport Consultant UK

“What we need to be doing is engaging young women and young girls when their school age and when they're picking their coursework you know that they're going to be doing or University places”. Irene F Manager Ireland

Individual Characteristics - Health status and wellbeing.

In terms of health status and wellbeing the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Individual Characteristics - Demographic (age ethnicity etc)

In terms of the effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.) the interviews and focus group discussions conducted produced no data on this FC.

Findings emerging from the data not included in FC’s.

Findings which emerged from the data that were not previously accounted for in the FC’s relating to the key factors influencing career choices for women, included:

The individual characteristics/personality of the women

Many participants when discussing women employed in the transport sector provided caveats to their statements suggesting that the current working environments and cultures in which they worked would not be attractive to all women.

“I think credibility is a massive thing, showing value in the work you do, having to prove yourself almost. Having to work twice as hard as a man... If a female acts soft, they are seen as weak and if they appear hard and more like a male then you are a bitch”. Nancy F HR UK

The reasons given were based on both structural and individual causes such as the existing male dominated organisational culture within the transport sector, woman having little or no existing credibility in the transport sector, workspaces being cold and dirty and the individual personality of some women who maybe were not “thick skinned” enough to deal with the environment.

“...there is probably I don’t know if it’s strength but you have to be able to hold your own, yeah have thick skin, because it can be intimidating if you’re in a room full of men which I have been, it can be intimidating if you allow it to be but it’s something that I found myself dealing with since I was about 25/26, so I’ve got used to it” Siobhan F Director Ireland

“A lot of people I know have developed very male dominated traits and have become bullies to other women who they think are rising starts in the business. So yes...you have to be thick skinned to work in transport and that is without a shadow of a doubt”. Crystal F Director UK

The comments regarding individual personality traits, and thick skinned as being an attribute for women working in transport came from a variety of participants from across both frontline and management roles and came from mainly UK Scotland and Ireland.

“I look back and see that I tried to be accepted as one of the boys and talk that talk and make sure that any of the jokes that were given were not offensive to me and grow that thick skin”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

A will to Change.

Many of the participants when discussing factors that influence women’s career choices in respect to employment in the transport sector claimed that was already an acknowledgement that things had to change to support women as employees in the sector and to encourage more women to come into the sector.

“I do think there is more of a will to change but it’s very much company dependent. Very few train drivers chose who they want to work for based on the salary, I could earn 20% more if I worked at a company next door, that is not why people chose companies now they chose companies based on how they are going to be looked after, how they are valued and if companies just understood that”. Hannah F Train Driver UK

“XX are very proactive; we have a very diverse group of people who have gotten together to try and champion it... I think for me it’s starts with the top and getting them to put it at the top of their agenda and I mean, even at the moment we have got 5 devolved regions within the company and none of them have a regional MD that is a female”. Crystal F Director UK

“I mean Network Rail, Northern, LNER simply because of their contractual conditions are, but other people aren’t and therefore I don’t think they are challenging themselves enough to say we would like it to be better but we are not really sure how to do it. Things are too difficult. I think there is a lot of willingness, I sit on the railway EDI working group, but a lot of the comments that I hear from people who do not sit on an executive or sit on a board who are that meeting, are this isn’t a priority for our board, this isn’t a priority for our executive”. Naomi F Business Services Director UK

The requirement for more women in senior roles to help improve and promote female recruitment across the transport sector was discussed widely with multiple participants from across roles in the UK/Scotland claiming that currently the majority of senior executive board members in the sector were “male, pale and stale”, which according to the Oxford Dictionary of Human Resource Management (2017) refers to “a phrase uttered to condemn an organization for being dominated by white, middle-aged men. It is often used in relation to corporate board composition but can be applied to any collection of people that fails to reflect a diverse sex, racial, and age mix” (ibid 2017: online)

“When you look at the people who are getting promoted or the people who are in senior management or people of influence, a lot of them are male, pale and stale”. Crystal F Director UK

“When the media don’t portray the sector well, when you have people working who are “pale, male, stale” middle to old age, how attractive is that?” Louise F Managing Director UK

Annex 10 Modes of Transport Represented

Annex I | Job Level and Title of Participants

